

Toolkit and Policy Recommendation Handbook

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Across Europe, **backlash against gender equality** is increasingly mainstream, shaping political competition and sometimes policy. It is closely tied to the rise of right-wing populist parties, which mobilise voters through opposition to gender and sexual equality. For EU actors, the challenge is both defending equality and addressing the conditions that make these narratives persuasive.

How to use this Handbook

This Handbook is designed as a practical policy tool:

Part I develops the analytical framework to understand the drivers of political dissatisfaction.

Part II operationalises this framework by establishing the methodological approach through which these insights are translated into policy-relevant analysis across key domains.

Part III presents the resulting **policy recommendations**, derived from the application of this approach to each domain.

Readers seeking immediate guidance may focus on Part III, while Parts I and II provide the conceptual and empirical foundations underpinning the recommendations. More detailed domain analysis and supporting material are available in the supplementary material available online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

This Handbook provides a clear answer: backlash is not primarily driven by ideological rejection of gender equality, but by **unmet material needs and perceived failures of political responsiveness**. Gender matters—but not in the way often assumed.

Based on extensive evidence from the UNTWIST project—including a large-scale survey, focus groups with Right Wing Populist Parties (RWPP) switcher voters, and participatory workshops across multiple Member States—the findings show that citizens' dissatisfaction is rooted in everyday experiences of economic insecurity, pressure on care systems, limited access to services, and declining trust in institutions. These grievances are **structured by gender**, but they are not initially expressed as opposition to gender equality.

To capture this dynamic, the Handbook introduces two key concepts:

Gendered positional deprivation: how material insecurity and social change are experienced differently by women and men across their life course.

Losers of feminism: a contingent political outcome in which these experiences are later interpreted—often through political narratives—as losses attributed to gender equality.

The evidence identifies a clear sequence:

Material insecurity and institutional gaps generate dissatisfaction;

Gendered positional deprivation shapes how this dissatisfaction is lived;

Political narratives may then redirect grievances against gender equality.

This means that backlash is not the starting point—it is the result of unresolved social and economic tensions.

Five policy domains emerge as critical across countries:

Access to **quality healthcare**.

Access to **affordable housing and social services**.

Work–family balance.

Care systems for children, older people, and dependents.

Labour market integration and security.

These are the areas where citizens most directly experience fairness—or its absence. Persistent shortcomings in these domains create the conditions under which dissatisfaction can be politicised.

A central finding is a **representation gap**: while political agendas address welfare issues, they often fail to reflect the **gendered realities of citizens' everyday lives**. This weakens democratic responsiveness and opens space for actors who offer simplified or symbolic explanations.

What this means for policymakers:

Do not treat backlash as primarily ideological. It is rooted in material conditions and institutional performance.

Strengthen policy delivery in core welfare domains. Visible improvements in healthcare, housing, care, and employment are key to rebuilding trust.

Integrate gender into mainstream policy design. Not as an add-on, but as a lens to understand how needs differ across populations.

Address life-course inequalities. Care burdens, labour precarity, and work–family tensions are central drivers of dissatisfaction.

Close the gap between policy outputs and lived experience. Responsiveness must be tangible and felt in everyday life.

The strategic implication is clear: **the most effective way to counter backlash against gender equality is to deliver better policies**. By addressing the material roots of dissatisfaction—and their gendered dimensions—the EU can reduce the appeal of divisive narratives, strengthen democratic legitimacy, and reinforce its foundational commitment to equality.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AMIF — Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund

COM — European Commission official document (numbered proposals, communications, or reports)

COVID-19 — Coronavirus Disease 2019

DE — Germany

DG EAC — Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture

DG EMPL — Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion

DG ENER — Directorate-General for Energy

DG JUST — Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers

DG SANTE — Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety

DK — Denmark

ECEC — Early Childhood Education and Care

ECDC — European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control

EDIP — European Defence Industry Programme

EGF — European Globalisation Adjustment Fund

EHDS — European Health Data Space

EIB — European Investment Bank

EIGE — European Institute for Gender Equality

ELA — European Labour Authority

EMA — European Medicines Agency

EMCO — Employment Committee

EMPL — European Parliament Committee on Employment and Social Affairs

ENVI — European Parliament Committee on the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety

EPBD — Energy Performance of Buildings Directive

EPSCO — Employment, Social Policy, Health and Consumer Affairs Council (configuration of the Council of the EU)

ERDF — European Regional Development Fund

ES — Spain

ESF — European Social Fund

ESF+ — European Social Fund Plus

EU — European Union

EU-SILC — European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions

EU4Health — EU4Health Programme

EURES — European Employment Services

EWCS — European Working Conditions Survey

FEMM — European Parliament Committee on Women’s Rights and Gender Equality
GDP — Gross Domestic Product
HaDEA — European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HERA — Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority
HOUS — European Parliament Special Committee on the Housing Crisis in the European Union
HTA — Health Technology Assessment
HU — Hungary
ICT — Information and Communication Technologies
LFS — Labour Force Survey
LTC — Long-Term Care
MARPOR — Manifesto Research on Political Representation
MCDA — Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
MFF — Multiannual Financial Framework
MGA — Manifestoes Gender Analysis
ML — Mainstream Left
MR — Mainstream Right
MS — Member State(s)
NEET — Not in Employment, Education or Training
NHS — National Health Service
OECD — Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PES — Public Employment Services
RRF — Recovery and Resilience Facility
RWPP — Right-Wing Populist Parties
SPC — Social Protection Committee
STR — Short-Term Rental
TFEU — Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
UK — United Kingdom

INTRODUCTION

Across Europe, political dissatisfaction has become a defining feature of contemporary democratic life. While this dissatisfaction takes multiple forms, one of its most visible political expressions has been the growing support for right-wing populist parties (RWPPs), often accompanied by a **backlash against gender equality** and the rights of women and girls. For European policymakers¹, this development raises a dual challenge: how to uphold gender equality as a core value of the European Union, and how to respond effectively to the social and economic grievances that underpin political discontent.

This Handbook addresses this challenge by providing an integrated analytical and policy-oriented framework to understand and respond to the drivers of political dissatisfaction from a gender perspective. It is based on the research carried out within the **UNTWIST project**, which combines large-scale quantitative data, qualitative insights from focus groups with voters, and participatory workshops across multiple Member States (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary). By bringing these strands together, the Handbook moves beyond simplified explanations of political behaviour and offers a nuanced account of how material conditions, institutional performance, and gendered social positions interact in shaping citizens' perceptions and political choices.

A central premise of the Handbook is that **backlash against gender equality cannot be adequately understood as a purely ideological phenomenon**. Instead, it emerges from the intersection of unmet material needs, perceived institutional failures, and the ways in which these experiences are lived and interpreted through gendered social positions. The concepts of **gendered positional deprivation** and **losers of feminism** provide the analytical tools to capture these dynamics, highlighting both the structural roots of dissatisfaction and the conditions under which it may be politically mobilised against gender equality.

The Handbook is structured in three parts, each serving a distinct but complementary function.

Part I develops the analytical framework to understand the drivers of political dissatisfaction.

Part II operationalises this framework by establishing the methodological approach through which these insights are translated into policy-relevant analysis across key domains.

Part III presents the resulting **policy recommendations**, derived from the application of this approach to each domain.

These three parts are designed to be used flexibly. Readers primarily interested in policy action may turn directly to Part III, while Parts I and II provide the conceptual

¹ These recommendations are primarily addressed to EU policymakers because the European Union provides the overarching legal, financial, and strategic framework within which many relevant policies are coordinated, funded, or regulated across Member States. At the same time, many proposals are also applicable to national, regional, and local authorities, which retain key responsibilities for policy design, implementation, and service delivery within their respective competences.

grounding and empirical evidence that support the recommendations. Taken together, they offer a coherent framework that links diagnosis and action. More detailed domain analysis and supporting material are available in the supplementary material online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

The analysis **identifies five core domains** in which citizens most directly experience fairness, recognition, and institutional support: healthcare, housing and social services, work–family balance, care systems, and labour market integration. These domains constitute the everyday arenas in which political dissatisfaction takes shape. Persistent shortcomings in these areas generate forms of gendered positional deprivation that, when left unaddressed, create favourable **conditions for the politicisation of grievances and the emergence of backlash narratives**.

The central implication for EU policymakers is that strengthening gender equality requires **more than normative commitment or discursive defence**. It requires improving the material and institutional conditions that shape citizens' everyday lives, and ensuring that policies are responsive to the gendered dimensions of these experiences. By **addressing the root causes of dissatisfaction**—rather than only its political expressions—policymakers can reduce the appeal of divisive narratives, reinforce democratic legitimacy, and advance the Union's foundational commitment to equality.

PART I – CITIZEN NEEDS, POLITICAL DYNAMICS AND EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE

This part presents the empirical and analytical foundations of the study. It brings together comparative evidence on citizens' concerns, political dynamics, and policy performance across six countries (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary), with particular attention to the factors shaping voter dissatisfaction and political realignment. The country selection combines EU Member States with two non-EU cases to provide a broader comparative perspective, helping to distinguish dynamics linked to EU governance contexts from wider transnational trends. The objective is to identify the substantive issues that structure everyday experiences and to **establish a robust basis for subsequent policy analysis and recommendations** at the EU level, where common frameworks for coordination, funding, and regulatory action can be mobilised alongside national competences.

1. Analytical Framework and Political Problem

Political Challenge: Backlash Against Gender Equality and RWPP

In recent years, a backlash against gender equality and the rights of women and girls has become increasingly visible across Europe. While in some contexts this backlash remains primarily discursive, in others it has translated into concrete political initiatives that challenge established commitments to gender equality.² These developments are particularly consequential in the European Union, where gender equality constitutes a foundational value embedded in the Treaty on European Union and supported by an extensive regulatory and monitoring framework.

This backlash is closely linked to the sustained rise of right-wing populist parties (RWPP), whose electoral support has expanded significantly over recent decades and whose participation in government has become increasingly common. These parties systematically mobilise opposition to gender and sexual equality as part of their political platforms. Empirical evidence shows that anti-gender rhetoric becomes more salient and socially legitimate in contexts where RWPP gain parliamentary representation or governing power.³

Explanatory Gap: Limits of Existing Accounts

Understanding this development requires moving beyond aggregate electoral trends to examine who supports these parties and why. The electoral success of RWPP is not evenly distributed across the electorate but rooted in the mobilisation of specific groups

² United Nations Research Institute for Social Development & UN Women. (2025). Understanding Backlash Against Gender Equality: Evidence, Trends and Policy Responses. UNRISD / UN Women. Available at: <https://cdn.unrisd.org/assets/library/reports/2025/understanding-backlash-2025-unrisd-un-women.pdf>.

³ Oxfam France. (2024, March 8). Gender equality in Europe: Back, or the future? Oxfam France. Available at: <https://www.oxfamfrance.org/app/uploads/2024/03/Note-contextuelle-Gender-equality-in-Europe-back-or-the-future.pdf>.

of voters who experience social, economic, and political change as a loss, displacement, or misrecognition. Existing research has highlighted the role of the so-called “**losers of globalization**”⁴ in this process. According to this perspective, citizens who perceive themselves as negatively affected by economic restructuring, labour market transformations, or cultural change are more likely to withdraw support from mainstream parties and turn to RWPP as a form of protest.

While highly influential, this framework remains incomplete. It rests on the implicit assumption that the consequences of globalization are experienced in broadly similar ways across social groups and that processes of grievance formation are largely gender-neutral. It also assumes that political reactions to perceived losses follow comparable logics for men and women. These assumptions limit its explanatory power. Empirical evidence shows that the classical losers-of-globalization hypothesis performs far better in explaining men’s support for RWPP than women’s, suggesting that similar structural conditions do not translate into identical political outcomes.⁵

More fundamentally, the framework overlooks how material insecurity and social change are mediated by gendered social positions. Labour markets, care regimes, and social expectations are structured along gender lines, shaping how individuals experience insecurity, evaluate their situation, and interpret change. As a result, economic vulnerability and political dissatisfaction are not simply distributed unevenly—they are experienced differently by men and women and embedded in distinct life-course trajectories.⁶

This limitation becomes particularly consequential when considering one of the defining features of contemporary RWPP mobilisation: the centrality of opposition to gender equality and feminism.⁷ Anti-feminist and anti-gender discourses cannot be fully explained by economic dislocation alone. They are rooted in perceived shifts in social status, recognition, and entitlement, which are themselves structured by changing gender relations. Incorporating a gender-sensitive perspective is therefore essential not only to capture differentiated experiences of insecurity but also to explain how these experiences become politically mobilised.

Analytical Innovation: A Gender-Sensitive Framework

Against this backdrop, the UNTWIST project refines the losers-of-globalization framework by introducing a gender-sensitive analytical approach. Rather than treating those affected by structural transformation as a homogeneous group, the project starts from the premise that gendered social positions mediate both material conditions and

⁴ Kriesi, H. (2014). The Populist Challenge. *West European Politics*, 37(2), 361-378. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2014.887879>.

⁵ Fontana, M.-C., Sidler, A., & Hardmeier, S. (2006). The ‘New Right’ Vote: An Analysis of the Gender Gap in the Vote Choice for the SVP. *Swiss Political Science Review*, 12(4), 243-271. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1662-6370.2006.tb00067.x>.

⁶ Dietze, G., & Roth, J. (2020). Right-Wing Populism and Gender. *European Perspectives and Beyond* (G. Dietze & J. Roth, Eds.). Transcript Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203793510-5>.

⁷ Kováts, E., & Pöim, M. (2015). Gender as a symbolic glue. The position and role of conservative and far right parties in the anti-gender mobilization in Europe (E. Kováts & M. Pöim, Eds.). *Foundation for European Progressive Studies - Friedrich Ebert Stiftung*. Available at: <http://www.fes.de/gender/publikationen.php>.

political responses. Economic restructuring, labour market flexibilisation, and changes in welfare provision intersect with gendered divisions of labour and care responsibilities, shaping how grievances are experienced and articulated.⁸

Two key concepts are introduced to capture these dynamics: gendered positional deprivation and losers of feminism.

Gendered positional deprivation refers to situations in which individuals perceive a deterioration in their life chances, status, or recognition, and interpret this decline in relation to their gender group. It builds on classic notions of relative deprivation⁹ but introduces a crucial positional dimension: individuals evaluate their situation not only in absolute terms, but in comparison to others and over time, asking whether people like them are doing worse than before or worse than they should be. By foregrounding gender as a key axis of comparison, this concept captures how similar structural conditions can generate different subjective experiences and political responses among men and women.

Importantly, gendered positional deprivation does not manifest symmetrically. For many women, it is rooted in cumulative structural pressures, including labour market precarity, care responsibilities, and insufficient institutional support. These experiences are often continuous, relational, and embedded in everyday life. For many men, by contrast, deprivation tends to be mediated through indirect processes of status erosion, linked to changing labour markets and shifting family roles. These experiences are more often interpreted in terms of lost stability, fairness, or recognition, rather than explicitly in gendered terms.

Building on this foundation, the concept of **losers of feminism** captures a more specific and politically consequential dynamic. It refers to individuals who not only experience gendered grievances but also attribute these grievances to feminism or gender equality policies. This attributional shift is critical: it transforms diffuse experiences of insecurity into targeted political resentment. In this process, right-wing populist actors play a central role by providing interpretive frames that present gender equality as a zero-sum process and feminism as a source of loss, injustice, or social disorder.

This distinction between experience and attribution is essential. Gendered positional deprivation refers to lived perceptions of insecurity and misrecognition, whereas losers of feminism captures a particular way of interpreting and politicising these experiences. The two do not necessarily coincide. Individuals may experience gendered grievances without attributing them to feminism, and such attribution may emerge only later, shaped by political discourse and framing.

Evidence: How Grievances Translate into Support

Empirical evidence from the UNTWIST project supports the relevance of this distinction. Gendered positional deprivation is relatively widespread across Europe,

⁸ Ruiz Jiménez, A. M., Ortiz Barquero, P., & Zambrana Pérez, R. (2023). Theorising gender voting gaps through Gender Positional Deprivation. <http://hdl.handle.net/10433/16611>.

⁹ Relative deprivation refers to the perception of being disadvantaged compared with relevant others or with what one believes one is entitled to, generating feelings of grievance and injustice. Runciman, W. G. (1966). *Relative Deprivation and Social Justice: A Study of Attitudes to Social Inequality in Twentieth-Century England*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.

affecting a substantial proportion of both women and men. However, it is associated with different political outcomes. Among men, experiences of gendered positional deprivation are linked to a higher likelihood of supporting right-wing parties. Among women, similar experiences are more often associated with support for left-wing alternatives. This divergence highlights the importance of moving beyond gender-blind accounts of relative deprivation.¹⁰

By contrast, losers of feminism constitute a smaller but politically decisive group. Although numerically limited, this group emerges as one of the strongest predictors of proximity to RWPP. It is disproportionately male and characterised by a clear attribution of perceived losses to feminism or gender equality policies. Among women, a similar shift toward RWPP support is observed only when gendered positional deprivation is combined with explicit anti-feminist attribution. This confirms that attribution processes play a crucial role in translating lived grievances into political behaviour.

Taken together, these findings point to a broader causal sequence linking structural change to political realignment. Material transformations associated with globalization—such as economic insecurity, labour market instability, and pressures on care systems—generate experiences of dissatisfaction and perceived decline. These experiences are shaped by gendered social positions and give rise to gendered positional deprivation. However, they do not initially take the form of ideological opposition to gender equality. Rather, they are primarily experienced as material insecurity, institutional failure, or lack of recognition.

Political attribution typically occurs at a later stage. It is through the intervention of political actors, particularly RWPP, that these experiences are reframed and organised into coherent narratives of blame. In this process, feminism and gender equality policies may be constructed as causes of perceived loss, giving rise to the category of losers of feminism. This transformation is not automatic but contingent, depending on the availability and resonance of political frames.

Policy Relevance: Why This Matters for Representation and Responsiveness

This temporal sequencing has important implications. It suggests that support for RWPP is driven less by prior ideological opposition to gender equality than by unresolved material grievances and deficits of political representation. Gender-related conflicts emerge not as primary drivers but as secondary interpretations of broader dissatisfaction.

The analytical framework developed here therefore situates gendered positional deprivation and losers of feminism as central mechanisms linking structural change, lived experience, and political mobilisation. By integrating gender into the analysis of relative deprivation, it provides a more comprehensive understanding of why RWPP attract support from specific groups of voters and how gendered grievances can become politically salient.

This perspective also informs the structure of the analysis that follows. The next sections examine how these dynamics unfold empirically, focusing first on the

¹⁰ Ortiz Barquero, P. & Romero Portillo D. (2026) Deliverable 8.1 of the UNTWIST project: Summary of Findings (WP8). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/19203938>. Survey database is available in Zenodo: Ruiz Jiménez, A. M., Bartolomé Peral, E., & Sendra, M. (2025). UNTWIST representative survey on gendered political behaviour in six European countries, with RWPP voters oversampling (Versión 01) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17018531>.

narratives of RWPP switcher voters and then on the key domains in which grievances take shape. Together, these analyses provide the basis for identifying the representational gaps that enable blame-based mobilisation and for formulating policy recommendations aimed at addressing the underlying sources of dissatisfaction.

2. From Material Grievances to Political Realignment

Why RWPP Switcher Voters Matter

For methodological and analytical reasons, the UNTWIST project deliberately concentrated its qualitative investigation on right-wing populist party (RWPP) switcher voters—that is, individuals who shifted from supporting mainstream parties to voting for RWPP in the most recent electoral cycle. This focus was designed to deepen understanding of how material grievances evolve into political realignment, particularly in relation to gendered positional deprivation and the potential emergence of losers of feminism.

Concentrating on switchers offers a distinct analytical advantage. Whereas stable RWPP voters may be guided by long-standing ideological commitments or entrenched identities, switchers have undergone a discernible rupture in political preference. Their trajectories therefore allow for reconstructing a temporal sequence of political change, capturing both the conditions that generated dissatisfaction and the processes through which this dissatisfaction became politically meaningful.

How Grievances Evolve into Political Change

This perspective enables a more fine-grained analysis of how grievances are formed, experienced, and subsequently politicised. In contrast to approaches that treat RWPP support as the direct expression of ideological positions, the UNTWIST framework distinguishes analytically between experience and attribution. Voters first experience forms of insecurity, strain, or perceived decline; only later are these experiences interpreted through political frames that assign responsibility and meaning.

Within this framework, the analysis focuses on whether gender-related grievances are present at the moment of electoral switching, or whether they emerge only after political realignment as part of a process of attribution. This distinction is crucial for understanding the role of gender in RWPP support: whether gendered grievances function as primary drivers of political change or as secondary interpretations of broader dissatisfaction.

Qualitative methods are particularly well suited to capturing this process. While quantitative analyses can identify correlations between socioeconomic conditions, gender attitudes, and voting behaviour, they are less effective in reconstructing how individuals themselves interpret and sequence their experiences. By contrast, focus group discussions provide access to voters' narratives, allowing us to trace how material grievances are articulated, prioritised, and connected to political choices over time.

The analysis of 18 focus groups across Europe,¹¹ involving RWPP switcher voters, shows that the politicisation of grievances follows a structured but non-linear sequence. Across countries (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary), participants' accounts consistently point to a first stage characterised by material and institutional dissatisfaction. Experiences of economic insecurity, declining social protection, institutional inefficiency, and perceived unfairness dominate explanations of why mainstream political parties lost credibility. These grievances are expressed in terms of everyday life—cost of living, access to services, work instability—rather than in ideological or identity-based terms.

Three Stages of Political Realignment

Importantly, at this initial stage, grievances are not articulated as conflicts over gender equality or feminism. Even when experiences are clearly gendered—such as care burdens, work–family tensions, or labour market precarity—they are not framed as gender-political claims by focus groups participants. Instead, they are expressed as practical problems, structural constraints, or failures of public provision. This confirms that gendered positional deprivation operates first and foremost at the level of lived experience, not as an explicit ideological stance.

A second stage emerges in the form of diffuse dissatisfaction and disorientation. Participants describe a growing sense of instability, loss of control, and declining fairness, often accompanied by distrust in political institutions and elites. This dissatisfaction is structured by gendered social positions but articulated differently by men and women. Women tend to frame discontent through concrete, relational experiences—care responsibilities, time scarcity, and institutional neglect—while men more often express dissatisfaction in abstract or systemic terms, such as unfairness, loss of status, or erosion of social order.

Crucially, this stage remains largely pre-political in attributional terms. Although grievances are clearly present and often intense, they are not yet organised around specific political explanations or targets. In particular, explicit attribution of these experiences to feminism or gender equality policies is rare. This reinforces the distinction between gendered positional deprivation as an experiential condition and losers of feminism as an attributional outcome.

Political realignment occurs in a third stage, in which dissatisfaction becomes susceptible to political framing. RWPP do not primarily generate grievances; rather, they provide interpretive frameworks that reorganise existing dissatisfaction into coherent narratives of blame. These narratives identify responsible actors—elites, institutions, or social groups—and, in some cases, construct gender equality or feminism as sources of perceived loss.

Gendered Pathways of Attribution

The findings show that this process of attribution is conditional and context-dependent. Across countries (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary), attitudes

¹¹ Ortiz Barquero, P., & Ruiz Jiménez, A. M. (2024). Deliverable 2.3 of the UNTWIST project: Summary of findings. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14176481>. Anonimized transcriptions of the focus groups are available in Zenodo: Ruiz Jiménez, A., & González Fernández, M. T. (2024). Anonymised transcriptions (local and translated versions) of 18 Focus Groups with RWPP voters in Spain, UK, Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Switzerland [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11200055>.

toward feminism are shaped less by explicit ideological opposition than by lived experience and evaluations of social change. Women tend to approach feminism pragmatically and ambivalently: while few strongly identify with the label, many articulate concerns aligned with feminist critiques, particularly around fairness, recognition, and care. Men, by contrast, engage with feminism more distantly, often treating it as an external discourse rather than as a framework for interpreting their own experiences.

This asymmetry is reflected in the temporal sequencing of attribution. Among men, focus group's evidence suggests that experiences of insecurity and disorientation are initially articulated in non-gendered terms. Only subsequently—through exposure to political discourse—can these experiences be reframed as gendered grievances and, in some cases, attributed to feminism. This corresponds to the emergence of losers of feminism as an attributional category rather than an initial condition.

Among women, by contrast, gendered positional deprivation is often already present at the moment of political realignment, rooted in cumulative experiences of care overload, labour market constraints, and insufficient institutional support. However, even in these cases, attribution to feminism is not automatic. Women's grievances are more likely to be expressed as demands for support, recognition, and fairness, and only translate into RWPP support when combined with explicit attributional frames.

Taken together, these findings support a clear causal sequence (Figure 1):

Figure 1. From material grievances to political realignment

Material insecurity and institutional shortcomings generate dissatisfaction structured by gendered social positions. This dissatisfaction, however, does not initially take the form of ideological opposition to gender equality. Political attribution occurs later, when grievances are interpreted through available discursive frames, particularly those provided by RWPP.

This sequencing has important implications for understanding RWPP mobilisation. It indicates that support for these parties is driven less by prior ideological commitments than by unresolved material grievances and deficits of political responsiveness.

Gender-related conflicts emerge primarily as secondary interpretations, rather than as original drivers, of political dissatisfaction.

This dynamic also helps explain the limited salience of explicit anti-feminist narratives in switchers' accounts, despite their strong presence in RWPP discourse. While such narratives can become influential, they typically operate as retrospective frames that organise and legitimise pre-existing dissatisfaction, rather than as initial motivations for political change.

Policy Implications for Democratic Responsiveness

From a policy perspective, these findings are particularly significant. If political attribution depends on prior conditions of dissatisfaction, then addressing the material sources of insecurity can disrupt the processes through which grievances are politicised. Reducing economic precarity, strengthening care infrastructures, and improving institutional responsiveness can limit the resonance of blame-based narratives by narrowing the gap between lived experience and political representation.

Rather than treating gender equality primarily as a symbolic or cultural issue, the analysis highlights the importance of materially grounded, gender-responsive policies. By addressing the structural conditions that generate gendered positional deprivation, such policies can reduce both lived dissatisfaction and the likelihood that these experiences will be reframed through exclusionary or antagonistic political narratives.

In this sense, the analysis of RWPP switcher voters confirms the central insight of the UNTWIST framework: gendered grievances are not inherently political in their origin. They become politically consequential through processes of interpretation, attribution, and mobilisation. Understanding this sequence is essential for designing policy responses capable not only of addressing inequality, but also of reducing the conditions under which dissatisfaction can be transformed into support for right-wing populism.

3. Five Domains of Gendered Positional Deprivation

Why These Domains Matter

Building on the preceding analysis of how material dissatisfaction is translated into political grievance and, in some cases, into RWPP narratives that attribute responsibility to external actors such as feminism, often by mobilising experiences of gendered positional deprivation, the UNTWIST project draws on complementary empirical evidence to identify where these grievances most consistently originate. By combining the focus group findings with a representative survey conducted between

2024 and 2025¹² and data from 12 participatory workshops held in 2025¹³, we capture both the lived experiences articulated by citizens and the broader, cross-national patterns that shape perceptions of political (mis)representation and relative deprivation.

This integrated empirical approach allows us to move from the dynamics of grievance formation to the identification of the most salient and transversal material arenas in which gendered positional deprivation is produced, experienced, and evaluated, and where shortcomings in political responsiveness generate the conditions under which RWPP attribution and scapegoating can later resonate.

How the Five Domains Were Identified

We identified five key topics that anchor feelings of relative deprivation. Several criteria guided the selection of these topics (Figure 2): first, each issue was identified as a significant concern by the largest share of RWPP voters in our survey; second, it consistently emerged as a salient source of grievances across focus groups with RWPP switcher voters in all participating countries (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary); third, it was also raised during the participatory workshops. At the same time, we selected topics that are salient across a substantial proportion of mainstream voters on both the left and the right, in order to identify areas where improving political responsiveness could broaden the appeal of mainstream parties.

¹² Ruiz Jiménez, A. M., Bartolomé Peral, E., & Sendra, M. (2025). UNTWIST representative survey on gendered political behaviour in six European countries, with RWPP voters oversampling (Versión 01) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17018531>.

This is a large-scale, cross-national survey (2024–2025) covering over 9,500 respondents across six European countries. The survey uses probability-based sampling and post-stratification weighting to ensure that results are representative of national populations. Rigorous quality controls and validation against established datasets further ensure the robustness and reliability of the findings. A preliminary analysis of the survey can be found in: Ortiz, P., & Romero-Portillo, D. (2026). Deliverable 8.1 of the UNTWIST project: Summary of findings (WP8). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19203938>. See also: Ruiz Jiménez, A. M., & Romero-Portillo, D. (2026). UNTWIST briefing 06: Distinct Grievance Pathways to the Populist Radical Right: The Gender Dimension in Contemporary Europe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19208292>.

¹³ UNTWIST conducted 12 participatory workshops in 2025 across six European countries, involving over 100 participants with diverse socio-demographic and political profiles. Building on prior survey and focus group findings, the workshops were designed both to validate the relevance of previously identified grievances across broader and politically mixed groups and to support the co-creation of policy-relevant insights through structured deliberation. Conducted under a common protocol with trained facilitators and ethical oversight, the high degree of convergence across countries reinforces the robustness and reliability of the findings for policy design.

Blassel, R., & Veronesi, L. (2026). Deliverable 9.1 of the UNTWIST project: Technical summarise of workshops. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19204208>. Blassel, R., & Veronesi, L. (2026). Deliverable 9.2 of the UNTWIST project: Final summary of policy recommendations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19202249>. Anonimized transcriptions of the participatory workshops are available in Zenodo: Blassel, R., & Ruiz Jiménez, A. M. (2026). Anonymised transcriptions of 12 participatory workshops in Spain, UK, Denmark, Germany, Hungary and Switzerland [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17831547>.

Figure 2. The UNTWIST funnel method for selecting topics across data types and countries

The selection highlights three broad domains in which citizens experience representation gaps as particularly salient, irrespective of whether these perceptions align with objective indicators—a question examined in subsequent sections. Healthcare and housing emerge as clear material priorities shared across groups and contexts, reflecting concerns with basic living conditions and access to essential services. Work–family balance and care for dependents capture the social and familial pressures that structure everyday life, revealing strong gendered dimensions of insecurity. Labour market integration, though somewhat less consistently emphasised across countries, still represents a recurrent concern linked to broader perceptions of instability.

Across these domains, grievances are not experienced solely as problems of access or provision. Rather, they are interpreted through implicit comparisons over time, across social groups, and against normative expectations of fairness and recognition. In this sense, these domains function as concrete arenas in which individuals evaluate whether “people like them” are being treated fairly, supported adequately, and recognised appropriately by public institutions.

The Five Core Domains

Five specific topics emerge as the most relevant within these domains (Figure 3). More detailed qualitative and quantitative data on each of these domains are presented in part III together with the definition of policy priorities and policy packages for each for the domains.

Figure 3. Core domains of gendered positional deprivation

- **Accessing good quality healthcare**

This topic shows the strongest quantitative consensus, often ranking first across RWPP, Mainstream Right (MR), and Mainstream Left (ML) voters, and is extensively discussed in qualitative data. Access to healthcare emerges as a gendered source of grievance not only through differences in use, but through differences in experiential intensity and evaluative framing.

Women consistently articulate healthcare as a high-salience issue embedded in long-term life trajectories, often linked to reproductive health, mental health, and caregiving responsibilities. Their accounts emphasise continuity of care, professional responsiveness, and the cumulative strain produced by fragmented systems. Healthcare shortcomings are interpreted not only as service failures, but as signals of insufficient recognition and unequal valuation of needs over time, amplifying perceptions of vulnerability and injustice.

Men, by contrast, tend to approach healthcare more episodically, focusing on specific encounters, waiting times, or system efficiency. Their evaluations are less frequently embedded in broader narratives of inequality or care responsibility. This contrast illustrates how similar institutional shortcomings can generate different forms of positional evaluation, rooted in gendered roles and expectations.

- **Accessing affordable housing, social services, and other goods**

Housing and access to social services rank among the highest priorities across all groups and countries. Here, gender differences relate to how material insecurity is experienced and interpreted in relation to stability, autonomy, and fairness.

Women frame housing affordability and social services as foundational conditions for

everyday life, particularly in contexts involving care responsibilities. Their narratives emphasise precarity, administrative complexity, and the emotional burden of navigating fragmented systems, often linking these experiences to constrained life choices and long-term insecurity. These conditions are frequently interpreted as reflecting structural unfairness and insufficient institutional support for socially necessary roles, particularly care.

Men also recognise rising costs and access barriers, but more often situate these concerns within broader market dynamics or macroeconomic trends. Housing is more frequently framed in terms of individual economic positioning and achievement, while social services are discussed in more abstract terms. As a result, similar material constraints are less often translated into sustained narratives of institutional misrecognition.

- **Balancing paid employment and family duties**

The reconciliation of work and family life emerges as a central and persistent grievance across all contexts. However, its interpretation reveals clear gendered patterns in how individuals assess fairness, responsibility, and constraint.

Women describe work–family balance as a structurally imposed tension characterised by trade-offs between career continuity, job quality, and family responsibilities. These trade-offs are experienced as involuntary and shaped by institutional limitations and persistent gender norms. As such, they are frequently interpreted as evidence of systemic imbalance and unequal distribution of responsibilities, undermining both recognition and opportunity.

Men also acknowledge difficulties in reconciling work and family life, but tend to frame them as logistical or temporary coordination problems rather than as indicators of structural disadvantage. The issue is less often connected to long-term career consequences or institutional design, and more frequently treated as a matter of individual adjustment.

- **Caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents**

Care responsibilities constitute a core axis of gendered grievance across all countries.

Women's accounts highlight the intensity, emotional labour, and moral weight of caregiving, as well as the limited institutional support available. Care is framed as non-optional and identity-defining, with direct implications for employment, income, and well-being. Importantly, these experiences are not only described in material terms, but as reflecting systematic under-recognition of care work and unequal distribution of responsibility. The lack of institutional support is interpreted as a failure to value essential social contributions, reinforcing perceptions of injustice and positional disadvantage.

Men, in contrast, tend to describe care as a secondary or supportive role, often emphasising episodic involvement. The demands of care and shortcomings in provision are less frequently articulated as structural or political problems. This difference reflects not divergent values, but asymmetrical exposure to responsibility and institutional dependence, which shapes how grievances are experienced and expressed.

- **Integrating successfully into the labour market**

Labour market integration is somewhat more uneven across contexts but remains a significant concern. Women's accounts emphasise fragmented and precarious trajectories shaped by care responsibilities and institutional constraints. Employment is evaluated not only in terms of access, but in relation to sustainability, dignity, and compatibility with family life.

These experiences are often interpreted by women as reflecting unequal opportunities and structural barriers, particularly when compared to normative expectations of stable and continuous employment. Labour market integration thus becomes a key site where positional deprivation is experienced through disrupted trajectories and limited recognition.

Men's narratives, by contrast, emphasise employment stability, income, and occupational status, often assuming a more linear model of labour market participation. Setbacks are generally attributed to economic conditions rather than to gendered constraints, and are less frequently linked to broader institutional or relational dynamics.

Cross-Cutting Gender Patterns

Our focus groups indicate that gender differences¹⁴ across these domains are less a matter of divergent values than of asymmetrical exposure to responsibility, risk, and institutional dependence, as well as of different evaluative and discursive frameworks. Women's grievances are cumulative and relational, embedded in interconnected life-course pressures and articulated through experiences of coordination, care, and constraint. Men's grievances, while often aligned in substantive importance, are more episodic, abstract, and less directly linked to personal dependency on welfare and care systems.

Importantly, this does not imply lower relevance of these domains for men. Survey data shows that healthcare, housing, care, work–family balance, and labour market integration are equally salient across genders. The difference lies in how grievances are articulated and interpreted, not in their underlying importance.

Policy Relevance: From Everyday Pressures to Political Grievance

Taken together, these five domains do not simply reflect inequalities in access to resources. They constitute the concrete arenas in which gendered positional deprivation is produced and evaluated through processes of comparison, fairness assessment, and recognition. Across these domains, individuals assess their situation not only in absolute terms, but in relation to expectations about what people like them should be able to achieve and how their contributions should be valued.

Shortcomings in these areas therefore undermine not only material conditions, but also perceived fairness, social standing, and institutional recognition. As individuals interpret

¹⁴ Gender difference were better noted in focus groups, as they were segregated by sex. The same key importance of the five domains as sites of grievances were largely confirmed in participatory workshops; however, while these workshops were largely mixed-sex the gender difference was less obvious.

everyday insecurity and overload as signals of unjust treatment or declining status linked to their gendered social position, material deficiencies are translated into positional grievances.

These domains thus form the material foundations from which gendered grievances emerge and intensify. While not inherently political in themselves, they create the conditions under which dissatisfaction can later be reframed and politicised through processes of attribution, including blame-based and scapegoating narratives. In this sense, they represent the critical interface between lived experience and political mobilisation.

4. Representation Gap and Party Supply

Why Political Supply Matters

The theoretical framework developed in this report starts from the hypothesis that shifting electoral support toward right-wing populist parties is rooted less in ideological persuasion than in failures of political responsiveness. Both the classical losers-of-globalisation hypothesis and its gender-sensitive refinements introduced by the UNTWIST project—gendered positional deprivation and losers of feminism—share this core assumption: when mainstream parties fail to adequately represent and respond to citizens' material needs, particularly as these are experienced through gendered social positions, voters become more likely to disengage from established political options.

From this perspective, the problem is not simply one of programmatic mismatch, but of systematic under-response to gendered grievances as they are experienced in everyday life. As shown in previous sections, these grievances emerge in specific material domains and are initially articulated in non-ideological terms. However, when they remain unaddressed, they create the conditions under which dissatisfaction can be reframed through processes of political attribution, including the construction of losers of feminism.

Having examined this process from the demand side through the narratives of RWPP switcher voters, the analysis now turns to the supply side of political representation. Specifically, this section assesses to what extent political parties—mainstream and populist alike—respond to the material and gendered needs identified across the UNTWIST empirical evidence, and whether gaps in programmatic responsiveness help explain the conditions under which scapegoating and blame-based mobilisation by RWPP become politically effective.

In contrast to the centrality of material conditions and perceived deterioration in living standards among RWPP switcher voters, our findings reveal a striking disconnect between these citizens' priorities and party agendas. Our longitudinal analysis of party manifestoes¹⁵ indicates that labour market and welfare issues—precisely the areas at

¹⁵ Carteny, G., Erbacher, R. A., & Braun, D. (2024). Deliverable 4.2 of the UNTWIST project: Summary of findings WP4. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14178241>. Carteny, G., & Braun, D. (2024). See also: Carteny, G., & Braun, D. (2024). UNTWIST briefing 04: Party Priorities and Positions on Gender-Related Issues. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14215292>.

the core of gendered positional deprivation—are becoming domains of weak political responsiveness. While parties continue to engage with a range of gender-related topics, the declining salience of gender equality in the labour market and welfare system is notable and troubling. This erosion of attention to the material and socioeconomic dimensions of gender equality has unfolded over more than a decade, marked by successive crises in Europe—from the Eurocrisis of the early 2010s to the more recent pandemic and cost-of-living crises.

Measuring Party Responsiveness: MGA and MARPOR

When we focus specifically on the five domains identified in the previous section—access to healthcare; access to housing, social services and basic goods; care for children, older people and dependents; conciliation of family and work; and labour market integration—a clear comparative pattern emerges across the two main datasets analysing party manifestoes, the MGA and MARPOR datasets.¹⁶

The MGA and MARPOR coding schemes differ fundamentally in their analytical logic and the type of political content they capture. **MGA** is explicitly designed to identify gendered dimensions of political discourse, coding only those quasi-sentences that refer directly to gender inequalities, gendered social structures, or gender-relevant policy frames. It therefore captures whether and how parties recognise and articulate gendered positional deprivation. **MARPOR**, by contrast, applies a general programmatic taxonomy that organises manifesto content into broad policy domains without explicitly considering gender as an analytical axis. As a result, MARPOR captures the overall salience of welfare, economic, or social issues, but not whether parties frame these issues in ways that respond to gendered experiences of inequality.

The analysis of the political supply side draws on a systematic coding of 412 party manifestos across six European countries (2003–2021), primarily based on the Comparative Manifesto Project (MARPOR) and complemented with additional electoral programme data. Using the Manifesto Gender Analysis (MGA) framework, originally developed by UNTWIST, over 440,000 quasi-sentences were coded by trained researchers.

¹⁶ The Comparative Manifesto Project (MARPOR) is a widely used international research dataset that systematically codes party manifestos to measure policy priorities and issue salience across countries and over time. By breaking down electoral programmes into comparable units, it provides a standardised and reliable basis for analysing party agendas and policy emphasis, and is extensively used in academic and policy research on political competition and representation. Data and coding book for the Manifesto Project (MARPOR) can be found at: <https://manifestoproject.wzb.eu/>.

The Manifesto Gender Analysis (MGA) is an original coding framework developed within the UNTWIST project to systematically assess how political parties address gender-based needs in their electoral programmes. Building on established approaches such as MARPOR, the MGA combines large-scale manifesto coding with a novel scheme explicitly aligned with the UNTWIST conceptual framework (WP1). It enables a fine-grained and comparable analysis of party agendas by identifying not only policy topics, but also target groups, intersectional dimensions, and the framing of gender-related issues. This approach overcomes limitations of existing datasets by capturing how gender concerns are embedded across policy domains, providing a robust basis for evaluating political responsiveness to citizens' material and gendered needs. Data and coding book for the Manifesto Gender Analysis can be found at: Braun, D., & Carteny, G. (2024). Gender codification of 412 national (general) and European Parliament elections in six European countries (2003-2021) (1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11476917>.

The two systems thus provide complementary but non-overlapping measures: MGA identifies gender-specific recognition and framing, whereas MARPOR measures general policy attention.

The Representation Gap Across the Five Domains

Three of the five domains—healthcare, housing and social services, and care—appear prominently in MARPOR but only marginally in MGA. In MARPOR, all three are subsumed under the broad welfare expansion category (per504), which captures a large share of manifesto content across party families. RWPP, MR, and ML alike register high levels of attention—often between 8 and 15 per cent—suggesting that welfare issues are central to programmatic discourse.

However, this apparent responsiveness masks a deeper limitation. While parties speak extensively about welfare, they rarely frame these issues in ways that reflect how they are experienced as gendered grievances, or how they relate to fairness, recognition, and unequal burdens across social groups. In MGA, attention to these problems is minimal across all party families, and particularly low among RWPP. Only limited traces of gender-sensitive framing appear among MR, and more consistently among ML, whose manifestos show the highest—though still modest—levels of attention to gender inequalities in welfare and care.

Taken together, these patterns indicate that welfare issues are politically visible but insufficiently interpreted through the lens of gendered positional deprivation. As a result, parties fail to connect general policy commitments with the lived experiences that structure dissatisfaction among voters.

Labour market integration presents a somewhat different configuration. Here, both datasets reveal modest yet consistent engagement, though unevenly distributed across party families. MGA captures references to inequalities related to pay, discrimination, or labour rights, with ML devoting the most attention, MR somewhat less, and RWPP the least. MARPOR shows a parallel structure, with employment-related content dispersed across several categories, typically ranging between 1 and 7 per cent.

While these levels remain modest overall, the alignment across MGA and MARPOR suggests that labour market issues are recognised as relevant across party families. However, only ML—and to a lesser extent MR—frame these issues in ways that engage with structural inequalities and gendered constraints. RWPP, in contrast, devote little attention to employment as a domain of inequality, reflecting a broader pattern of limited engagement with the structural sources of grievance.

Conciliation of family and work further sharpens these differences. Because MARPOR lacks a specific category to capture this issue, it remains effectively invisible in that dataset. MGA, however, records meaningful variation. ML consistently devotes the most attention to conciliation, MR addresses it less frequently, and RWPP rarely engage with it at all.

This pattern is analytically significant. Conciliation emerges as a domain in which gendered positional deprivation is particularly visible, but only where parties adopt gender-equality frames. Its absence in much of the party system suggests not only a lack of attention, but a failure to recognise a key site where grievances are produced and experienced.

Across these domains, a consistent pattern emerges. Welfare issues occupy a central place in party programmes, but their gendered dimensions remain largely

unacknowledged. Labour market inequalities receive modest and ideologically structured attention, while conciliation appears only where gender is explicitly politicised. As a result, parties often address the symptoms of dissatisfaction without engaging with the underlying structures of gendered inequality through which these grievances are experienced.

Cross-National Variation

A further layer of variation emerges across countries. Spain and Switzerland display the highest levels of gender-sensitive attention in MGA, particularly in care and, in the case of Spain, also in labour market issues and conciliation. In these contexts, mainstream left parties more explicitly connect citizens' everyday problems with gendered inequalities. Germany and the United Kingdom show more moderate levels of engagement, with gendered framings remaining secondary within broader programmatic debates. Denmark presents a notable contrast: despite strong welfare commitments reflected in high MARPOR scores, MGA registers minimal gendered framing, indicating that welfare is politicised largely without reference to gender. Hungary stands out as the clearest outlier, with almost no gender-sensitive framing across party families, pointing to a structurally weak presence of gender-equality discourse in the party system.

These cross-national differences highlight that the representation gap is shaped not only by ideological orientation but also by national political contexts, which condition the extent to which parties recognise and respond to gendered forms of deprivation.

Policy Relevance: From Programmatic Gaps to Political Realignment

Taken together, the evidence points to a structural disconnect between the domains in which citizens experience gendered positional deprivation and the ways in which political parties articulate and prioritise these issues. This disconnect is not simply a matter of insufficient attention, but of insufficient recognition and translation of lived grievances into programmatic responses.

In this sense, the representation gap constitutes a critical link in the broader causal chain identified in this report. When material grievances are not adequately recognised or addressed, dissatisfaction accumulates and remains politically unresolved. This, in turn, creates fertile ground for processes of attribution in which political actors—particularly RWPP—can reframe these grievances through narratives of blame, including the construction of losers of feminism.

The problem, therefore, is not only that mainstream parties fail to compete effectively with RWPP at the level of discourse, but that they often fail to intervene earlier in the causal sequence—at the level of material conditions and gendered experiences where grievances originate. Addressing this gap requires not only greater attention to welfare and labour market issues, but a more systematic integration of gender as a structuring dimension of inequality, recognition, and political responsiveness.

5. Where Representation Fails, Scapegoating Thrives

The Representation Gap and Expressive Defection

Taken together, these findings point to a growing representational gap between citizens' material concerns and the policy agendas articulated by mainstream parties.

Across countries (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary), voters consistently identify deteriorating living conditions, economic insecurity, and declining social protection as the primary sources of dissatisfaction with mainstream politics. At the same time, party programmes devote comparatively limited and uneven attention to these issues. This mismatch lends strong support to the hypothesis of expressive voting. Rather than voting to secure concrete policy gains, many citizens use the ballot to punish mainstream parties they hold responsible for perceived material decline. By contrast, our data offer little evidence in favour of instrumental voting for right-wing populist parties, understood as support based on expectations of effective policy delivery.

This expressive logic is clearly reflected in the focus group discussions. Dissatisfaction with the mainstream political offer and with the broader "state of things" emerges as a highly salient, though unevenly articulated, theme. In most countries analysed by UNTWIST (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary), participants do not frame their discontent primarily as rejection of specific parties; instead, they articulate a diffuse political malaise encompassing economic strain, institutional underperformance, and perceived unfairness. This malaise corresponds closely to the experiential dimension of gendered positional deprivation, in which individuals perceive declining security, recognition, and life chances in relation to their social position.

This dissatisfaction is particularly pronounced in Hungary (across women's and men's groups) and among German men, where it appears early in discussions, is participant-initiated, widely shared, and repeatedly revisited, functioning as a general interpretive lens through which multiple issues are understood. Gendered patterns are consistent across contexts: men tend to articulate dissatisfaction in abstract, systemic, and moral terms—such as loss of fairness, elite self-interest, or the erosion of the middle class—whereas women more often ground critique in concrete, lived experiences related to cost of living, healthcare, education, and care burdens. In Denmark, Switzerland, and the UK, dissatisfaction is present but more muted and pragmatic, expressed as frustration with responsiveness and political distance rather than as a sense of systemic breakdown.

RWPP as Vehicles of Protest, Not Policy Delivery

Within this context of diffuse dissatisfaction, RWPP occupy a secondary and largely instrumental position in voters' narratives. They are discussed less frequently and less centrally than mainstream politics, and rarely as objects of strong identification or trust. When they do appear, RWPP are framed primarily as vehicles for protest, disruption, or symbolic rebalancing, rather than as credible governing alternatives. Participants associate RWPP with the capacity to "shake things up", articulate grievances perceived as ignored, or impose order—especially in relation to migration, security, or elite accountability.

Crucially, this positioning confirms that RWPP support is not rooted in the initial formation of grievances, but in their political re-articulation. Expectations are expressive rather than programmatic: RWPP are valued for their capacity to signal dissatisfaction or exert pressure on mainstream actors, not for their ability to deliver coherent policy solutions. This framing is most evident in Hungarian and German men's groups, whereas women's groups tend to express greater ambivalence and moral caution, often highlighting risks, excesses, or social consequences. Across contexts, scepticism about RWPP competence and governability remains widespread, reinforcing the conclusion that RWPP function primarily as instruments of defection rather than as positively endorsed representatives.

If support for RWPP were primarily instrumental, one would expect these parties to offer stronger representation of the gendered material needs identified in previous sections. However, our analysis of party manifestos shows that RWPP do not provide more substantive engagement with citizens' material concerns than mainstream parties. On the contrary, they assign relatively low importance to gender-related issues connected to labour market participation, welfare provision, and living conditions—precisely the domains in which gendered positional deprivation takes shape.¹⁷ Instead, RWPP discourse tends to privilege symbolic or identity-based domains—such as rights, discrimination, or gender-based violence—often framed in adversarial terms.

How Blame Narratives Gain Traction

What, then, explains RWPP's electoral appeal among switcher voters? (Figure 4).

Figure 4. How blame narratives gain traction

As Mondon and Winter¹⁸ argue, RWPP thrive where blame discourses resonate with pre-existing gaps in political representation. Our findings strongly support this interpretation. The limited responsiveness of mainstream parties to material insecurity

¹⁷ Brause, S. D. & Kinski, L. Mainstream party agenda-responsiveness and the electoral success of right-wing populist parties in Europe. *J. Eur. Public Policy* 31, 295–323 (2024).

¹⁸ Mondon, A. & Winter, A. (2020). *Reactionary Democracy: How Racism and the Populist Far Right Became Mainstream*. London: Verso.

and declining living conditions—particularly as these are experienced through gendered social positions—creates a permissive environment in which RWPP can successfully deploy strategies of attribution and scapegoating.

In this process, RWPP do not create grievances but reframe them, transforming diffuse dissatisfaction into targeted narratives of blame. It is at this stage that the mechanism captured by the concept of losers of feminism becomes politically salient. Individuals who experience gendered positional deprivation may come to interpret their situation through attributional frames that identify feminism or gender equality policies as sources of loss. This attribution is neither automatic nor universal; it is contingent on the availability and resonance of political narratives that simplify complex structural problems and assign responsibility to identifiable actors or symbolic out-groups.

Strategic Implications for Democratic Competition

These dynamics have important implications for political competition. Our findings suggest that mainstream parties could more effectively counter RWPP's appeal by addressing the underlying conditions of dissatisfaction rather than engaging primarily at the level of discourse. The growing distance between citizens' material concerns and the policy attention devoted to them has allowed RWPP to gain traction through emotionally charged and simplified narratives.

Rather than operating on the terrain defined by RWPP—and thereby reinforcing their framing—mainstream parties would be better served by re-centring political competition on the material and socioeconomic dimensions that voters consistently identify as sources of dissatisfaction. Clear, credible, and inclusive policy responses in areas such as labour market security, welfare provision, care infrastructures, and living conditions would not only improve material outcomes but also reduce the conditions under which gendered grievances can be reinterpreted through blame-based narratives.

In this sense, the representational gap identified here operates as a critical mechanism linking experience and political attribution. It shapes how material insecurity and perceived neglect are lived and interpreted by women and men, giving rise to gendered positional deprivation. The subsequent attribution of these experiences to feminism or gender equality—captured by the notion of losers of feminism—constitutes a secondary and contingent mechanism that RWPP activate through discursive strategies rather than a primary driver of electoral defection.

Policy Relevance: Addressing Material Grievances First

Overall, the findings indicate that support for right-wing populist parties is driven less by policy endorsement than by unresolved material grievances and deficits of political representation, experienced in gendered ways. When mainstream parties fail to respond to these differentiated needs, space is created for RWPP to mobilise dissatisfaction through attribution and scapegoating rather than substantive solutions.

Addressing this dynamic requires policy interventions that strengthen democratic responsiveness and tackle the structural sources of gendered positional deprivation. Rather than engaging primarily at the level of political discourse, effective responses must focus on the material conditions in which dissatisfaction originates. The next section therefore sets out the policy logic underpinning such an approach, clarifying why material responsiveness is central to reducing the appeal of blame-based political mobilisation.

6. Policy Logic: Why Material Responsiveness Matters

Why Responsiveness Matters

The analysis presented in this Handbook leads to a clear conclusion: strengthening democratic resilience in Europe requires improving the material responsiveness of public policy. The rise of right-wing populist parties (RWPP) is driven less by ideological persuasion than by persistent gaps between citizens' lived experiences and the capacity of political institutions to recognise and respond to them.

Across countries and methods, the evidence consistently shows that dissatisfaction originates in material conditions. Citizens point to economic insecurity, pressures on living standards, and declining access to essential services as the primary sources of discontent. These experiences are rooted in everyday life—in healthcare, housing, care responsibilities, work–family balance, and labour market stability.

These pressures are not experienced uniformly. They are structured by gendered social positions, shaping how insecurity, constraint, and unfairness are lived and interpreted. This is what the UNTWIST project conceptualises as gendered positional deprivation: a condition in which individuals perceive a deterioration in their life chances and evaluate it in relation to people like them. Importantly, these experiences do not initially take the form of ideological opposition or support for specific political actors. They emerge as dissatisfaction with material conditions and institutional performance.

How Material Grievances Become Political Risks

The political significance of these experiences lies in what happens when they remain unaddressed. When institutions fail to respond, dissatisfaction accumulates and creates space for political interpretation. At this stage, actors—particularly RWPP—can reframe diffuse grievances into simplified narratives of blame, assigning responsibility to elites, institutions, or social groups. In some cases, this includes attributing perceived losses to gender equality or feminism, giving rise to what the project terms losers of feminism.

This attribution is not inevitable. It is contingent on the absence of credible and visible policy responses. Where institutions effectively address the sources of insecurity, the appeal of blame-based narratives is reduced. Where they do not, these narratives gain plausibility and traction.

Three Dimensions of Material Responsiveness

The implication is clear: the most effective way to counter populist mobilisation is not to engage primarily at the level of discourse, but to intervene earlier in the causal chain—at the level of material conditions where dissatisfaction originates. Material responsiveness, in this sense, goes beyond general economic performance or aggregate policy outputs. It requires aligning public policy with how problems are actually experienced. This involves three interrelated dimensions.

- **Substantive Responsiveness**

First, substantive responsiveness: policies must directly address the sources of insecurity identified by citizens, particularly in the domains where gendered positional deprivation is most pronounced—healthcare, housing, care, work–family balance, and labour market integration. This requires sustained investment and policy coherence, but also prioritisation of the areas where dissatisfaction is most acute.

- **Recognitional responsiveness**

Second, recognitional responsiveness: policies must reflect how these problems are experienced across different social groups. Gendered divisions of labour, care responsibilities, and employment trajectories shape not only exposure to risk, but also expectations of fairness and support. Policies that fail to account for these differences risk being formally neutral but substantively insufficient, reinforcing perceptions of neglect or misrecognition.

- **Communicative responsiveness**

Third, communicative responsiveness: policy responses must be visible, credible, and intelligible. Even effective policies can fail to rebuild trust if citizens do not perceive them as addressing their concerns. Bridging this gap requires not only implementation, but also the capacity to clearly connect policy action to lived experience.

Together, these dimensions define what it means to be responsive in a context marked by complex and differentiated forms of insecurity. They also explain why responsiveness matters politically. When citizens perceive that their concerns are recognised and addressed, dissatisfaction is less likely to translate into political disaffection. When responsiveness is weak, dissatisfaction remains unresolved and becomes more susceptible to politicisation through blame and attribution.

Strategic Implications for Democratic Resilience

This shifts the strategic focus of political competition. Rather than confronting RWPP primarily on symbolic or ideological terrain—where they often set the terms of debate—mainstream actors can reduce their appeal by addressing the conditions that enable their success. This means narrowing the gap between lived experience and political representation, particularly in the domains where grievances are most consistently produced.

For European policymakers, this perspective underscores the importance of strengthening the material foundations of democratic legitimacy. The role of public policy is not only to deliver outcomes, but to ensure that these outcomes are experienced as fair, supportive, and responsive across different social positions.

From Policy Logic to Recommendations

The recommendations developed in this Handbook are grounded in this logic. By targeting the domains in which gendered positional deprivation takes shape, they aim to improve material conditions, strengthen institutional responsiveness, and reduce the scope for dissatisfaction to be reinterpreted through blame-based narratives. The next section sets out the rationale for focusing these recommendations at the EU level, clarifying the added value of this level of intervention within the analytical framework developed in this Handbook.

7. EU-Level Policy Recommendations

Why Recommendations Follow from the Findings

The policy recommendations developed in this Handbook are directly grounded in the analytical framework and empirical findings of the UNTWIST project. The analysis has

shown that support for right-wing populist parties is not primarily driven by ideological opposition to gender equality, but by experiences of gendered positional deprivation rooted in unresolved material insecurity and insufficient political responsiveness. When mainstream political actors fail to address citizens' concrete needs in key domains of everyday life, these representation gaps create the conditions under which grievances can be retrospectively politicised through processes of attribution, including blame and scapegoating narratives.

The recommendations that follow are therefore designed to strengthen democratic outputs by improving the material responsiveness of public policies in the domains where gendered positional deprivation takes shape, thereby reducing both lived dissatisfaction and the plausibility of populist attribution strategies. In this sense, they are intended not only to improve policy performance, but to intervene in the causal chain identified in this Handbook by addressing the material and institutional conditions under which dissatisfaction emerges and is subsequently politicised.

Why Focus on the EU Level

While our participatory workshops help co-create policy recommendations focusing on the national level, the UNTWIST consortium decided to complement these with EU-level policy recommendations in this Handbook. This dual approach reflects the need to connect citizens' articulated needs with the institutional levels at which effective and scalable responses can be designed.

Although the evidence base includes two non-EU countries for comparative purposes, the recommendations focus on the EU level because the European Union is the principal supranational framework through which common values, legal standards, funding instruments, and coordinated policy responses can be advanced across Member States. At the same time, many proposals are also relevant for national, regional, and local political actors responsible for implementation within their respective competences.

Figure 5. Why policy recommendations are addressed at the EU level

The EU's Added Value for Democratic Responsiveness

Focusing policy recommendations at the EU level offers distinct advantages in both normative and practical terms (Figure 5). First, the European Union provides a unique institutional arena for upholding and promoting shared values—such as democracy, the rule of law, and fundamental rights—that transcend national boundaries. Positioning recommendations within this framework reinforces the EU's capacity to act as a guarantor of these principles, particularly when domestic political developments may weaken them. In this sense, EU-level engagement allows policy actors to align proposals with a broader normative order, including gender equality as a core value of the Union.

At the same time, the EU is not external to the dynamics identified in this Handbook, but structurally implicated in both their causes and their potential resolution. Through its influence on labour markets, welfare coordination, social investment strategies, and regulatory frameworks, the EU helps shape the material conditions in which citizens experience security, recognition, and opportunity. The domains in which gendered positional deprivation takes shape—healthcare, housing, care provision, work–family balance, and labour market participation—are all areas where EU-level policies, funding instruments, and coordination mechanisms exert direct or indirect effects. This makes the EU a particularly relevant level of intervention for addressing the structural sources of dissatisfaction identified in this first part.

Recommendations addressed to EU institutions also benefit from significant political visibility and leverage. The EU's multi-level governance system enables policy priorities to circulate across institutional and communicative channels, shaping national agendas through soft law, funding instruments, and strategic coordination. By targeting the EU level, proposals can extend their influence beyond the supranational sphere while helping to reduce the gap between citizens' lived experiences and institutional responses, which lies at the core of the representation failures analysed in this Handbook.

At a more structural level, the EU provides a framework for fostering coherence among diverse national approaches. Recommendations developed at this scale can promote shared standards and reduce policy fragmentation, ensuring that Member States pursue complementary objectives in areas of common concern. This is particularly important in the interconnected domains where gendered positional deprivation is produced, as fragmented responses can reinforce perceptions of unfairness, neglect, or declining social protection.

Moreover, the EU's capacity to pool financial, technical, and administrative resources enhances the feasibility and reach of policy interventions. European-level strategies can mobilise collective instruments such as the European Social Fund, the Green Deal, or Horizon Europe, enabling actions that would be difficult to sustain at the national level. The EU also functions as a site of comparative learning, where evidence-based approaches can circulate, be tested, and adapted across diverse contexts, supporting mutual policy innovation.

Finally, focusing on the EU level ensures alignment with the Union's competences and institutional architecture. In areas of shared or exclusive competence, this positioning increases the likelihood that recommendations can be translated into concrete action. Taken together, these elements underscore the added value of EU-level policy design, where normative authority, political visibility, and institutional capacity intersect to address the structural conditions identified in this Handbook.

Citizens' Preferred Pathways for Action

Despite this EU-level focus, findings in our participatory workshops provide essential insight into how citizens themselves understand both the sources of dissatisfaction and the pathways for addressing it. The participatory workshops reveal a high degree of convergence across countries in how participants diagnose problems related to gendered inequalities and socioeconomic insecurity.

Across contexts (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary), participants consistently identify public institutions, political authorities, and major economic actors as the primary agents responsible for addressing these issues. This reflects a widespread expectation that structural problems require structural solutions. Internal or individual strategies are mentioned far less frequently and, in some cases, explicitly rejected as ineffective. These findings point to a strong perception that current institutional responses are insufficient, reinforcing the sense of representation gap identified throughout this Handbook.

Importantly, participants do not experience gendered or socioeconomic inequalities as isolated issues, but as interconnected deficits within broader institutional, economic, and cultural systems. Their preferred solutions therefore combine multiple dimensions: redistribution, regulation, structural reform, and cultural change. While national contexts shape the specific content and emphasis of proposals, participants across countries share a demand for more responsive, coordinated, and future-oriented public institutions, capable of addressing both material inequalities and the norms that sustain them. These findings reinforce the central argument of this Handbook: improving material responsiveness in the domains where gendered positional deprivation takes shape is essential not only for social outcomes, but also for restoring the link between citizens and democratic institutions.

The preferred solutions expressed by citizens in participatory workshops can be classified into five categories. First, regulation emerges as the most common proposition, reflecting demands for stronger and more effective rules. Second, higher public spending is widely identified as essential, particularly in care, welfare, and education. Third, cultural change is mentioned as necessary to address persistent norms and expectations, especially around gender equality. Fourth, individual solutions appear far less frequently, indicating limited confidence in self-driven approaches. Finally, state intervention is often invoked in general terms, signalling a strong expectation of public responsibility, even where specific policy instruments are not clearly articulated.

From Diagnosis to Policy Design

Taken together, the preceding sections have established the analytical framework for understanding the drivers of political dissatisfaction, the mechanisms through which it is transformed into political support for right-wing populist actors, and the rationale for intervention at the EU level. The Handbook now turns to the methodological approach through which these insights are translated into policy-relevant outputs. **Part II** sets out the principles and procedures guiding the development of the recommendations, clarifying how the analytical framework is operationalised across policy domains. Building on this, **Part III** presents the resulting policy recommendations, structured around the key areas in which gendered positional deprivation takes shape and where improved material responsiveness can strengthen democratic resilience.

PART II – FROM CITIZEN CONCERNS TO EU ACTION: ANALYTICAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

Building on the empirical diagnosis developed in Part I, this part sets out the analytical and methodological framework through which citizen-defined concerns are translated into policy-relevant problem structures and EU-level action. It moves from thematic delimitation and bottleneck identification to the mapping of the Union’s legal, institutional, and financial capacities, thereby defining the conditions under which policy intervention remains feasible, implementable, and publicly legible.

8. From Diagnosis to EU Policy Implementation

Building on the analytical framework and empirical findings presented in Part I, this section focuses on how EU-level action can be operationalised to address the domains in which gendered positional deprivation takes shape. Rather than revisiting the sources of dissatisfaction or the dynamics of political realignment, the objective here is to translate these insights into feasible policy pathways that can improve material responsiveness and strengthen the link between citizens and democratic institutions.

Part I has shown that citizens’ dissatisfaction is rooted primarily in material conditions experienced in everyday life—particularly in areas such as healthcare, housing, care, work–family balance, and labour market integration. These domains constitute the key arenas in which individuals assess their security, recognition, and life chances. Where institutional responses in these areas are perceived as insufficient, inconsistent, or unfair, citizens develop grievances that may evolve into broader dissatisfaction with political systems. Under certain conditions, these experiences can subsequently be reframed through processes of attribution, including blame and scapegoating.

The task of policy design is therefore to intervene upstream in this process. This requires focusing not on reactive responses to political symptoms, but on improving the material and institutional conditions through which dissatisfaction emerges. In practice, this means strengthening the responsiveness, accessibility, and perceived fairness of public policies in the domains where gendered positional deprivation is produced. EU-level action can play a critical role in supporting this objective, provided that interventions are aligned with the Union’s institutional capacities and governance structures.

8.1. The European Union as an Operational Policy Environment

Designing effective EU-level interventions¹⁹ requires engaging with the Union as a multi-level governance system characterised by shared competences, diverse policy

¹⁹ Although the comparative evidence includes two non-EU countries, the recommendations are directed to the EU level because many of the challenges identified require coordination across Member States and can be addressed through the Union’s regulatory, financial, and strategic instruments. Many measures may also inform action by national, regional, and local authorities within their respective competences.

instruments, and significant cross-national variation. Unlike national governments, the EU rarely exercises direct control over core welfare domains. Instead, its influence is mediated through a combination of regulatory frameworks, financial instruments, coordination mechanisms, and agenda-setting processes.

Competences and Indirect Influence

First, many of the policy areas identified in Part I—particularly healthcare, housing, and care provision—remain primarily within the competence of Member States. However, the EU exerts indirect but substantial influence through mechanisms such as funding programmes, fiscal coordination, labour market regulation, and social policy guidelines. Effective policy design must therefore operate through these channels, leveraging the EU's capacity to support, coordinate, and incentivise national action rather than replacing it.

A Diverse Policy Toolbox

Second, EU policy operates through a diverse set of instruments, each with different strengths and limitations. Financial tools—such as the European Social Fund, cohesion policy instruments, and investment programmes—enable targeted support and capacity-building. Regulatory frameworks can set minimum standards and shape market conditions. Coordination mechanisms, including the European Semester, allow for policy alignment and monitoring across Member States. In addition, knowledge-sharing platforms facilitate the diffusion of best practices and evidence-based approaches. The effectiveness of EU-level action depends on selecting and combining these instruments in ways that match the nature of the problem being addressed.

Cross-National Variation and Flexible Implementation

Third, cross-national variation is a defining feature of the EU policy landscape. Member States differ significantly in their welfare regimes, labour market structures, care systems, and institutional capacities. As a result, policy approaches must balance common objectives with flexibility in implementation. EU-level strategies should therefore provide a coherent framework while allowing adaptation to national contexts, ensuring both consistency and effectiveness.

Visibility, Attribution, and Citizen Perception

Fourth, the visibility and attribution of policy action are critical. As shown in Part I, dissatisfaction is shaped not only by material conditions, but by perceptions of institutional responsiveness. Policies that improve outcomes but remain invisible or poorly attributed to public action may fail to reduce dissatisfaction. EU-level interventions must therefore be designed in ways that are recognisable to citizens, clearly linked to their everyday concerns, and communicated effectively across levels of governance.

Integrated Responses to Interconnected Problems

Finally, the interconnected nature of the domains identified in Part I requires integrated policy approaches. Healthcare, housing, care, and labour market participation are not isolated policy areas, but interdependent systems. Shortcomings in one domain often reinforce vulnerabilities in others. EU-level action should therefore aim to promote coordination across policy areas, avoiding fragmented interventions that fail to address the cumulative nature of material insecurity.

8.2. From Domains to Policy Pathways

Building on the institutional and operational features of EU governance outlined above, the next step is to translate these conditions into a structured approach to policy design.

Domains as Policy Entry Points

To operationalise EU-level action, the five domains identified in Part I are treated as policy entry points. Each domain represents a site where gendered positional deprivation is produced, a set of institutional arrangements that shape citizens' experiences, and a cluster of policy levers through which these experiences can be improved.

The objective is not to replicate national responsibilities, but to identify where EU-level action can add value by strengthening institutional capacity, reducing fragmentation, and improving the alignment between citizens' needs and policy responses. This requires translating identified grievances into actionable policy pathways through a structured process.

Step 1: Identify Forms of Dissatisfaction

First, each domain must be understood in terms of the specific forms of insecurity and dissatisfaction it generates. These may include barriers to access, insufficient quality of services, administrative complexity, or unequal distribution of resources and responsibilities. Importantly, these issues are experienced differently by women and men, reflecting the gendered organisation of labour markets, care systems, and social expectations.

Step 2: Diagnose Policy Bottlenecks

Second, these forms of dissatisfaction can be linked to identifiable policy bottlenecks. These may arise from underinvestment, regulatory gaps, coordination failures, or mismatches between policy design and lived realities. Identifying these bottlenecks is essential for moving from general problem recognition to targeted intervention.

Step 3: Match EU-Level Levers to the Problem

Third, EU-level levers must be mapped onto these bottlenecks. Depending on the domain, this may involve financial support, regulatory action, coordination mechanisms, or combinations thereof. The aim is to determine where EU intervention can most effectively improve outcomes, support national systems, and enhance perceived responsiveness.

Step 4: Link Intervention to Outcomes

Finally, policy pathways must be designed in a way that connects intervention to expected outcomes—not only in material terms, but also in terms of institutional trust and political legitimacy. Improving access to services, reducing insecurity, or supporting care systems can contribute directly to better living conditions. At the same time, visible and coherent policy responses can strengthen citizens' perception that public institutions are responsive to their needs.

Operational Logic for the Recommendations Ahead

This approach establishes the operational logic through which analytical findings are translated into policy design. By structuring intervention around domains, bottlenecks, and EU-level levers, it provides a coherent framework for developing policy responses that are both analytically grounded and institutionally aligned. The next section sets out the methodological framework that governs this process, detailing how policy options are constructed, assessed, and prioritised within the constraints of the EU's multi-level governance system.

9. Evidence to Action: Policy Framework

This section sets out the operational framework through which the Handbook translates the analytical findings of Part I into EU-level policy recommendations in Part III. To enhance the usability of the handbook, the domain chapters in Part III focus on the most policy-relevant elements of that approach—namely the identification of priorities, the formulation of policy packages, and the resulting recommendations. The fuller domain-specific analytical development of this methodology is provided in supplementary material available online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

Building on the identification of gendered positional deprivation, the five domains in which it takes shape, and the representational gaps that allow grievances to become politically mobilised, the objective here is not to revisit diagnosis, but to explain how these insights are converted into structured, feasible, and prioritised policy responses.

Section overview

Figure 6. From citizen concerns to policy recommendations

Rather than presenting a standalone research methodology, the section clarifies the sequence through which citizen-defined concerns are transformed into problem structures, how these are filtered through the constraints and opportunities of the EU's multi-level governance system, and how they are developed into EU-plausible policy packages that can be comparatively assessed. The approach is therefore explicitly designed to produce recommendations that are not only analytically grounded, but also institutionally feasible, politically usable, and capable of generating outcomes that are visible and meaningful to citizens.

The framework follows a cumulative and traceable logic (Figure 6). It moves from an upstream agenda defined by comparative empirical evidence on citizen concerns, to the identification of recurrent bottlenecks within each domain, to the mapping of EU action space, to the formulation of policy packages, and finally to their comparative appraisal under explicit criteria. Across these steps, the methodology preserves a clear chain of reasoning linking diagnosis, institutional plausibility, policy design, and prioritisation.

9.1. Policy Approach, Evidence Base, and Upstream Thematic Delimitation

Methodological Orientation

The research approach underpinning this framework is mixed and pragmatic. It is designed to generate policy options that are both institutionally realistic and politically usable. Methodologically, the Handbook moves from an upstream citizen-defined agenda, to problem structuring within each theme, to mapping the EU action space, to the formulation of EU-plausible policy packages, and finally to comparative prioritisation under explicit institutional and political constraints.

Triangulated Evidence Base

This approach triangulates three types of evidence:

- EU legal and institutional sources
- Comparative empirical evidence on citizen concerns and policy performance
- Expert and stakeholder knowledge

This triangulation is necessary because the study's starting point is a representational problem: as shown in Part I, many voters who move towards RWPP appear motivated less by ideological alignment than by dissatisfaction rooted in material conditions and in the perceived inability of mainstream actors to respond effectively to everyday needs. The study therefore treats public policy as a channel for rebuilding representative capacity through credible outputs, while recognising that policy effects are filtered through fairness perceptions and contested narratives.

Why This Approach Matters Politically

The methodology assumes that distrust is not only a perceptual problem. It also reflects real failures of delivery, prioritisation, and responsiveness in areas that structure everyday life. For that reason, communication is treated here as a condition of legibility

and accountability, not as a substitute for institutional performance. The objective is to identify policy packages that are not only normatively desirable, but also feasible within the EU's multi-level governance framework and capable of generating outcomes that citizens can recognise in practice.

Traceability and Common Reasoning Chain

To preserve traceability, the analysis links diagnosis, institutional plausibility, package design, and prioritisation through a common chain of reasoning. Each recommendation is expected to rest on a clear account of four elements: the problem it addresses, the EU levers through which it can act, the implementation pathway through which change could occur, and the indicators through which progress can be monitored. This is what allows the study to move from citizen-relevant concerns to policy proposals that remain both auditable and politically usable.

A Constrained Agenda: Starting from the Five Themes

The present Handbook does not re-select the thematic agenda from scratch. It starts from a set of priority arenas already established through prior comparative project work and asks what can credibly be done within them at EU level. The selection of the five themes is anchored in the project's prior comparative diagnosis of citizens' needs, based on 18 focus groups across six country contexts, complemented by participatory workshops and a representative survey with segmentation by voter families and an oversample of RWPP voters. This empirical work constrains the agenda by identifying which everyday problems are consistently salient and politically consequential across electorates, including among voters who have shifted away from mainstream parties as a form of protest. For the purposes of this Handbook, those findings are treated as an input, not as a question to be reopened. Survey distributions, focus-group material, and opinion patterns are therefore not re-analysed here in order to determine a new thematic shortlist. Instead, they are used to justify why the five selected themes constitute the most relevant arenas for policy response and political reconnection identified in Part I.

The Role of Part II

This distinction is methodologically important. The role of the prior project evidence, presented in Part I, is to define the political arenas that matter; the role of this Part II is to determine what forms of EU-enabled action are plausible, implementable, and publicly legible within those arenas. The analysis therefore begins from a constrained agenda and proceeds by structuring the main bottlenecks within each theme, mapping the available EU levers, and formulating policy packages that can be compared under common criteria.

From Citizen Concern to Operational Diagnosis

Within each of the five selected themes, the analysis moves from broad citizen concern to a more operational diagnosis of the problems that policy would need to address. The aim is not simply to restate dissatisfaction, but to identify the recurrent bottlenecks, structural constraints, and implementation failures that most consistently generate it across contexts.

This step is necessary because citizen salience does not by itself determine policy design. A problem may be politically visible without being institutionally tractable; conversely, some intervention points may matter greatly for outcomes even if citizens do not describe them in technical terms. The analytical task is therefore to confront

lived experience with comparative evidence in order to reconstruct the mechanisms through which dissatisfaction arises and to distinguish between symptoms, drivers, and possible leverage points.

A Common Diagnostic Logic

In practice, this means that each theme is read through a common diagnostic logic. First, the analysis identifies the aspects of the problem that are most salient in the project's qualitative and survey material. Second, these concerns are confronted with comparative and evaluative evidence in order to test whether they reflect broader cross-country pressures, recurring system weaknesses, or identifiable service and governance bottlenecks. Third, only those problem clusters that are both empirically supported and plausibly open to EU-level influence are retained for option development.

Filtering Concerns into Actionable Problem Structures

This stage therefore performs a filtering function between the upstream thematic agenda and the later design of policy packages. It ensures that the study does not move directly from public frustration to institutional recommendation without an intervening step of analytical reconstruction. In methodological terms, it is the point at which politically salient concerns are translated into problem structures that can support subsequent work on EU competences, implementation routes, monitoring indicators, and comparative appraisal.

From Recurrent Patterns to EU-Level Proposals

Across the Handbook, this diagnostic move is progressive and traceable. The analysis does not assume that the same bottlenecks exist in identical form across all national contexts, nor that a common concern automatically implies a common solution. Instead, it identifies the recurrent problem patterns that appear often enough, and with sufficient consistency, to justify structured policy development at EU level. This is what allows the Handbook to move from citizen-defined arenas of concern to proposals that remain both analytically grounded and institutionally realistic.

9.2. Mapping the EU Action Space and Formulating EU-Plausible Policy Packages

Why the EU Action Space Must Be Defined First

Before policy options are formulated, the study establishes the EU action space within which intervention is plausible. This step identifies the levers and limits through which the Union can shape outcomes even when delivery remains primarily national, regional, or local. Its purpose is to avoid two methodological errors: proposing solutions that exceed the EU competence framework, and overlooking indirect EU instruments that can be decisive because they shape incentives, capacity, coordination, and comparability across Member States.

What the EU Action Space Includes

In this Handbook, the EU action space is understood as the set of legal, institutional, coordinative, financial, and monitoring instruments through which the Union can influence policy outcomes within the domains identified in Part I. This includes binding

legal instruments where EU authority exists, coordination and agenda-setting tools, financing and co-financing mechanisms, conditionality linked to spending, monitoring and data infrastructures, and, where relevant, market-shaping mechanisms. The analysis therefore treats EU action not only as formal legislation, but as a wider governance architecture that can raise floors, enable reform, reduce bottlenecks, and structure accountability across levels.

Mapping this action space functions as a boundary condition prior to option development and prioritisation. Measures that assume powers the EU does not hold, or that lack an identifiable governance and financing route, are set aside at this stage. At the same time, the mapping exercise is designed to capture forms of EU influence that may be indirect but still practically significant, especially where the Union can support delivery through standards, incentives, funding alignment, or comparable reporting.

Three Dimensions of the Mapping Exercise

The analysis is organised around three mutually reinforcing dimensions. First, regulatory analysis identifies the relevant legal basis, the scope of competence, the conditions and limits of EU action, and possible synergies with other instruments and programmes. Second, institutional analysis maps the main actors, roles, incentives, and coordination spaces in a multi-level governance perspective, including both formal and informal mechanisms that condition implementation. Third, programme and financing analysis identifies the operational routes through which measures could be supported, delivered, monitored, and, where relevant, scaled.

This stage therefore provides the institutional filter that connects diagnosis to policy design. It clarifies what the EU can credibly do, through which channels, with which actors, and under what constraints. That is what allows the next stage of the methodology to move from problem structures identified in Part I to EU-plausible policy packages without collapsing normative ambition into institutional overreach.

Why the Handbook Uses Policy Packages Rather Than Isolated Measures

Where intervention remains plausible within the mapped EU action space, the study formulates policy packages rather than isolated measures. This reflects how EU action typically works in practice: legal instruments, funding streams, coordination mechanisms, and monitoring arrangements often reinforce one another, and a measure that appears weak in isolation may become credible as part of a coherent package.

Package construction is therefore designed to translate each problem structure into an explicit logic of intervention. For each option, the analysis specifies the policy components through which change would occur, the governance route through which the package would operate, the actors responsible for implementation, the capacities required for delivery, and the indicators through which outputs and outcomes could be tracked. This makes it possible to compare options not only in normative terms, but in relation to whether they can actually be implemented within the EU's multi-level governance framework.

Four Design Questions for Every Package

In practical terms, each package is built around four questions:

- First, does the option require a legal backbone, or can it operate through softer coordination and guidance?

- Second, does it have an identifiable financing and delivery route, including programme support, institutional capacity, or co-financing conditions?
- Third, does it require specific governance and monitoring arrangements in order to be credible and accountable?
- Fourth, can it generate a citizen-legible results pathway, meaning a chain from intervention to observable output that remains understandable and auditable over time?

This stage also incorporates a programmatic analysis of each option's internal logic. Problems are translated into a structured policy-design chain linking problem → outputs → outcomes → longer-term impact. Where relevant, this analysis includes territorial and social equity considerations, key risks and dependencies, preliminary checks of institutional readiness, and the identification of monitoring indicators that are realistic rather than aspirational. The purpose is not to maximise policy ambition in the abstract, but to ensure that proposals are constructed in a way that remains operationally credible and responsive to the forms of deprivation identified in Part I.

Output of This Stage: A Comparable Set of EU-Plausible Options

At the end of this stage, the study does not yet rank options. It produces a set of EU-plausible packages with an explicit implementation logic, a traceable results chain, and a sufficiently clear delivery pathway to allow structured comparative appraisal in the next step.

9.3. Evidence Base for Appraisal, Comparative Prioritisation, and Study Limitations

Evidence Base for Appraisal

The comparative appraisal of policy packages builds directly on the EU-plausible options formulated in Subsection 9.2 and is supported by a structured evidence base designed to answer a specific methodological question: not which issues matter politically, but which options are most credible, implementable, and capable of generating visible results within the EU's multi-level governance framework. The role of this section is therefore to clarify what kinds of sources are used to assess packages against feasibility, impact, and communicative potential, and how those sources are selected.

- **Four Layers of Evidence**

The evidence base is organised in four layers. First, **legal–institutional sources** establish competence fit, scope of action, and institutional viability. This layer includes EU primary and secondary law and their operational extensions, complemented where necessary by Commission communications, staff working documents, Council materials, European Parliament documents, and relevant agency guidance. Its function is to determine whether a measure is credible within the EU competence framework and whether a plausible governance route exists.

Second, **programme and financing documentation** is used to assess whether an option has an identifiable delivery pathway. This includes programme regulations,

implementation guidance, work programmes, monitoring and evaluation material, and performance or audit documentation related to the main EU funding and delivery vehicles used across themes. This layer is particularly important for feasibility because it clarifies whether a package can be linked to a realistic financing route, governance model, and reporting chain.

Third, **comparative and evaluative sources** are used to test impact plausibility and measurement feasibility. These sources document cross-country bottlenecks, baseline pressures, service gaps, workforce constraints, territorial inequalities, and comparable performance indicators. Their purpose is not to generate a new social diagnosis in this section, but to assess whether the proposed results chain of a package is plausible and whether progress could be tracked through meaningful outputs and outcomes over time.

Fourth, **contestation and legibility sources** are used to assess communicative potential as a property of governance design rather than of campaign technique. These sources help determine whether a package can be explained in plain terms, whether attribution to EU-level action is plausible, whether the measure is resilient to predictable fairness disputes or zero-sum framings, and whether simple proof indicators could be published regularly. In line with the broader framework of the Handbook, communicative potential is treated as a condition of political credibility linked to visible responsiveness, not as a substitute for substantive policy performance.

- **Source Selection and Comparability**

Across these layers, source selection remains purposive and mechanism-driven rather than exhaustive. Documents and instruments are retained if they meet four cumulative criteria:

- Legal and institutional relevance.
- Operational specificity.
- Thematic fit and cross-theme spillovers.
- Evaluability and communicability.

The same logic also defines exclusions: the study does not prioritise instruments that are purely declaratory, sources that cannot support meaningful monitoring, or interventions whose effects are too indirect to be credibly attributable within political timeframes.

Cross-national comparability is treated as conditional rather than automatic. Even where an EU instrument is formally common, baseline systems, service models, and administrative capacities vary substantially across Member States. The evidence base is therefore used not to assume uniform implementation conditions, but to identify where EU action can realistically raise floors, expand capacity, reduce bottlenecks, or improve comparability without requiring institutional uniformity.

Taken together, these four layers ensure that appraisal remains consistent, auditable, and traceable across themes. They provide the evidentiary foundation for comparing packages under common criteria while preserving the distinction between three analytical moments: the upstream identification of politically salient arenas, the construction of EU-plausible packages, and the later comparative appraisal through explicit scoring.

Comparative Prioritisation

Because this report is meant to support real choices, prioritisation cannot rely on intuition alone. Once options have been formulated as EU-plausible policy packages, the study applies a light, transparent form of structured comparative appraisal to assess them consistently against three transversal criteria: feasibility, impact, and communicative potential (Figure 7).²⁰ This approach is particularly relevant in light of the representational dynamics identified in Part I, where the credibility of policy responses depends not only on their substantive effects, but also on their perceived fairness, visibility, and responsiveness.

Figure 7. Comparative appraisal model for policy packages

- **Three Appraisal Criteria**

The scoring protocol follows three steps.

Step 1 — Standardised scoring

To prevent selective reasoning, each criterion is operationalised through the same standardised sub-questions for every package.

Feasibility (1–5):

Competence fit (is EU action clearly permissible?); instrument readiness (does the EU already have an operational vehicle?); administrative and data burden (what capacities are required?); time to visible results (can citizens notice progress within political timeframes?). This approach is consistent with the Commission's Better Regulation

²⁰ Marsh, K., IJzerman, M., Thokala, P., Baltussen, R., Boysen, M., Kalo, Z., Longrenn, T., Mussen, F., Peacock, S., Watkins, J., & Devlin, N. (2016). *Multiple criteria decision analysis for health care decision making—Emerging good practices: Report 2 of the ISPOR MCDA Emerging Good Practices Task Force*. *Value in Health*, 19(2), 125–137.

logic, which stresses proportionality, feasibility, and evidence-based design when comparing options.²¹

Impact (1–5):

Population reach (how many people can benefit?); intensity of change (expected reduction in key bottlenecks or improvement in access, quality, or stability); equity effects (does it narrow territorial or social inequalities?); system spillovers (does it unlock capacity in related domains?); sustainability (is the effect likely to persist beyond a pilot cycle?).

Communicative potential (1–5):

Citizen legibility (can benefits be stated in plain terms?); attribution clarity (can EU contribution be credibly linked to the improvement?); fairness robustness (is the measure resilient to predictable zero-sum or undeservingness framings?); proof indicators (are there simple indicators that can be published regularly?).

Step 2 — Weighting and sensitivity check

As a baseline, feasibility and impact carry the greatest weight because a measure that is not implementable or not meaningful will not restore credibility. Communicative potential is treated as an enabling condition for legitimacy and uptake, but not as a substitute for substance. For the purposes of comparative appraisal, the baseline weighting is 0.3 for feasibility, 0.4 for impact, and 0.3 for communicative potential. The study then applies a simple sensitivity check to verify whether the shortlist remains stable under reasonable alternative assumptions. This is aligned with standard option-comparison practice in EU appraisal guidance, which recommends transparent comparison methods and explicit handling of trade-offs.²²

Step 3 — Traceability and evidence notes

Each score is accompanied by a short evidence note that documents the reasoning behind the appraisal. As a minimum, each note cites (i) one legal or operational source showing competence, programme rules, or delivery pathways, and (ii) one comparative or evaluative source supporting impact plausibility, measurement feasibility, or implementation lessons. Where evidence is uneven, the note states uncertainty explicitly and identifies what would require further validation, for example through stakeholder interviews or pilot evaluation design. This creates a clear audit trail from diagnosis to package design, expected result, and indicator.

- **Output of the Appraisal Process**

The output of this process is not only a ranking, but a reasoned justification for why certain policy packages outperform others under the three criteria. This appraisal logic

²¹ European Commission. (2021). *Better regulation guidelines. guidelines (SWD(2021) 305 final)*. Publications Office of the European Union. https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-making-process/planning-and-proposing-law/better-regulation/better-regulation-guidelines-and-toolbox_en

²² European Commission. (2021). *Better regulation guidelines. guidelines (SWD(2021) 305 final)*. Publications Office of the European Union. https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-making-process/planning-and-proposing-law/better-regulation/better-regulation-guidelines-and-toolbox_en

is presented directly within each policy package, ensuring that scoring remains readable, traceable, and comparable across themes.

Study Limitations

Competence constrains. The study recognises limitations that are inherent both to the EU governance context and to this type of applied comparative policy research. The first is competence-related: in most of the domains covered by the Handbook, the EU acts primarily as a coordinator, enabler, or catalyst, while many decisive reforms still depend on Member State political will, administrative capacity, and implementation at regional or local level. This creates a structural gap between what can be proposed at EU level and what can ultimately be delivered in practice.

Cross-national heterogeneity. The second limitation is heterogeneity. Institutional arrangements, baseline service provision, labour-market structures, administrative capacity, and data availability vary significantly across Member States. As a result, comparability is never absolute, and a policy package that is plausible in one context may face different constraints or delivery conditions in another. The methodology therefore does not assume uniform implementation conditions, but works instead through conditional comparability, identifying where EU action can credibly raise floors, reduce bottlenecks, or strengthen coordination across diverse systems.

Temporal constraints. The third limitation is temporal. Many of the outcomes targeted in the Handbook—whether in health, housing, care, or labour-market integration—require time horizons that exceed annual budget cycles and often outlast political mandates. This creates an inherent tension between the need for visible progress within political timeframes and the reality that structural reform often produces effects gradually. For that reason, the study places particular emphasis on interim indicators, proof mechanisms, and monitoring routines that can make progress visible before longer-term impacts fully materialise.

Uneven evidence quality. Additional constraints arise from the quality and unevenness of available evidence. Documentary sources differ in precision, scope, and evaluative depth; some areas offer robust comparative data, while others depend more heavily on operational documentation, case-based lessons, or partial indicators.

Attribution and political interpretation. A further limitation concerns attribution and political interpretation. Even when EU-enabled action contributes materially to improved outcomes, citizens may not identify that contribution clearly, especially in domains where delivery remains national or local. Conversely, the EU may be blamed for failures in areas where it has only partial leverage. This means that legibility, proof indicators, and governance clarity are not secondary presentational issues, but part of the practical conditions under which policy credibility can be built or lost.

- **How the Methodology Responds**

These limitations are mitigated through triangulation, transparent criteria, and traceable reasoning. The methodology does not seek to eliminate uncertainty entirely; rather, it is designed to make assumptions visible, filter options through institutional realism, and compare packages through explicit criteria rather than intuition. Despite these constraints, the approach remains capable of producing solid, results-oriented recommendations that are compatible with multi-level governance realities and with citizens' expectations for fairness, transparency, and responsiveness.

10. Communicative Translation and Narrative Strategy

Purpose of This Section

The purpose of this section is to explain how shortlisted packages can be translated into a publicly legible, politically robust, and evidence-based communication strategy that supports uptake, accountability, and democratic credibility.

In this Handbook, communication is not treated as a separate layer added after policy design. Nor is it treated as a substitute for institutional performance. It is understood as the process through which EU-enabled action becomes recognisable to citizens in terms of what is changing, who is responsible, what can be verified, and on what timeframe. The goal is therefore not promotional. It is to make policy outputs and implementation pathways sufficiently visible and intelligible that citizens can judge performance in relation to their own lived experience.

This distinction matters because many of the policy packages proposed in the Handbook operate through multi-level governance, indirect levers, or enabling instruments rather than through direct EU delivery. If these mechanisms remain opaque, improvements may go unattributed, contested narratives may fill the gap, and even substantively strong measures may fail to generate political trust. Communicative translation is therefore treated as part of the broader logic of legibility, attribution, proof, and accountability.

Five Principles for Communicative Translation

The communication strategy follows five principles. First, competence discipline. Communication must remain strictly consistent with what the EU can and cannot do. It should never imply that the Union directly delivers services where delivery is primarily national, regional, or local. Its role must be described with precision: setting rights floors, enabling investment, coordinating reform, supporting implementation, improving comparability, and strengthening monitoring and accountability. Second, citizen legibility. Policy packages should be translated into terms that are recognisable in everyday life. The key question is not whether a package is technically sophisticated, but whether people can understand what it is expected to change in practice: shorter waits, lower cost burdens, more reliable services, clearer access routes, stronger support, or more stable transitions into work. Third, proof-led communication. Communication should be anchored in a small set of visible outputs and indicators that can be published regularly. The purpose is to avoid overclaiming and to ensure that public communication remains tied to verifiable progress rather than symbolic commitment alone. Fourth, fairness robustness. Communication must anticipate predictable contestation. Many policies in the fields covered by the Handbook can be attacked through zero-sum framings, undeservingness narratives, or claims of technocratic overreach. A robust communication strategy therefore explains not only what a package does, but why it is fair, who benefits, and how burden-sharing and access are justified. Fifth, continuity over spectacle. Credibility is built through repeated, intelligible updates rather than isolated campaign moments. The communication system should therefore be organised around a regular rhythm of explanation, monitoring, and proof rather than around one-off announcements.

From Policy Package to Public Legibility

Each shortlisted package should be translated through a common communicative structure (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Communication as democratic accountability

At minimum, communication should answer four questions: what problem is being addressed, what is being done, who is responsible for what, and what will change and how will people know. The starting point should be a problem that citizens already recognise in lived terms rather than in institutional jargon. The package must then be described in a way that makes the intervention logic understandable without flattening it into a slogan. Because most packages operate through shared governance, communication must clarify the respective roles of the EU, Member States, local actors, service providers, employers, or other implementing institutions. Every claim should be tied to a visible output, a proof indicator, and a realistic time horizon. Where change is gradual, communication should distinguish clearly between early signals of progress and longer-term structural outcomes.

This structure ensures that communication remains aligned with the methodology of the Handbook. It prevents packages from being presented either as technocratic abstractions or as politically inflated promises. It also strengthens traceability by linking public claims to the same logic of problem, lever, implementation pathway, and indicator that underpins the analytical design of the report.

Building a Proof Architecture

A communication strategy of this kind depends on proof architecture. Proof should not be understood as a single success story or a retrospective narrative of achievement, but as a repeatable system of public evidence. This requires a limited set of indicators that are understandable, updateable, and clearly connected to each package's intended effects. Different packages will naturally require different indicators, but the general logic is the same. Indicators should show whether progress is occurring in a form that citizens can interpret without specialist knowledge. They should also help distinguish between outputs that are directly visible in the short term and broader outcomes that require longer implementation horizons.

In practical terms, the communication system should be organised around predictable proof moments: regular updates tied to a small number of published indicators, supported where necessary by short explanatory material that clarifies what the indicator means, what it does not yet show, and what the next stage of implementation is expected to deliver. This regularity matters because it turns communication into an accountability routine rather than an episodic exercise in justification. Although the communication principles are transversal, narrative translation should remain sensitive to differences across policy domains.

Adapting Narratives Across Policy Domains

The public meaning of visible improvement is not the same in health, housing, care, work–family balance, or labour-market integration. Each theme therefore requires a specific adaptation of the common communication logic. In health, the dominant communicative axis is likely to be access, security, and continuity of care. In housing, the key terms are more likely to be stability, affordability, and fairness. In work–family balance and care, communicative translation depends more heavily on time, reliability, and burden-sharing. In labour-market integration, it turns more clearly on pathways, progression, recognition, and protection against drift or exclusion. What must remain common across themes is the discipline of translation: no package should be communicated as a generic institutional achievement. It should be communicated as a specific intervention into a recognisable everyday bottleneck, with a clear explanation of the relevant governance chain and the evidence through which progress can be judged.

Feedback Loops and Democratic Accountability

Communication should also include simple feedback mechanisms that strengthen verification and democratic accountability. The objective is not performative consultation, but a credible loop through which citizens, service users, professionals, and stakeholders can identify implementation problems, test whether published indicators remain intelligible, and signal where delivery is falling short. What matters is that opportunities for feedback are visibly connected to monitoring and follow-up. If people are invited to respond but cannot see how that response informs communication, implementation, or corrective action, distrust may deepen rather than recede. In this sense, communication is not an ornamental layer added after policy design, but part of the accountability infrastructure through which public performance becomes assessable.

Further Guidance and Supplementary Resources

The domain chapters in Part III present the most policy-relevant outputs of this approach: priorities, policy packages, and recommendations. Readers wishing to explore the fuller analytical development underpinning each domain—including the complete application of the common framework and the domain-specific communicative narratives through which policy action can be translated into publicly legible terms—can consult the supplementary material available online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

Readers seeking more specialised guidance on political communication strategies, online media environments, and the communication of gender-based needs may also

consult UNTWIST Deliverable 10.1²³, which provides complementary recommendations and communication guidelines for democratic actors, institutions, civil society organisations, and media stakeholders. That document develops additional proposals on messaging, platforms, governance, and evidence-based communication that sit alongside the policy-focused approach of this Handbook.

²³ Nerino, V., Rothermel, A.-K., & Businger, M. (2026). Deliverable 10.1 of the UNTWIST project: Summary of Findings (WP10). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19204396>.

PART III — FROM EU ACTION TO RESULTS: POLICY PACKAGES AND PRIORITISATION

The preceding part has established the analytical and institutional framework through which citizen-defined priorities can be translated into plausible EU-level action. By structuring recurrent bottlenecks, mapping the Union's legal and governance capacities, and identifying the operational levers available within a multi-level system, the analysis has defined the conditions under which **policy intervention remains both feasible and meaningful**.

On this basis, Part III translates the analytical and methodological framework developed in Parts I and II into policy guidance across the five priority domains identified in the study: healthcare, housing, education and skills, childcare and work-life balance, and labour market integration (Figure 9). It is designed as a practical resource for policymakers and other relevant actors, bringing together the main policy priorities, policy packages, and recommendations in a more accessible and action-oriented format. Readers wishing to explore the fuller analytical discussion underpinning each domain chapter, including the complete application of the framework set out in Part II, can **consult the supplementary material available online** (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

The objective is not to propose abstract recommendations, but to identify policy options that can be realistically implemented, generate visible improvements in citizens' everyday experience, and sustain political credibility over time. For this reason, the policy packages are evaluated against three transversal criteria: feasibility, impact, and communicative potential, making trade-offs explicit and allowing for transparent prioritisation.

Taken together, this approach ensures that the transition from citizen concerns to policy action remains traceable, auditable, and oriented towards results that are both institutionally grounded and publicly recognisable.

Figure 9. Summary of policy priorities and packages per domain

11. Healthcare Systems: Strengthening Access, Quality and Responsiveness. EU Policy Packages.

Why This Domain Matters

Healthcare stands out as the most universal and urgent theme across the UNTWIST evidence base. In this domain, gendered positional deprivation emerges when barriers to timely, affordable, and good-quality care undermine citizens' sense of fairness, security, and institutional support, particularly in relation to gendered health needs, caregiving responsibilities, and unequal exposure to service fragmentation. When these conditions remain insufficiently addressed, they contribute to a representation gap, as citizens perceive that political actors are not responding effectively to one of the most basic domains of everyday life.

What Citizens Told Us Across Europe

Accessing good-quality healthcare is discussed in both focus groups and participatory workshops in all countries. In every country included in UNTWIST (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary), people speak of systems that feel strained—whether through long waiting times, rising costs, or difficulties navigating services. Across contexts, there is a shared concern about underfunding and the need for greater public investment. Mental health repeatedly surfaces as a gap, sometimes framed as an issue for schools, as in Spain, or linked to generational pressures, as in the United Kingdom. Yet the nuances differ: in Denmark, frustrations centre on hospital work environments and expensive dental care; in Germany, debates tie into broader welfare-state critiques and calls for gender-specific medical research; in Hungary, the under-financing of healthcare and the emigration of doctors to Western Europe dominate the conversation. The United Kingdom adds another dimension with widespread anxiety about the privatisation of the National Health Service and a call for more preventive health policies.

Gendered Experiences of Healthcare Insecurity

Access to healthcare emerges as a gendered source of grievance primarily through differences in experiential intensity and framing. Women consistently articulate healthcare as a high-salience issue embedded in long-term life trajectories, often linked to reproductive health, mental health, and their role as primary caregivers for children or elderly relatives. Their accounts emphasise continuity of care, professional responsiveness, and the cumulative strain produced by fragmented or under-resourced systems. Healthcare shortcomings are frequently interpreted as amplifying vulnerability and inequality over time, and as reflecting broader deficits in institutional recognition. Men, by contrast, tend to approach healthcare more episodically, discussing it mainly in relation to acute needs or isolated encounters. Their evaluations focus on system efficiency, waiting times, or perceived mismanagement, and are less often connected to broader narratives of social inequality or care responsibilities.

What the Survey Evidence Shows

Quantitative evidence confirms this is the most strongly supported topic across the board. In UNTWIST survey accessing good-quality healthcare emerges as one of the most consistently prioritised issues across the six countries examined. As shown in Figure 10, it is ranked as the top policy concern by voters across all three party families in Spain, the United Kingdom, and Hungary, where reported salience is particularly high. In Denmark, healthcare also ranks prominently, reaching first place among RWPP

voters and remaining within the top three priorities for MR and ML electorates. In Germany and Switzerland, the issue is somewhat less dominant but still remains among the leading concerns across all party families.

Figure 10. Ranking of "accessing good quality healthcare" as the most challenging aspect of life for people like them among RWPP, MR, and ML voters

Figure 11. Total percentage of voters (broken down by gender) who believe that "accessing good quality healthcare" is the most challenging aspect of life for people like them

The overall pattern confirms that healthcare is a broad-based valence issue rather than a narrowly segmented demand. Concern about access to quality healthcare extends across ideological blocs and across gender groups (Figure 11), indicating widely shared expectations regarding affordability, availability, and system performance.

At the same time, the quantitative similarities between women and men should be read alongside the qualitative evidence on how healthcare problems are experienced. While women often report slightly higher levels of concern, the issue is also highly salient among male respondents in every country examined. The significance of gender differences lies less in whether healthcare matters, and more in how shortcomings are interpreted: women more frequently connect healthcare to continuity of care, caregiving burdens, reproductive and mental health needs, and long-term insecurity, whereas men more often emphasise efficiency, waiting times, and system performance. Even so, the central finding remains that access to good healthcare commands broad support across both gender groups.

From Diagnosis to Policy Action

The following sections presents priorities, policy packages, and recommendations in concise form. Extended analytical material for each domain is available in the supplementary material available online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

11.1. Policy Priorities of Health

Purpose of This Section

This section defines the policy priorities for health by moving from the concerns documented in the previous section to the recurrent bottlenecks that most consistently structure dissatisfaction in this field. The aim is not to restate the evidence already presented, but to perform the intermediate analytical step described in Section 9.1: translating politically salient concerns into analytically defined problem clusters that can support structured policy development.

Within the framework developed in Part I, this analytical step is particularly important because healthcare is not only a domain of service provision, but also a domain in which failures of responsiveness are directly experienced as failures of institutional protection. Where access is delayed, fragmented, or unreliable, citizens are more likely to interpret these shortcomings not as isolated technical problems but as signs that public institutions are no longer adequately responding to their needs. In this sense, the section identifies the bottlenecks through which gendered positional deprivation is produced and sustained in the health domain, and through which representation gaps become politically salient.

The section therefore filters the health-related concerns identified in the project material through comparative and evaluative evidence in order to distinguish visible symptoms from underlying drivers and to identify those leverage points that are both empirically supported and relevant for EU-level action.

Retained Policy Priorities

On that basis, three policy priorities are retained for health:

- System capacity strain linked to chronic under-resourcing.
- Mental health as a structural gap in provision.
- A rebalancing towards prevention and health promotion.

Figure 12 shows a summary of the six policy packages developed within this domain of Health for each of the policy priorities that are retained in the analysis.

Figure 12. Policy priorities and packages for Health (excerpt from Figure 9)

Policy Priority 1: System Capacity Strain and Under-Resourcing

Why This Is a Priority

Across the project material, dissatisfaction with healthcare is most consistently associated with difficulties of access, delays in obtaining care, and the perception that services are increasingly difficult to rely on. Read analytically, these concerns point, less to isolated service failures, than to a broader pattern of system capacity strain. In this sense, what appears in the qualitative and survey material as frustration with waiting times, rushed consultations, uneven service availability, or difficulties navigating care can be interpreted as the visible expression of a recurrent bottleneck: demand pressing against systems operating with limited reserve capacity.

This bottleneck is politically significant because it directly affects one of the domains in which citizens assess whether public institutions are fair, reliable, and responsive. When waiting times lengthen, access becomes uncertain, or services become harder to navigate, shortcomings in healthcare are experienced not only as material inconvenience but as evidence of weakening institutional support. In this way, capacity

strain contributes to gendered positional deprivation by intensifying insecurity and perceived neglect, particularly among those whose everyday lives are more strongly shaped by sustained contact with health systems.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative evidence supports retaining this problem cluster as a priority. Waiting-time and access data directly confirm this bottleneck across the project countries. According to OECD Health at a Glance 2025, only 41% of the population in Hungary reported being satisfied with the availability of quality healthcare, well below the OECD average of 64%. In Spain, Germany, and Denmark, unmet healthcare needs due to system-related reasons — predominantly waiting times — remain a recognised pressure, with waiting times cited as the leading cause of unmet needs in multiple European countries.²⁴ The UK illustrates the scale of the problem most starkly: NHS England reported an overall elective-care backlog of 7.46 million in December 2024.²⁵ Across OECD countries, elective surgery waiting times increased on average by 27–30% in the three years following the COVID-19 pandemic and have not fully recovered. As OECD Health at a Glance 2025 further highlights, higher per capita health investment is consistently associated with longer life expectancy and greater satisfaction with healthcare availability. Yet, while OECD countries spend around 9% of GDP on health on average—and notably less in parts of Central and Eastern Europe—these differences reflect uneven system capacity. Spending trajectories have also evolved unevenly in response to major global shocks, including the 2008 financial crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, and more recent disruptions linked to geopolitical tensions and inflationary pressures. These indicators confirm that capacity constraints and access delays are not merely episodic perceptions: they reflect broader structural weaknesses and implementation pressures across health systems.

Implications for EU-Level Action

For that reason, system capacity strain is retained here as a policy priority. It represents a recurrent bottleneck that is empirically supported, clearly linked to lived dissatisfaction, and sufficiently tractable to support EU-level option development around capacity reinforcement, service coordination, and performance visibility.

Policy Priority 2: Mental Health as A Structural Gap

Why This Is a Priority

A second recurring pattern in the material concerns mental health. The issue is not simply that mental health is considered important, but that it appears as an area where public provision is often experienced as delayed, fragmented, or uneven. Analytically, this suggests a structural gap in provision rather than a secondary or residual

²⁴ OECD. (2025). *Health at a Glance 2025: OECD Indicators*. OECD Publishing. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/health-at-a-glance-2025_8f9e3f98-en.html.

²⁵ NHS England. (2025, February 13). Waiting list falls as NHS staff treated record numbers last year. Available at: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/2025/02/waiting-list-falls-as-nhs-staff-treated-record-numbers-last-year/>.

weakness. The recurring relevance of first access, continuity of support, and weak coordination across services indicates that dissatisfaction is generated not only by the prevalence of need, but by the inability of systems to provide timely and coherent responses.

This problem cluster is also highly relevant to the broader logic of the Handbook. In mental health, the gap between recognised need and actual provision is especially likely to be experienced as institutional abandonment, because difficulties of access often arise precisely where vulnerability is greatest and where continuity of support is most necessary. As a result, mental health shortcomings can intensify perceptions of unfairness, invisibility, and neglect, reinforcing a representation gap in a domain that citizens increasingly perceive as central to social well-being.

Comparative Evidence

This interpretation is reinforced by comparative evidence. Recent OECD data show both the scale and the provision gap directly.²⁶ One in five adults across OECD and EU27 countries experiences mild-to-moderate depressive symptoms, conditions that often go unrecognised and untreated and risk escalating into more severe disorders. Across countries, two thirds of people seeking mental health support report difficulties accessing it. Prevalence and provision gaps differ significantly across the project countries: higher rates of moderate or severe depressive symptoms are recorded in Hungary, while mental health workforce and service coverage remain below OECD averages in Spain. In 2022, reported prevalence of anxiety and depression remained at least 20% above pre-pandemic levels across OECD countries. Crucially, spending on prevention in mental health and the broader system remains at 3% of total health expenditure on average — well below what evidence suggests is needed to address demand at the structural level. From a gender perspective, these challenges are further shaped by distinct patterns of risk and service use: although men are more than three times as likely to die by suicide (17.2 compared to 5 per 100 000), women more frequently report self-harm behaviours and are hospitalised at higher rates, indicating different forms of unmet need. Moreover, cross-country variation in the gender gap in suicide mortality rates is substantial—reaching around 20 points in Hungary, about 10 in Denmark and Germany, and below 10 in Spain— consistently reflecting higher suicide mortality among men than women and suggesting that access barriers and system responses interact with gendered vulnerabilities in uneven ways. These data support the view that mental health is not a marginal concern but a recurrent area of unmet need, and that current systems often struggle to translate formal recognition of the issue into accessible and continuous care pathways.

Implications for EU-Level Action

Mental health is therefore retained as a policy priority because it captures a structural weakness that is both socially consequential and institutionally relevant. It identifies a problem cluster that is empirically grounded, recurrent across contexts, and open to policy development around access pathways, integration of services, early intervention, and continuity of care.

²⁶ OECD. (2025b). *Health at a Glance 2025: OECD Indicators*. OECD Publishing. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/health-at-a-glance-2025_8f9e3f98-en.html.

Policy Priority 3: Prevention and Health Promotion as A Sustainability Strategy

Why This Is a Priority

A third problem cluster emerges from the gap between immediate service pressures and the more limited role still assigned to prevention and health promotion. Across the material, concerns about overload, delayed intervention, and reactive service delivery point toward a broader analytical diagnosis: health systems remain too strongly oriented toward managing deterioration once pressures have already intensified.

This matters not only for long-term public-health performance, but also for political responsiveness. Where systems repeatedly intervene too late, citizens experience institutional action as reactive, fragmented, and insufficiently protective. Prevention is therefore relevant to the Handbook's broader framework because it concerns the ability of public institutions to respond before avoidable pressures become crises, thereby strengthening credibility and reducing the accumulation of dissatisfaction.

Comparative evidence

Objective evidence supports this interpretation. Objective evidence supports this interpretation and points directly to the cost of underinvestment. OECD Health at a Glance 2025 reports that there were over three million premature deaths in 2023 among people aged under 75 across OECD countries that could have been avoided through better prevention and healthcare interventions — with diseases of the circulatory system and cancer accounting for almost half of all deaths. This burden is strongly gendered, as avoidable mortality among men (303 deaths per 100 000) is roughly twice that of women (149 per 100 000), and varies considerably across countries, from around 390 deaths per 100 000 in Hungary to 114 in Switzerland, with most other project countries clustering around the OECD average of 222.²⁷ Despite this, preventive healthcare spending returned to just 3% of total health expenditure in 2023, after a temporary rise to 6% during the COVID-19 pandemic. Eurostat data²⁸ confirm the same pattern at country level: preventive-care expenditure remained around 0.57% of GDP at EU level in 2022, with similarly modest shares in the project countries (Denmark 0.81%; Germany 0.47%; Spain 0.45%; Hungary 0.37%). The OECD Secretary-General noted in November 2025 that countries should increase the share of total health spending allocated to preventive interventions, currently insufficient to address the major risk factors — obesity, smoking, harmful alcohol use — that drive up healthcare costs in the longer term. These figures reinforce the interpretation that prevention remains comparatively underweighted relative to its potential contribution to reducing avoidable pressure on acute and hospital-based services. In that sense, the issue is not only one of public-health ambition, but of system design: insufficient preventive investment weakens the capacity of health systems to contain future demand and address risks earlier.

²⁷ OECD. (2025b). *Health at a Glance 2025: OECD Indicators*. OECD Publishing. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/health-at-a-glance-2025_8f9e3f98-en.html.

²⁸ Eurostat. (2025, March). Preventive health care expenditure statistics. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Preventive_health_care_expenditure_statistics.

Implications for EU-Level Action

Prevention and health promotion are therefore retained as a policy priority because they identify a recurrent structural imbalance with clear implications for long-term system sustainability. The priority is analytically linked to the concerns documented above, supported by comparative evidence, and plausibly open to EU-level action through instruments that strengthen primary care, public-health capacity, outreach, monitoring, and equitable access to preventive services.

The following sections examine how these priorities can be addressed within the EU's institutional and governance framework, by mapping the action space through which policy responses can be realistically developed.

11.2. Policy Recommendations

Purpose of the Policy Packages

The six policy packages presented in this section respond directly to the three priorities identified in Section 11.1: reducing system capacity strain and waiting-time pressure, addressing mental health as a structural gap in provision, and strengthening prevention as a long-term sustainability strategy. Together, they are designed to address a key representation gap identified in the UNTWIST analysis by targeting the material conditions through which gendered positional deprivation is produced in the health domain.

How the Packages Are Assessed and Ranked

Table 1. List of policy packages on health, ordered by weighted scores

Proposal package	Feasibility (1–5)	Impact (1–5)	Communicative potential (1–5)	Weighted score
Tracking Waiting Times in Europe	5	4	5	4.6
European Pact for the Health Workforce	4	5	4	4.4
European Medicines Availability and Shortages Plan	4	4	5	4.2
Cross-Border Digital Health in Europe	5	3	4	4.0
School and Community Mental Health Support	4	4	4	4.0
Affordable Essential Dental Care Pilots	3	4	5	3.8

In line with the analytical framework developed in Part II, each package is developed as an EU-plausible intervention—combining a legal or regulatory lever, a governance route, a financing channel, and a set of monitorable outputs—and evaluated against three criteria: feasibility, impact, and communicative potential. The scoring follows a light MCDA approach consistent with the Commission’s Better Regulation guidelines, with impact weighted most heavily to ensure that prioritisation reflects genuine improvement in citizens’ lives rather than administrative convenience. The packages are sequenced from the highest to the lowest weighted score, and the appraisal makes trade-offs explicit so that choices remain transparent and revisable (Table 1).

Why These Packages Matter

By improving access, continuity, workforce capacity, and preventive reach, these measures aim to strengthen institutional responsiveness in a domain central to everyday life, thereby reducing the plausibility of blame-based and scapegoating narratives built on unresolved healthcare dissatisfaction.

POLICY PACKAGE 1: Tracking Waiting Times in Europe

Proposed score: Feasibility 5 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 5 (weighted score: 4.6)

About: This policy package establishes an EU-wide benchmarking system to monitor and compare healthcare waiting times across Member States through a public Access Dashboard. It focuses on standardising indicators to make system bottlenecks visible and politically actionable without interfering in national management. By creating transparency, it enables peer learning and targeted technical support to improve patient time to care. The proposal is highly feasible because it builds on existing EU reporting structures and can therefore be developed at low administrative cost. Its main strength lies in its communicative power: it offers citizens a clear and verifiable metric showing how European coordination can help protect access to healthcare.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – system capacity strain and under-resourcing.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 5)

Competence fit. Very strong, because the instrument works as a coordination and transparency tool aligned with an EU role in monitoring, comparability, mutual learning, and follow-up rather than in reorganising national delivery.

Instrument readiness. High, because the EU already operates comparative health-system reporting ecosystems, including indicator production and country profiling, so the dashboard extends existing practice rather than creating a new architecture.

Administrative/data burden. Relatively low, because the approach supports phased implementation through a small set of highly comparable procedures and indicators before scaling up across more heterogeneous data systems.

Time to visible result. Fast in visibility terms, because publication itself creates comparability and public exposure from the first reporting cycle, even if actual reductions in waiting times depend on stronger follow-up routines.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to keep narrow and disciplined: start with comparable procedures, lock definitions early, include equity breakdowns, and build in peer learning plus structured follow-up so reporting does not become symbolic.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Broad, because waiting times are a widely experienced barrier to access across health systems rather than a niche issue affecting only specific groups.

Intensity of change. Meaningful but design-dependent, because benchmarking can drive improvement when linked to incentives and structured follow-up, whereas publication alone is not transformative.

Equity effects. Potentially positive, because disaggregated indicators can make unequal access by income, region, or age more visible; without that, equity gains are likely to remain weaker.

System spillovers. Relevant but conditional, because better access metrics can improve capacity planning, referral pathways, and coordination routines only if benchmarking is connected to reform support.

Sustainability. Strong if embedded in recurring reporting-and-follow-up cycles, but weaker if the system drifts into symbolic compliance without visible improvement mechanisms.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to pair benchmarking with governance: clear definitions, equity breakdowns, risk-adjusted interpretation where needed, and a mandatory follow-up routine that converts visibility into pressure for improvement.

Communication (score: 5)

Citizen-legibility. Extremely strong, because “time to care” is intuitive and easy for citizens to verify against their own experience of the health system.

Attribution clarity. Unusually clean for a health package, because the EU can plausibly claim responsibility for comparability, transparency, and follow-up without pretending to run hospitals directly.

Fairness robustness. Robust under contestation, because the package increases visibility and accountability rather than redistributing scarce services directly, which makes it easier to defend.

Proof indicator. Strong, because progress can be shown through published indicators, trend improvements, and documented follow-up actions that provide clear proof points.

Narrative fit. Very good, because the package works naturally within a broader issue-level narrative of protecting and renewing Europe’s health model through visible access and accountability.

POLICY PACKAGE 2: European Health Workforce Pact

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 5 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.4)

About: This policy package proposes an EU-enabled coordination-and-capacity Pact designed to strengthen the health workforce across Member States. The EU's role is to set shared standards for planning and retention while aligning funding to modernise working environments and training pipelines. Although Member States retain authority over pay and staffing, the Pact provides the structural support needed to address chronic under-resourcing and vacancy pressures. It delivers high structural impact by addressing the binding constraint of many health systems: having enough professionals to ensure timely and quality care. While results are medium-to-long term, the initiative is credible because it focuses on valuing and sustaining the workforce that makes universal access possible.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – system capacity strain and under-resourcing.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Strong but not maximal, because the EU has a credible role in coordination, capacity-building, and funding alignment, while core levers such as pay and staffing decisions remain national.

Instrument readiness. Solid, because EU-level channels already exist for workforce planning support, skills initiatives, and reform assistance, so the Pact can be built by combining existing tools rather than inventing a wholly new framework.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because implementation requires multi-actor coordination, common data and forecasting standards, and monitoring of mobility and retention, although this remains manageable with a clear division of labour.

Time to visible result. Medium-to-slow, because workforce pipelines are long and structural shortages cannot be corrected quickly, even if some earlier gains may appear through retention and working-conditions measures in targeted settings.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to keep the Pact disciplined: the EU should set orientations, fund enabling measures, and build implementation capacity, while Member States carry the main responsibility for staffing and employment changes.

Impact (score: 5)

Population reach. Very broad, because workforce constraints shape access, quality, prevention capacity, and mental health provision across the health system rather than in a single service area.

Intensity of change. Structurally high, because addressing workforce shortages expands what health systems are actually able to deliver rather than producing only marginal improvements at the edges.

Equity effects. Potentially strong, because interventions can be targeted at territorial gaps, shortage professions, and retention problems in areas where underserved groups depend on fragile capacity.

System spillovers. Large, because stronger workforce capacity improves waiting times, continuity of care, mental health scaling, and prevention delivery across multiple parts of the system.

Sustainability. High if the Pact shifts from general commitment to measurable workforce stability through retention, continuity, vacancy reduction, and long-term planning rather than short-term fixes.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to prioritise retention and working conditions, support task redesign where appropriate, expand training throughput in shortage areas, and target territorial inequities explicitly.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Clear but less immediate than waiting times, because people understand that enough staff matters, even if the benefits are not always visible through a single simple metric.

Attribution clarity. More difficult than in other packages, because responsibility is shared and workforce pipelines are long, so the EU contribution must be made visible through indicators and a disciplined enabling narrative.

Fairness robustness. Generally solid, but not friction-free, because questions around mobility, rural coverage, and uneven distribution can generate contestation if fairness is not framed carefully.

Proof indicator. Credible proof requires a small public-facing set of indicators such as continuity, vacancy rates, targeted staff-to-patient ratios, and time-to-first-appointment improvements.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package works well within a broader narrative of valuing and sustaining the backbone of care rather than treating the workforce as a technical input.

POLICY PACKAGE 3: European Medicines Availability and Shortages Plan

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 5 (weighted score: 4.2)

About: This policy package strengthens EU-enabled resilience against medicine shortages by expanding joint procurement and enhancing shortage intelligence. The EU provides the coordination and tools to monitor supply chains, while Member States implement these measures within their national contexts to ensure medicine availability. It addresses the root causes of shortages through better data, diversified supply, and shared stockpiling, delivering a high structural impact on patient care. The proposal is highly feasible because it builds on existing frameworks such as HERA and the broader Critical Medicines trajectory. Its greatest strength is its communicative potential, as the promise that medicines are available when needed is concrete, intuitive, and widely resonant.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – system capacity strain and under-resourcing.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Strong but shared, because the EU has a credible role in preparedness, coordination, joint procurement frameworks, and resilience rules, while procurement and reimbursement decisions remain largely national.

Instrument readiness. High, because operational building blocks already exist through joint procurement options, preparedness functions, and a wider legislative and strategic trajectory supporting institutional commitment.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because better shortage intelligence and stronger procurement coordination require more data-sharing and governance, although the burden remains manageable if focused on critical products.

Time to visible result. Mixed but reasonably credible, because visibility and coordination gains can appear in the short term, while deeper supply resilience and diversification are clearly medium-to-long term.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to design the package as EU-enabled and Member State-activated, expanding procurement where value-added is clear, strengthening shortage intelligence, and keeping national roles explicit.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Broad, because medicine shortages affect large populations and directly undermine a basic condition of access to care across health systems.

Intensity of change. High in principle but not automatic, because outcomes depend on combining several instruments and addressing root causes rather than relying on procurement alone.

Equity effects. Potentially positive, because the package can reduce unequal exposure to shortages across Member States and vulnerable groups, although benefits may cluster in higher-capacity systems if design is weak.

System spillovers. Significant, because fewer shortages improve continuity of care, reduce avoidable complications, and lower system stress caused by substitutions and delayed treatment.

Sustainability. Stronger if short-term mitigation is tied to longer-term diversification and resilience incentives, but weaker if the package only manages recurring crises without changing structural vulnerability.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Best organised as a staged results chain, linking short-term data and coordination gains to medium-term procurement and stockpiling performance and long-term supply resilience.

Communication (score: 5)

Citizen-legibility. Extremely strong, because the promise is simple and concrete: the medicine should be available when it is needed.

Attribution clarity. Plausible and fairly clean, because EU coordination of procurement, shortage monitoring, and resilience rules is explainable without claiming control over all national medicine systems.

Fairness robustness. Very robust, because the idea that essential medicines should not be missing is easy to defend across ideological and political lines.

Proof indicator. Strong proof points include fewer critical shortage events, shorter shortage durations, better stock visibility, and documented coordinated mitigation actions.

Narrative fit. Very good, because the package fits naturally within a resilience and protection frame and translates that frame into a highly tangible everyday outcome.

POLICY PACKAGE 4: Cross-Border Digital Health in Europe

Proposed score: Feasibility 5 / Impact 3 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.0)

About: This policy package focuses on making the European dimension of care tangible by enabling cross-border tele-health and data interoperability. The EU's role is to provide the infrastructure and standards, notably through MyHealth@EU, so that vital information such as ePrescriptions and patient summaries can safely follow citizens across borders. It reduces administrative friction and medical errors for mobile workers and residents in border regions, making healthcare more seamless and secure. The proposal is highly feasible because it builds on an established legal basis and existing digital services. Its main strength lies in offering clear and intuitive promises: your medical data is available and your prescriptions work wherever you are in Europe.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – system capacity strain and under-resourcing.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 5)

Competence fit. Very strong, because cross-border rights, interoperability standards, and enabling infrastructure are all areas where EU-level coordination has an obvious and credible role.

Instrument readiness. High, because the package builds on an existing legal basis and operational cross-border services rather than on a speculative future digital architecture.

Administrative/data burden. Contained, because implementation can be staged through modular and standards-driven use cases instead of requiring a broad and unrealistic promise of full digital transformation at once.

Time to visible result. Relatively fast in defined use cases, because progress can be seen early in areas such as ePrescriptions working abroad and patient-summary exchange coverage, even if full interoperability maturity is slower.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to prioritise a small set of high-value services, standardise governance and technical requirements early, and scale only once reporting and adoption are stable.

Impact (score: 3)

Population reach. Meaningful but limited, because benefits are concentrated among mobile citizens, border regions, and people involved in cross-border care episodes rather than the entire population.

Intensity of change. Moderate, because the package improves safety and efficiency by reducing information gaps and duplication, but does not directly relieve core domestic capacity constraints.

Equity effects. Positive in some settings, because border populations and mobile workers can benefit substantially, although gains may accrue more to digitally mature systems unless adoption support is targeted.

System spillovers. Real but modest, because interoperability reduces administrative friction and duplicative testing, yet these spillovers remain smaller than those associated with workforce or waiting-time reforms.

Sustainability. High if cross-border interoperability becomes embedded in routine care pathways and supported by stable governance, but dependent on trust and continued standardisation.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Best focused on medication continuity, emergency continuity, and chronic patients who relocate or travel, so interoperability becomes part of normal care rather than a niche digital add-on.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Strong, because promises such as “your prescription works abroad” and “your key medical information follows you safely” are tangible and easy to understand.

Attribution clarity. Fairly good, because cross-border enablement is clearly European, although communication must avoid overclaiming broader domestic health-system effects.

Fairness robustness. Generally defensible, but not automatic, because privacy and data-protection concerns can generate contestation if safeguards are not foregrounded clearly.

Proof indicator. Credible proof points include the number of cross-border ePrescriptions filled, patient-summary coverage, reduced administrative steps, and selected safety indicators.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package makes the European dimension of healthcare tangible in a way that citizens can understand through practical use cases.

POLICY PACKAGE 5: School and Community Mental Health Support

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.0)

About: This policy package creates an EU-funded replication facility designed to scale successful mental health models that connect schools to primary care and community services. The EU acts as an enabler by providing funding, standards, and training,

while local systems handle actual delivery. By using schools as accessible entry points, the package aims to reduce service fragmentation and ensure clear referral pathways for children and adolescents. It addresses a structural gap in provision with significant equity potential, especially if targeted at underserved areas. While the EU's role is indirect, the initiative is intuitive for families and supports a clear narrative of modernising public services to respond to the mental health needs of younger generations.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 2 – mental health as a structural gap.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Strong but indirect, because the EU can credibly act through funding, standards, evaluation, and training, while actual service delivery remains national and local.

Instrument readiness. Good, because there are already operational vehicles for EU-funded replication, systems strengthening, and cross-country learning that can support a structured rollout.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because scaling requires coordination across education, health, and social services as well as pathway monitoring, though complexity can be reduced through standardised minimum requirements.

Time to visible result. Medium, because some improvements such as first-contact times and referral completion can appear relatively early, while symptom-level mental health outcomes are slower and more context-dependent.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to fund a limited number of replicable models with clear staffing, referral, supervision, and safeguarding requirements, alongside implementation-readiness support where needed.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Broad for children and adolescents, because schools provide an accessible and familiar setting for early contact and prevention-oriented support.

Intensity of change. Potentially high in access terms, because school-based entry points can reduce fragmentation and improve first-contact capacity, although intensity depends on implementation fidelity and specialist links.

Equity effects. Strong if targeted well, because underserved territories and schools can benefit most where cost, distance, and stigma currently block access to support.

System spillovers. Relevant, because the package can reduce pressure on families, improve linkage to community care, and ease some specialist bottlenecks through earlier identification and triage.

Sustainability. Promising but conditional, because long-term success depends on integration into routine services and on workforce support rather than on short-term project logic alone.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to prioritise early identification, clear referral pathways, continuity mechanisms, and evaluation based on access outcomes such as first assessment time, referral completion, and dropout.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Strong, because mental health access problems are widely understood and schools as entry points are intuitive for many families.

Attribution clarity. Moderate, because delivery is local and the EU role is enabling, so European contribution must be made visible through branding, standards, and published results.

Fairness robustness. Generally solid but sensitive, because schools' role and the politics of mental health can generate contestation unless support, safeguards, and non-stigmatising design are emphasised.

Proof indicator. Credible proof requires simple measures such as faster first contact, school coverage, referral completion, and continuity indicators rather than overpromising symptom resolution.

Narrative fit. Very workable, because the package fits a broader narrative of modernising public services to meet contemporary needs in a visible and socially relevant way.

POLICY PACKAGE 6: Affordable Essential Dental Care Pilots

Proposed score: Feasibility 3 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 5 (weighted score: 3.8)

About: This policy package creates an EU-funded pilot and replication facility designed to improve access to affordable essential dental care as part of a broader prevention and health-promotion strategy. Its purpose is to test and scale delivery models that address one of the most visible gaps in early and basic care: situations in which cost, waiting times, or weak territorial coverage prevent people from receiving timely dental treatment and routine follow-up before problems become more severe. Rather than attempting to harmonise national dental benefit systems, the package focuses on a clearly defined essential scope of care, such as pain relief, treatment of infection, urgent restorative care, and basic preventive check-ups, and supports pilots that can demonstrate practical improvements in early access, affordability, and continuity. The EU's role is to act as an enabler through co-funding, common evaluation criteria, and structured comparison of models, while Member States and local providers remain responsible for service organisation and delivery. The strength of the package lies in making prevention tangible through a highly legible everyday issue: where essential dental care is delayed or unaffordable, minor problems are more likely to escalate into avoidable pain, more complex treatment needs, and wider inequalities in health.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 3 – prevention and health promotion as a sustainability strategy.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 3)

Competence fit. Moderate rather than strong, because core levers such as benefit design, reimbursement, and service organisation remain national or subnational, so the EU can only play an enabling role.

Instrument readiness. Credible at pilot level, because EU co-funding, evaluation, and structured comparison provide a plausible route, whereas regulatory harmonisation in dental coverage would be much less feasible.

Administrative/data burden. Manageable but not light, because pilots require local delivery partners, outcome monitoring, and evaluation capacity, with feasibility depending on implementation readiness and a proportionate indicator set.

Time to visible result. Relatively fast at pilot level, because target settings can show early gains in treatments delivered, urgent-care waiting times, and cost barriers, although broader scaling is slower and politically harder.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to keep the EU role narrow, define a limited essential-care scope, select high-plausibility settings, and require co-funding and realistic scaling plans only where capacity exists.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Broad in underlying need but narrower in direct reach, because dental cost barriers affect many people even though pilot coverage will initially be territorially and operationally limited.

Intensity of change. High for beneficiaries, because timely access to essential dental care can prevent deterioration, reduce pain, and avoid escalation into more complex treatment, even if system-wide transformation remains limited without scaling.

Equity effects. Strong if targeted properly, because underserved groups and territories are most exposed to unmet need driven by cost, distance, and waiting times.

System spillovers. Relevant, because earlier dental access can reduce avoidable complications, lower downstream treatment burdens, and strengthen the preventive side of wider health protection.

Sustainability. Conditional, because successful pilots only become durable if they are integrated into stable financing and delivery arrangements rather than remaining isolated local experiments.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to define the scope clearly around pain, infection, urgent restorative care, and preventive check-ups, target underserved groups, and measure whether earlier access reduces unmet need and prevents escalation.

Communication (score: 5)

Citizen-legibility. Extremely strong, because dental pain, delayed treatment, and cost barriers are concrete experiences that citizens recognise immediately.

Attribution clarity. Credible if disciplined, because EU co-funding, branded pilots, and published indicators make contribution visible without implying that Europe is setting national dental entitlements.

Fairness robustness. Very robust when framed around essential care and prevention, because the package addresses a basic and recognisable need without overreaching into a broader entitlement debate.

Proof indicator. Strong proof points include reduced unmet need, shorter urgent-care waits, numbers treated in underserved areas, uptake of preventive check-ups, and lower reported cost barriers.

Narrative fit. Excellent, because it works as a visible example of prevention in practice: addressing everyday health needs before delay, neglect, or affordability problems generate wider harm.

12. Housing and Essential Services: Reducing Affordability Pressures and Access Gaps. EU Policy Packages.

Why This Domain Matters

Housing and social services are another cross-cutting concern, often inseparable from the broader cost-of-living crisis. In this domain, gendered positional deprivation emerges when rising housing costs, insecure access to housing, fragmented support systems, and unequal exposure to administrative and material strain undermine citizens' sense of fairness, security, and institutional support, particularly in relation to care responsibilities, household stability, and the ability to sustain an autonomous life. When these conditions remain insufficiently addressed, they contribute to a representation gap, as citizens perceive that political actors are not responding effectively to one of the most consequential domains of everyday life.

What Citizens Told Us Across Europe

Accessing affordable housing, social services, and other goods is present in both focus groups and participatory workshops across all countries in UNTWIST (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary). In general, people complain about rising housing costs, diminished welfare provision, and unfair access to subsidies. The fairness of who receives benefits—particularly whether immigrants are perceived as “deserving”—emerges especially in Spain, where participants resent subsidies going to others while still demanding more support for themselves. In Hungary, housing loans offered to families are said to have driven up property prices, leaving single women and families with children struggling to find rentals. Germany highlights the inadequacy of the welfare state and often frames the debate in chauvinistic terms, while Denmark emphasizes deteriorating elder care. In the UK, housing concerns appear alongside the burden of elder care, which families feel forced to take on due to underinvestment in social care. Workshops, meanwhile, often return to the plight of young people, who struggle to achieve independence due to rising rents and barriers to home ownership.

Gendered Experiences of Housing Insecurity

Gender differences in this domain relate to how material insecurity is experienced and narrated. Women frame housing affordability and access to social services as foundational conditions for everyday stability, particularly in households with dependent children or other care obligations. Their narratives stress precarity, administrative complexity, and the emotional burden of navigating fragmented welfare systems, often

linking these difficulties to constrained life choices and long-term insecurity. Men also acknowledge rising costs and access barriers, but tend to situate these concerns within broader market dynamics or macroeconomic trends. Social services are discussed more abstractly and less frequently through sustained personal reliance, while housing is more often framed in terms of individual economic positioning and achievement.

What the Survey Evidence Shows

Quantitative data confirms the pervasiveness of these worries. The quantitative analysis of the UNTWIST survey shows that access to affordable housing, social services, and other essential goods emerges as another highly prioritised issue across the six countries examined. As shown in the Figure 13, it ranks among the top two concerns across all three party families in Germany, Spain, and Switzerland, where material pressures linked to housing costs and everyday affordability appear particularly acute. In Hungary, the issue remains within the top three priorities across RWPP, MR, and ML electorates. In Denmark and the United Kingdom, it is somewhat less dominant but still remains firmly within the upper tier of public concerns.

Figure 13. Ranking of "access to affordable housing, social services, and other essential goods" as the most challenging aspect of life for people like them among RWPP, MR, and ML voters

The overall pattern indicates that housing and access to essential services function as broad-based socio-economic valence issues rather than narrowly segmented demands. Concern extends across ideological blocs and national contexts, suggesting

widely shared expectations regarding affordability, security, and fair access to social support.

At the same time, the quantitative similarities between women and men (Figure 14) should be read alongside the qualitative evidence on how these pressures are experienced. Women often report slightly higher levels of concern, but the issue is also highly salient among male respondents in every country examined. The significance of gender differences lies less in whether housing and service access matter, and more in how insecurity is interpreted and lived. Women more frequently connect these pressures to household stability, caregiving responsibilities, administrative burdens, and constrained long-term life choices, whereas men more often frame them through market conditions, economic competition, and individual material advancement. Even so, the central finding remains that access to affordable housing and reliable social support commands broad support across both gender groups.

Figure 14. Total percentage of voters (broken down by gender) who believe that “access to affordable housing, social services, and other essential goods” is the most challenging aspect of life for people like them

From Diagnosis to Policy Action

Taken together, these patterns place housing and social provision among the most widely shared priorities in the dataset, second only to healthcare in overall cross-group consensus. The issue combines immediate material insecurity—linked to affordability, access, and everyday stability—with a broader symbolic contest over fairness, deservingness, and the distribution of social support.

The following sections presents priorities, policy packages, and recommendations in concise form. Extended analytical material for each domain is available in the supplementary material online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

12.1. Policy Priorities of Housing

Purpose of this section

This section identifies the policy priorities for housing by converting the concerns set out in the previous section into a more focused diagnosis of the bottlenecks that most consistently shape dissatisfaction in this field. Its purpose is not to recapitulate the evidence already presented, but to carry out the intermediate step outlined in Section 9.1: moving from broad salience to analytically defined problem structures that can support policy design.

As highlighted in Part I, this analytical step is particularly important because housing is not only a domain of material provision, but also a domain in which failures of responsiveness are directly experienced as failures of protection, stability, and fairness. Where affordability collapses, supply remains inaccessible, or support systems fail to prevent exclusion, citizens are more likely to interpret these shortcomings not as isolated market outcomes but as signs that public institutions are no longer adequately responding to their needs. In this sense, the section identifies the bottlenecks through which gendered positional deprivation is produced and sustained in the housing domain, and through which representation gaps become politically salient.

In methodological terms, this involves distinguishing between the visible manifestations of housing stress, the structural conditions that sustain it, and the points at which intervention is most plausibly open to EU-level influence. The section therefore retains only those problem clusters that are both empirically supported and sufficiently recurrent across contexts to justify further option development.

Retained Policy Priorities

On that basis, three policy priorities are identified for housing:

- Affordability pressure and housing insecurity.
- Supply and delivery bottlenecks that block access.
- Severe housing exclusion and the weak linkage between housing and support services.

Figure 15 shows a summary of the six policy packages developed within this domain of Housing for each of the policy priorities that are retained in the analysis.

Figure 15. Policy priorities and packages for Housing (excerpt from Figure 9)

Policy Priority 1: Affordability Pressure and Housing Insecurity

Why This is a Priority

Accounts of housing pressure rarely take the form of references to market indicators or macroeconomic trends. Instead, dissatisfaction tends to centre on the practical consequences of affordability constraints: rising rents, barriers to entry, repeated moves, overcrowded living arrangements, and the persistent difficulty of securing housing on stable terms. Taken analytically, these patterns point to a recurrent bottleneck in the form of affordability pressure linked to housing insecurity. The issue is not only that housing costs are high, but that access to a stable home is increasingly experienced as uncertain, unequal, and weakly protected.

This bottleneck is politically significant because it directly affects one of the domains in which citizens assess whether public institutions are fair, reliable, and responsive. When housing costs become unmanageable or access to stable accommodation becomes uncertain, these pressures are experienced not only as economic hardship but as evidence of weakening institutional support. In this way, affordability pressure contributes to gendered positional deprivation by intensifying insecurity and perceived neglect, particularly among those whose everyday stability is more directly shaped by care obligations, household dependency, and sustained reliance on public support.

Comparative Evidence

This interpretation is reinforced by comparative evidence. Comparative data directly confirm the scale and structural nature of affordability pressure.²⁹ In 2024, 8.2% of the EU population spent more than 40% of their disposable income on housing costs — a figure that rises sharply among the most vulnerable: 31.1% of those living below 60% of median income experience housing cost overburden, compared to only 3.8% of those above the threshold (in some of the project countries such as Germany, Spain or the UK more than half of low-income tenant households are overburdened by housing costs, one of the highest rates in the OECD³⁰). Over the longer term, between 2010 and 2023 EU house prices rose by 48% and rents by 27.8%, well outpacing wage growth in most Member States. In Hungary, house prices more than tripled over the same period (+191%), compressing affordability across income groups. This pressure also exhibits a clear gendered dimension, as women are consistently more exposed to housing cost overburden than men across Europe (8.6% compared to 7.8% in the EU on average), with particularly pronounced gaps in high-cost contexts such as Switzerland and Denmark. Taken together, these indicators reflect a structural mismatch between housing costs and household incomes that cannot be attributed to isolated market cycles or individual hardship.

Implications for EU-Level Action

Affordability pressure and housing insecurity are therefore retained as a policy priority because they capture a recurrent source of dissatisfaction that is empirically grounded, cross-nationally visible, and relevant for policy development at EU level.

Policy Priority 2: Supply and Delivery Bottlenecks That Block Access

Why This Is a Priority

A second recurring pattern in the material concerns is the limited availability of housing that is accessible in practical, timely, and socially adequate terms. Taken analytically, this suggests that part of the housing problem lies not only in affordability pressure, but in supply and delivery bottlenecks that restrict access even where demand is clearly established. In this respect, recurring references to the absence of available options, long waiting periods, and the mismatch between what is built and what is needed can be read as the visible manifestations of a broader implementation constraint: housing systems are often unable to convert recognised need into delivered, usable, and appropriately targeted supply.

This problem cluster is also highly relevant to the broader logic of the Handbook. In housing, the gap between recognised need and actual availability is especially likely to be experienced as institutional failure because access depends not only on prices, but

²⁹ Eurostat. (2025, November). *Living conditions in Europe - housing*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Living_conditions_in_Europe_-_housing.

³⁰ OECD. (2024). *OECD Affordable Housing Database*. OECD Publishing. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/en/data/datasets/oecd-affordable-housing-database.html>.

on whether governance systems are capable of producing and protecting adequate supply. As a result, delivery bottlenecks can deepen perceptions of unfairness, exclusion, and neglect, reinforcing a representation gap in a domain that citizens increasingly perceive as central to social and economic security.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative evidence lends support to this interpretation, even where the link is partly indirect. Comparative data on housing supply directly supports this interpretation. According to the OECD Affordable Housing Database³¹, housing construction increased only slightly in many OECD and EU countries over the past decade, with construction activity in Spain actually declining relative to 2011 — one of the few countries in the OECD to register a structural fall. Social housing, which should act as the primary buffer for low- and middle-income households locked out of the private market, represents on average only 6–7% of the total housing stock across OECD and EU countries, and its relative size has declined in several Member States over the past two decades due to slower construction and privatisation of existing stock. This constraint is also visible in housing adequacy outcomes³²: nearly 29% of individuals below 60% of median income in the EU live in overcrowded households—defined as lacking a sufficient number of rooms relative to household composition—with similarly high rates in countries such as Hungary and Germany, indicating that even where housing is accessed, it often fails to meet basic standards of adequacy. Survey data indicate that 48% of Europeans aged 18–34 share accommodation with roommates, 16% live with parents or guardians while searching for housing, and more than half of home sharers would prefer to live alone.³³ These indicators confirm that the bottleneck is not solely one of price: supply has structurally failed to convert acknowledged need into available, affordable, and appropriate housing at scale.

Implications for EU-Level Action

This interpretation is important because it helps distinguish price pressure from pipeline failure. Affordability constraints may intensify dissatisfaction, but where housing delivery remains too slow, too fragmented, or too weakly oriented toward affordable provision, access problems are likely to persist even when financial support measures are introduced. The issue is therefore not reducible to market scarcity alone; it also reflects the institutional, administrative, and investment conditions that shape whether additional supply can be mobilised in time and at the relevant scale.

Supply and delivery bottlenecks are therefore retained as a policy priority because they capture a recurrent access constraint that is analytically distinct from affordability pressure, directly relevant to the structuring of dissatisfaction, and sufficiently tractable to support EU-level option development.

³¹ OECD. (2024). *OECD Affordable Housing Database*. OECD Publishing. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/en/data/datasets/oecd-affordable-housing-database.html>.

³² Eurostat. (2025, November). *Living conditions in Europe - housing*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Living_conditions_in_Europe_-_housing.

³³ HousingAnywhere – Half of young home sharers in Europe prefer to live alone (29 July 2025). Available at: <https://housinganywhere.com/home-sharers-in-europe>.

Policy Priority 3: Severe Housing Exclusion and Weak Housing–Services Linkage

Why This Is a Priority

A third recurring pattern in the material concerns the most acute forms of housing insecurity, where difficulties of access and affordability give way to situations of severe exclusion, instability, or unsafe living conditions. Taken analytically, these concerns point not only to extreme housing deprivation, but to a wider institutional weakness in the connection between housing and support services. In this respect, references to temporary accommodation, precarious living arrangements, repeated instability, or situations in which a relatively limited shock triggers housing loss can be read as the visible expression of a compound bottleneck: housing exclusion is intensified when social, health, employment, and administrative support systems fail to connect in a timely and coherent way.

This problem cluster is politically significant because it marks the point at which housing stress becomes not only chronic but socially visible, materially severe, and closely associated with institutional breakdown. Where exclusion deepens and support systems fail to intervene coherently, citizens are more likely to perceive not only material abandonment but a broader failure of public protection. In this way, severe housing exclusion reinforces gendered positional deprivation by turning cumulative vulnerability into an acute and publicly legible form of neglect.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative evidence directly supports retaining severe housing exclusion as a distinct policy priority. As of 2024, over two million people in OECD and EU countries experienced homelessness each year — a figure that represents only the most visible segment of a much larger population in precarious or inadequate housing.³⁴ In Europe alone, FEANTSA estimates that at least 1.3 million people experienced homelessness in 2023, a 44% increase over the previous five years, driven by rising rents, stagnant social housing supply, and insufficient integration of support services.³⁵ While men make up the majority of the homeless population in Europe, women account for a smaller share of recorded cases but often experience homelessness in less visible ways; due to safety concerns and care responsibilities, they are more likely to rely on temporary or informal arrangements and are therefore underrepresented in official statistics despite facing significant risks. Energy poverty provides another direct indicator of severe deprivation: in 2024, 9.2% of EU residents could not afford to keep their home adequately warm, rising to nearly 18% in Spain. Critically, 10.1% of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion in the EU reported experiencing discrimination when looking for housing in 2024 — more than double the rate among those not at risk (4.7%) — showing how housing exclusion and service access failures are systemically

³⁴ OECD. (2025). *OECD monitoring framework to measure homelessness*. OECD Publishing. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/oecd-monitoring-framework-to-measure-homelessness_3e98455b-en.html.

³⁵ FEANTSA. (2024). *Ninth overview of housing exclusion in Europe 2024*. European Federation of National Organisations Working with the Homeless. Available at: <https://www.feantsa.org/resources/9th-overview-of-housing-exclusion-in-europe-2024>.

linked.³⁶ These data confirm that the most acute forms of housing insecurity are not marginal anomalies but a structural outcome of compounding failures in affordability, supply, and integrated support.

Implications for EU-Level Action

This priority is analytically distinct from the previous two. Whereas affordability pressure concerns the cost and insecurity of maintaining housing, and supply bottlenecks concern the limited availability of suitable provision, the issue here is the point at which housing instability becomes acute and existing systems fail to provide integrated protection. The problem is therefore not only one of insufficient housing, but of weak coordination across the services that should prevent exclusion from deepening once vulnerability has emerged.

Severe housing exclusion and weak housing–services linkage are therefore retained as a policy priority because they capture a recurrent and institutionally revealing form of dissatisfaction: one in which housing stress becomes socially visible, materially severe, and closely tied to failures of coordination, prevention, and protective response. As such, this problem cluster is empirically supportable, analytically distinct, and relevant for EU-level option development.

12.2. Policy Recommendations

Purpose of the Policy Packages

The six policy packages presented in this section respond directly to the three priorities identified in Section 12.1: relieving affordability pressure and housing insecurity, addressing supply and delivery bottlenecks that restrict access, and tackling severe housing exclusion and the weak linkage between housing and support services. Together, they are designed to address a key representation gap identified in the UNTWIST analysis by targeting the material conditions through which gendered positional deprivation is produced in the housing domain.

How the Packages Are Assessed and Ranked

In line with the analytical framework developed in Part II, each package is developed as an EU-plausible intervention and evaluated against the same three criteria used throughout the Handbook: feasibility, impact, and communicative potential, with impact carrying the greatest weight. The packages draw on the full range of instruments available to the EU in this field—from the Affordable Housing Plan and the European Semester to EIB financing and STR data regulation—and are designed to operate across different time horizons, so that faster-acting governance and transparency measures complement longer-term investment in supply and social housing. The appraisal makes priorities and trade-offs explicit, and packages are ordered from highest to lowest weighted score.

³⁶ Eurostat. (2025, November). *Living conditions in Europe - housing*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Living_conditions_in_Europe_-_housing.

Table 2. List of policy packages on housing, ordered by weighted scores

Proposal package	Feasibility (1–5)	Impact (1–5)	Communicative potential (1–5)	Weighted score
Expanding Social and Affordable Housing	4	5	4	4.4
Preventing Homelessness and Scaling Housing First	4	4	5	4.3
Supporting First-Time Buyers While Preserving Affordability	4	4	5	4.3
Early Warning and Rapid Support for Housing Stress	5	4	4	4.3
Tenant Protection in High-Stress Areas	3	4	5	4.0
Affordable Renovation and Energy Protection	4	4	4	4.0

Why These Packages Matter

By improving affordability, expanding access, strengthening supply, and preventing acute exclusion, these measures aim to strengthen institutional responsiveness in a domain central to everyday life, thereby reducing the plausibility of blame-based and scapegoating narratives built on unresolved housing insecurity.

POLICY PACKAGE 1: Expanding Social and Affordable Housing in Europe

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 5 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.4)

About: This policy package aims to increase the supply of social, public, and permanently affordable housing across Europe. The EU's role is not to build housing directly, but to make delivery easier by reducing investment barriers, simplifying state-aid rules, and helping mobilise large-scale finance through the Affordable Housing Plan and the EIB-led pan-European housing investment platform. In practice, this would help Member States, regions, and cities move more projects from planning to construction, while keeping homes affordable over the long term. The package is strong because it addresses the core housing problem at scale: there are not enough affordable homes, and existing delivery systems are too slow and fragmented. Its main promise is clear and tangible: helping public authorities and non-profit providers deliver more homes that people can actually afford.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 2 – supply and delivery bottlenecks that block access.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Strong but enabling rather than direct, because the package fits an EU role in state-aid simplification, coordination, pipeline building, and finance mobilisation without implying control over land, permitting, or allocation.

Instrument readiness. Solid, because key operational building blocks are already emerging through the Commission's Affordable Housing Plan and the EIB's housing investment agenda rather than needing to be created from scratch.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because a platform-and-pipeline model can standardise templates and reduce fragmentation, but delivery still depends on substantial local administrative capacity that varies across places.

Time to visible result. Medium-to-slow in citizen terms, because stock expansion takes time, even if earlier progress can be shown through faster project preparation, financing approvals, and a visible delivery pipeline.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to design the package as EU-enabled and locally executed, with simplified state aid, standardised templates, scaled platform finance, and long-duration affordability rules attached to financed stock.

Impact (score: 5)

Population reach. Very broad over time, because expanding public, social, and permanently affordable stock can create stable access routes for large numbers of households otherwise priced out of the market.

Intensity of change. Structurally high, because stock expansion changes the supply balance itself and creates a stabilising buffer instead of only managing scarcity at the margins.

Equity effects. Potentially strong, because durable affordability and targeted allocation can benefit households under the greatest affordability stress, although gains weaken if units drift back toward market conditions.

System spillovers. Significant, because more permanently affordable supply can reduce pressure on homelessness services, emergency accommodation, social assistance, and labour mobility constraints linked to displacement.

Sustainability. High if affordability covenants are durable and financing pipelines become institutionalised, but weaker if investment remains one-off or protections expire too quickly.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to anchor a staged results chain from projects prepared and financed faster, to units delivered and allocated under affordability rules, to long-term net growth of permanently affordable stock.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Clear but not immediate, because "more homes you can actually afford" is highly understandable even if visible benefits take time to materialise.

Attribution clarity. Plausible if disciplined, because the EU can credibly claim to enable finance and reduce investment barriers without pretending to control local planning, allocation, or housing systems.

Fairness robustness. Generally strong, because the package expands supply rather than reallocating scarcity, although frustration may grow if delivery is too slow or uneven across territories.

Proof indicator. Credible proof can come from units delivered, affordability duration, beneficiary profiles, locations, and a public pipeline tracker showing what is financed and when it is expected to come online.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package fits a broader narrative of restoring access and rebuilding affordability capacity, though communication must manage expectations about time lags.

POLICY PACKAGE 2: Preventing Homelessness and Scaling Housing First

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 5 (weighted score: 4.3)

About: This policy package aims to prevent homelessness earlier and expand Housing First approaches across Europe. Its goal is not only to respond once people lose housing, but to reduce entries into homelessness and improve access to stable housing with support services. The EU's role would be to help cities and Member States scale proven models by providing coordination through the European Platform on Combatting Homelessness, aligning funding and implementation guidance, setting a small set of common standards, and supporting a shared method for counting and monitoring homelessness. Local authorities would still deliver housing and services on the ground. The package is strong because it combines a clear social objective with a concrete governance improvement: fewer people falling into homelessness, faster access to stable housing, and better evidence on what works. Its public promise is simple and legible: preventing homelessness where possible, and ensuring that when it happens, the response is faster, more stable, and more effective.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 3 – severe housing exclusion and weak housing–services linkage.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Strong but indirect, because the package fits an EU role in coordination, standards, funding alignment, and monitoring rather than direct delivery of housing and services.

Instrument readiness. Good, because practical routes already exist through the European Platform on Combatting Homelessness and ESF+ guidance supporting homelessness actions and Housing First approaches.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because the package adds reporting, counting, and minimum-standard requirements, though these are manageable and necessary for credible scaling and performance tracking.

Time to visible result. Relatively fast in targeted settings, because prevention and Housing First can reduce rough sleeping and improve housing stability early on, even if sustained system-wide reductions take longer.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to keep the design EU-enabled and locally delivered, with minimum standards, technical assistance, funding templates, and clear proof that the EU is enabling and auditing progress rather than running services directly.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Narrower than general affordability packages, but highly relevant, because homelessness affects fewer people numerically while representing acute exclusion and visible system failure.

Intensity of change. High for beneficiaries, because Housing First and prevention can transform housing stability quickly, although impact depends on fidelity, service integration, and access to housing.

Equity effects. Strong, because the package concentrates benefits on the most excluded groups, provided delivery systems do not privilege easier cases over high-need populations.

System spillovers. Significant, because reductions in chronic homelessness can lower pressure on emergency, health, and justice systems while improving wider social inclusion outcomes.

Sustainability. Conditional, because long-term gains depend on durable housing pathways and stable support services, and are harder to maintain where housing supply remains severely constrained.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to build a staged results chain from counting and targeting, to Housing First scale-up, to reductions in chronic homelessness and shorter homelessness durations supported by retention and re-entry data.

Communication (score: 5)

Citizen-legibility. Extremely strong, because rough sleeping and repeated exclusion are immediately visible and the moral claim that homelessness should not be normal is easy to grasp.

Attribution clarity. Plausible if proof-led, because the EU can credibly claim to convene, finance, standardise, and monitor without pretending to replace local authorities.

Fairness robustness. Very robust, because the narrative is protective rather than redistributive and frames homelessness as avoidable harm and a breach of the social contract.

Proof indicator. Strong proof can come from comparable counts, reduced chronic homelessness, improved housing retention, and visible programme expansion across cities using shared monitoring methods.

Narrative fit. Excellent, because the package fits rights-based and protection narratives and supports a credible European ambition to reduce and ultimately end homelessness.

POLICY PACKAGE 3: Helping Young People Access Affordable Housing

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 5 (weighted score: 4.3)

About: This policy package is designed to help young people and first-time buyers overcome the upfront deposit barrier. It would do so through a socially protected loan scheme, delivered through national promotional banks and supported by EU-aligned financing channels. The key condition is that homes supported through the scheme would remain affordable over time, so that public support does not simply raise prices or benefit only one generation of buyers. Instead, it would gradually help build a wider stock of homes with lasting affordability protections. The EU's role would be to provide a common template and financing support that can be adapted to different national mortgage systems. The package is attractive because it addresses a highly visible problem—young adults being locked out of housing access—while linking financial support to a clear public return: more accessible entry into housing without losing affordability in the long run.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – affordability pressure and housing insecurity.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Credible but enabling, because the EU does not run mortgage markets directly but can support standardised tools through coordination with national promotional banks and aligned financing channels.

Instrument readiness. Fairly strong, because the design is already administratively plausible and EU-level housing investment architecture is developing in ways that could host standardised templates.

Administrative/data burden. Manageable but not negligible, because banking-style delivery is relatively straightforward, though national differences in mortgage systems, consumer protection, and eligibility rules require modular adaptation.

Time to visible result. Relatively fast for eligible households, because approvals and purchase completions can appear early, while longer-term results depend on enforcing affordability covenants over time.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to keep the instrument narrow, standardised, and auditable, targeting first-time buyers who can service a mortgage but lack the deposit, while using clear caps and simple reporting through promotional banks.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Significant but not universal, because the package directly helps young adults facing deposit constraints rather than all households under housing pressure.

Intensity of change. High at household level, because it can unlock emancipation, mobility, and household formation quickly, though structural impact depends on preserving affordability through durable covenants.

Equity effects. Potentially positive but safeguard-dependent, because benefits can become regressive without income and asset targeting, while covenant design improves intergenerational fairness by preserving affordability over time.

System spillovers. Relevant, because easier access to housing can support labour mobility and reduce rental churn, although demand-side effects can also create price pressures if anti-inflation safeguards are weak.

Sustainability. Strong if covenants are durable and enforceable, because the measure then builds a permanent affordability asset rather than operating as a one-off subsidy.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to hard-wire anti-inflation safeguards through strict eligibility rules, price caps, exclusion of investors, and long-duration affordability covenants that remain central even where supply measures are limited.

Communication (score: 5)

Citizen-legibility. Extremely strong, because the promise directly matches a familiar experience: being able to pay monthly costs but being locked out by the deposit barrier.

Attribution clarity. Plausible if disciplined, because the EU can credibly claim to enable a common financing tool while Member States and promotional banks implement it within national systems.

Fairness robustness. Stronger than a simple buyer subsidy, because the covenant helps frame the package as building lasting affordability rather than handing out one-generation purchasing power.

Proof indicator. Credible proof can come from purchase completions, beneficiary profiles, default rates, and the accumulation of covenant-protected units over time and across resale cycles.

Narrative fit. Very strong, because the package fits narratives around blocked life trajectories, fair access, and converting public support into lasting affordability rather than temporary relief.

POLICY PACKAGE 4: Early Warning and Rapid Support for Housing Stress

Proposed score: Feasibility 5 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.3)

About: This policy package would help the EU detect housing stress earlier and organise a faster response when pressure starts to rise. It would do this by creating a common set of indicators to track problems such as affordability pressure, supply bottlenecks, or severe exclusion, and by linking those indicators to a follow-up process within the European Semester. When warning signs cross agreed thresholds, the EU would not take over housing policy, but it would trigger a structured response: clearer diagnosis, peer review, technical support, and better alignment of available funding. The EU's role is therefore to provide measurement, comparability, and coordinated follow-up, while Member States and local authorities remain responsible for delivery. The strength of the package lies in its preventive logic: instead of reacting only when the crisis is already politically explosive, it helps public authorities act earlier, more consistently, and on the basis of shared evidence.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 2 – supply and delivery bottlenecks that block access.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 5)

Competence fit. Very strong, because the package is a coordination instrument aligned with EU strengths in common definitions, transparency, and follow-up while remaining compatible with subsidiarity.

Instrument readiness. High, because the European Semester already exists as a recurring governance channel and the package extends an operating cycle rather than constructing a new institutional architecture.

Administrative/data burden. Relatively low to moderate, because core indicators already exist in EU statistical infrastructure and the main challenge lies in phased threshold-setting, timely reporting, and disaggregation.

Time to visible result. Fast in governance terms, because stress maps, threshold crossings, and activation of support plans can become visible quickly even if affordability outcomes emerge more slowly.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to implement the system in phases with a small core stress set and automatic procedural activation, so follow-up does not depend on ad hoc political discretion.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Potentially broad, because improved stress governance can target areas where large numbers of people face acute access and affordability pressures.

Intensity of change. Meaningful but indirect, because the package can change response speed and accountability, although it does not lower prices or build housing by itself.

Equity effects. Potentially positive, because better disaggregation can direct support toward groups and places under the highest stress, though gains depend on whether triggered responses produce real relief.

System spillovers. Relevant, because shorter response lags and better governance can reduce downstream exclusion, displacement, and political volatility caused by unmanaged housing pressure.

Sustainability. Strong if embedded in the Semester cycle with recurring “what changed?” reporting, but weaker if the system becomes only a reporting exercise without operational consequences.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to connect the short-term production of stress maps and support plans to medium-term delivery improvements and longer-term changes in affordability and exclusion indicators.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Fairly strong, because stress maps and warning triggers are understandable, although benefits remain abstract unless they are translated into visible action in high-pressure areas.

Attribution clarity. Plausible if disciplined, because the EU can credibly claim to measure stress consistently, activate follow-up, and align enabling support without claiming control over rents or local planning.

Fairness robustness. Generally robust, but only if measurement is linked to help, because otherwise the package risks looking like naming problems without improving conditions.

Proof indicator. Credible proof comes from published dashboards, activation records, implemented response packages, and trend changes in stress indicators across repeated cycles.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package supports a narrative of turning diffuse crisis into governable and auditable action, provided triggered support is visible.

POLICY PACKAGE 5: Tenant Protection in High-Stress Areas

Proposed score: Feasibility 3 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 5 (weighted score: 4.0)

About: This policy package is designed to help contain housing pressure and improve tenant stability in the areas where the crisis is most acute. It would give Member States and cities a clearer EU-supported framework for acting in high-stress housing areas, including measures to reduce excessive pressure from short-term rentals and to protect access to long-term housing. The EU would not impose one single model, but it would make local action more effective by defining a common toolbox, setting criteria for when stronger measures can be activated, and using short-term rental registration and data-sharing systems to improve enforcement and track results. National and local authorities would still choose and apply the instruments within their own legal competences. The package is strong because it turns a politically visible grievance into a more enforceable and evidence-based response. Its public promise is straightforward: where housing markets are under severe strain, authorities should be able to act earlier, more clearly, and with better tools to protect residents.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – affordability pressure and housing insecurity.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 3)

Competence fit. Limited rather than strong, because core levers such as rent controls, eviction protections, and tenancy law remain primarily national or regional, so the EU can only support an enabling protocol and toolbox.

Instrument readiness. Reasonably solid at the enabling level, because EU-level short-term rental registration and data-sharing infrastructure already provide a useful enforcement backbone even if local instrument choice remains heterogeneous.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate to high, because local enforcement capacity and monitoring remain essential, and operational burden varies sharply across cities despite better data infrastructure.

Time to visible result. Relatively fast in targeted areas, because enforcement and containment measures can reduce illegal listings and stabilise pressure sooner than broader structural housing reforms.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to design the package as EU-enabled and locally activated, with transparent stress thresholds, an enforceable toolbox focused on registration and anti-fraud measures, and a standard monitoring pack.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Concentrated but substantial, because the package targets high-stress zones where affordability pressure is most acute and where large renter populations can be affected directly.

Intensity of change. High in targeted contexts, because containment can provide near-term relief and stability, although it does not solve structural shortages across the wider system.

Equity effects. Plausible but dependent on design, because protections can benefit lower- and middle-income renters facing displacement, yet effects must be tracked to ensure they do not mainly help already-secure tenants.

System spillovers. Relevant, because greater tenant stability and lower acute pressure can reduce displacement, homelessness inflows, and strain on social services, especially when linked to longer-term supply measures.

Sustainability. Conditional, because long-term success depends on sustained enforcement and adaptive governance, while blunt or weakly monitored controls can create side effects.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to structure the package through a staged chain from registration and enforcement, to lower short-term rental pressure and improved tenant stability, to moderated affordability stress over time with equity breakdowns.

Communication (score: 5)

Citizen-legibility. Extremely strong, because the package speaks directly to daily experiences of rising costs, insecurity, and loss of housing access in high-stress cities and regions.

Attribution clarity. Plausible if disciplined, because the EU contribution is technical and visible through common registration and data frameworks that make local action more enforceable.

Fairness robustness. Strong, because the protection narrative is easy to defend when framed as proportionate intervention in clearly stressed areas rather than as blanket interference in housing markets.

Proof indicator. Credible proof includes registration outputs, illegal listings reduced, stabilisation indicators in high-stress areas, and visible reporting linking trigger thresholds to toolbox use and results.

Narrative fit. Very strong, because the package fits a protection and stability narrative well, as long as communication stays proof-led and avoids claiming that the EU sets rents directly.

POLICY PACKAGE 6: Affordable Renovation and Energy Protection

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.0)

About: This policy package is designed to ensure that housing renovation improves affordability rather than undermining it. The core idea is simple: when public money supports renovation, the result should be lower energy bills, better housing conditions, and protection against displacement. The package links the EU's renovation agenda under the recast Energy Performance of Buildings Directive with equity-focused support through the Social Climate Fund, so that energy upgrades do not end up pushing vulnerable households out of their homes. The EU's role is to provide the regulatory framework, funding support, and common conditions, while national and local authorities carry out renovations and apply tenant protections. The strength of the package lies in making the social promise of the green transition concrete: better homes, lower bills, and no affordability loss as a result of renovation.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – affordability pressure and housing insecurity.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Strong but conditional, because the package fits EU competence in building performance regulation and social transition funding while leaving rent-setting and tenancy law to national systems.

Instrument readiness. High, because the recast EPBD and the Social Climate Fund already provide a legal and financial backbone rather than requiring a new policy architecture.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because affordability safeguards and monitoring add requirements, but these can be handled through standard templates if local administrative capacity is adequate.

Time to visible result. Medium, because targeted renovations can deliver relatively fast bill relief for some households, while scaling to a larger affordability effect takes longer.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to apply a simple common conditionality template linking public renovation support to bill reduction, affordability retention, and tenant protection during works, while using district-level capacity support to speed implementation.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Significant, because the package targets households exposed to high energy costs and energy poverty and addresses a major part of total monthly housing costs.

Intensity of change. Potentially high for beneficiaries, because better insulation and lower bills can materially improve affordability and living conditions, though gains are not real if rent pass-through or displacement cancels them out.

Equity effects. Strong if targeted well, because support can prioritise vulnerable households and worst-performing stock while anti-displacement rules prevent renovation-driven exclusion.

System spillovers. Relevant, because lower energy poverty can reduce health burdens, ease demand on social assistance, and stabilise tenancy where households would otherwise face affordability shocks.

Sustainability. High if renovation quality is durable and affordability protections remain in place, but weaker where safeguards are short-lived or displacement offsets the social gains.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to organise the package through a staged chain from targeted renovations and immediate bill relief, to scaled district programmes, to longer-term reductions in energy poverty and housing-cost stress with both energy and housing outcomes monitored.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Clear when framed around total monthly cost, because warmer homes and lower bills are easy to understand and make climate action feel protective rather than punitive.

Attribution clarity. Plausible, because the EU contribution is concrete through regulation, social transition funding, and capacity support, although it must be tied to visible local results.

Fairness robustness. Dependent on safeguards, because without visible anti-displacement rules the package can be attacked as renovation that prices people out rather than protects them.

Proof indicator. Strong proof should combine bill reductions, comfort improvements, affordability retention, and evidence of tenant stability through simple before-and-after indicators.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package fits a socially fair transition narrative well when cost relief and anti-displacement protection remain central to communication.

13. Work–Family Reconciliation: Reducing Structural Barriers to Work–Life Balance. EU Policy Packages

Why This Domain Matters

The struggle to reconcile work and family life is a theme that resonates across national contexts. It is often described as a structural impossibility: jobs demand more flexibility than they offer, while families depend on dual incomes to make ends meet. In line with the analytical framework developed in Part I, these tensions are not only experienced as practical constraints, but as part of a broader lived experience of imbalance and insecurity that contributes to perceptions of gendered positional deprivation, while also reinforcing a representation gap in which existing policy frameworks are seen as insufficiently attuned to the realities of everyday life.

What Citizens Told Us Across Europe

Balancing paid employment and family duties is discussed in both focus groups and participatory workshops in all countries. Across contexts (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary), the common denominator is a sense of structural imbalance between the demands of labour markets and family responsibilities. Yet national emphases vary. In Spain and Hungary, discussions focus strongly on the daily strain of combining paid work and care under conditions of limited support. In the United Kingdom, participants describe the promise of work–life balance as increasingly unattainable in practice. In Denmark and Germany, debates centre more on parental leave arrangements, including how leave should be shared between parents and how existing models shape women’s labour-market position. In Hungary, participants also stress the lack of resources to outsource care tasks, leaving families with fewer options when care demands intensify.

Gendered Experiences of Work-Family Reconciliation

Gender differences are particularly pronounced in this domain. Women describe work–family reconciliation as a chronic and structurally shaped tension involving persistent trade-offs between career continuity, job quality, and family responsibilities. These pressures are frequently linked to insufficient childcare provision, workplace norms, and enduring expectations regarding unpaid care. Men also recognise difficulties in combining work and family life, but more often frame them as logistical or temporary coordination problems rather than as sources of structural disadvantage. Career consequences are less central in men’s accounts, while family responsibilities are more often portrayed as flexible or negotiable. These contrasting narratives reflect not only different lived experiences, but also different interpretations of institutional performance, with women more likely to connect everyday constraints to broader patterns of inequality and inadequate policy support.

What the Survey Evidence Shows

Quantitative evidence confirms the pervasiveness of these concerns. The UNTWIST survey shows that reconciling paid employment and care responsibilities is a consistently important issue across the six countries examined, although with greater cross-national and gender variation than healthcare or housing. As shown in the Figure 16, it ranks among the top priorities in several contexts, reaching particularly strong positions in Switzerland, where it is within the top three across all party families. It also ranks highly in Germany and Spain, where it remains among the leading concerns for MR and ML voters and retains substantial relevance among RWPP electorates. In Hungary and Denmark, the issue is especially salient for specific voter groups, while in the United Kingdom it remains firmly within the upper tier of public concerns across the political spectrum.

Figure 16. Ranking of "balancing paid employment and family duties" as the most challenging aspect of life for people like them among RWPP, MR, and ML voters

Figure 17. Total percentage of voters (broken down by gender) who believe that "balancing paid employment and family duties" is the most challenging aspect of life for people like them

The overall pattern indicates that work–care reconciliation is a broad socio-economic issue, but one structured more unevenly by social position than the previous topics. Concern extends across ideological blocs, yet its intensity varies more clearly according to the everyday distribution of care responsibilities, labour-market exposure, and household constraints.

Gender differences are more pronounced than in previous topics and should be interpreted as substantively meaningful rather than marginal variations in degree (Figure 17). In most countries, women report substantially higher levels of concern than men, and these gaps are largest where the qualitative evidence points to stronger experiences of structural strain. The clearest example appears among RWPP voters in Spain, where women place far greater emphasis on the issue than men. This alignment between qualitative and quantitative evidence suggests that the politics of work–family balance are closely linked to gendered experiences of career penalties, insufficient childcare provision, unequal care burdens, and limited institutional support.

From Diagnosis to Policy Action

Taken together, these patterns position work–care reconciliation as a major cross-cutting priority, though one marked by sharper internal inequalities than healthcare or housing. The issue therefore reflects not only pressures of time and income, but also enduring conflicts over the social organisation of care, labour-market expectations, and gender equality.

The following sections presents priorities, policy packages, and recommendations in concise form. Extended analytical material for each domain is available in the supplementary material online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

13.1. Policy Priorities of Work–Family Balance

Purpose of This Section

This section identifies the policy priorities for work–family balance by moving from the concerns presented in the previous section to the bottlenecks that most consistently turn everyday reconciliation into a source of dissatisfaction. Its purpose is not to restate the evidence already discussed, but to carry out the intermediate analytical step described in Section 9.1: translating politically salient concerns into problem structures that can support policy development.

From the perspective developed in Part I, that analytical step is particularly important because work–family balance is not only a matter of private organisation, but also a domain in which institutional shortcomings are directly experienced through everyday pressures of time, care, and employment. Where care is unavailable, working time is inflexible, or career penalties accumulate unequally, citizens are more likely to interpret these constraints not as isolated individual difficulties but as signs that policy frameworks are insufficiently aligned with lived realities. In this sense, the section identifies the bottlenecks through which gendered positional deprivation is produced and sustained in the domain of work–family balance, and through which representation gaps become politically salient.

The section therefore retains only those problem clusters that are both empirically supported and plausibly open to EU-level influence.

Retained Policy Priorities

On that basis, three policy priorities are identified for work–family balance:

- Care availability and affordability as the binding constraint.
- Time sovereignty at work.
- Fair sharing and career protection.

Figure 18 shows a summary of the five policy packages developed within this domain of Housing for each of the policy priorities that are retained in the analysis.

Figure 18. Policy priorities and packages for Work-Family reconciliation (excerpt from Figure 9)

Policy Priority 1: Care Availability and Affordability as The Binding Constraint

Why This Is a Priority

Across the project material, difficulties in reconciling work and family life are most consistently associated with the practical problem of organising care on terms that

make employment sustainable. Read analytically, these concerns point not simply to individual stress, but to a binding constraint created by the uneven availability, affordability, and reliability of care, and one that falls disproportionately on women. In this sense, what appears in the qualitative and survey material as overload, disrupted routines, reduced working hours, or repeated improvisation can be interpreted as the visible expression of a recurrent bottleneck: paid work becomes difficult to maintain where childcare and long-term care cannot be accessed in ways that are stable, timely, and financially manageable.

From the perspective of the Handbook's analytical framework, this bottleneck is central because it links directly to lived experiences of constraint that are structurally patterned along gender lines. Where care systems fail to provide accessible and affordable solutions, women in particular experience a cumulative form of positional disadvantage, as employment, income, and career continuity become contingent on privately absorbing care responsibilities. In turn, these experiences contribute to perceptions that institutional arrangements are insufficiently aligned with everyday needs, reinforcing a representation gap in a domain that citizens experience as fundamental to economic stability and family life.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative evidence supports retaining this problem cluster as a priority. On the availability side, in 2024 only 50.7% of children aged 1 to 2 in the EU received formal childcare or education, compared with 89.3% of children aged 3 to the minimum compulsory school age — revealing the sharpest gap precisely in the early years when employment pressure on parents is highest.³⁷ For long-term care, OECD Health at a Glance 2025 estimates that around 13% of adults aged 50 and over across OECD countries provide informal care, with women accounting for a disproportionate share — a structural demand that formal systems only partially absorb.³⁸ On the affordability side, net childcare costs for a single-parent family or families on low incomes represent over 10% of household income in Spain, Switzerland or the United Kingdom, and an EU unweighted average of 7% across Member States with a statutory minimum wage — a direct financial disincentive to employment, particularly for second earners.³⁹ On the reliability and gender distribution side, EIGE's CARE Survey 2024 — conducted across all 27 EU Member States with over 65,000 respondents — shows that women are more than twice as likely as men to provide intensive unpaid childcare (over 35 hours per week), and that 45% of men enjoy eight or more hours of weekly leisure compared with only 32% of women.⁴⁰ These are not peripheral inequalities: they reflect structural gaps in how care systems are designed, financed, and distributed across

³⁷ Eurostat. (2025, September). *Living conditions in Europe - childcare arrangements*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Living_conditions_in_Europe_-_childcare_arrangements.

³⁸ OECD. (2025). *Health at a Glance 2025: OECD Indicators*. OECD Publishing. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/health-at-a-glance-2025_8f9e3f98-en.html.

³⁹ OECD Family Database. (2024). *PF3.4: Childcare support*. OECD Publishing. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/en/data/datasets/oecd-family-database.html>.

⁴⁰ EIGE. (2026). CARE Survey – Second wave: Online panel survey on gender gaps in unpaid care, individual and social activities – Analytical report, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

households. Taken together, these indicators support the view that reconciliation problems are not only matters of personal organisation, but reflect broader capacity gaps in the care infrastructure — gaps that are unevenly distributed along gender lines and require systemic policy responses.

Implications for EU-Level Action

For that reason, care availability and affordability are retained here as a policy priority. They represent a recurrent bottleneck that is empirically supported, clearly connected to lived dissatisfaction, and sufficiently relevant for EU-level option development around service access, affordability, and the conditions that make employment compatible with care responsibilities.

Policy Priority 2: Time Sovereignty at Work

Why This Is a Priority

A second recurring pattern in the material concerns not the absence of care as such, but the organisation of working time. Taken analytically, this suggests that a central obstacle to work–family balance lies in weak time sovereignty at work: people may formally remain in employment, yet still lack sufficient control over schedules, boundaries, and daily coordination. In this respect, recurring references to rigid hours, short-notice changes, extended availability, or flexibility that is difficult to use in practice can be read as the visible manifestations of a broader implementation problem: work arrangements are often insufficiently aligned with the temporal realities of care, family life, and everyday contingency.

Within the framework of Part I, this bottleneck is particularly relevant because it highlights the gap between formal entitlements and their practical usability in everyday life. Where flexibility exists in principle but cannot be exercised without penalty, or where boundaries between work and private life are weakly protected, individuals experience a form of constraint that is both material and institutional. These experiences contribute to perceptions of unfairness and imbalance, particularly among those with care responsibilities, and reinforce a representation gap insofar as policy frameworks are seen as failing to translate formal rights into workable conditions.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative and institutional evidence reinforces this interpretation. Comparative survey data directly confirm the scale of this problem. The European Working Conditions Survey 2024⁴¹, conducted across 35 countries with over 36,000 workers, shows that one in five European workers — approximately 20% — now regularly or occasionally works in telework or hybrid arrangements. While this offers flexibility benefits, the EWCS 2024 finds that regular teleworkers are significantly more likely to work during their free time to meet work demands, to be contacted outside working hours for work-related reasons, and to have private or family activities disrupted by

⁴¹ Eurofound. (2025). *European Working Conditions Survey 2024: First findings*. Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a97b37dd-beb8-11f0-a612-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>.

work requests. These boundary-blurring effects are more pronounced for women teleworkers in particular. Beyond telework, the survey shows that difficulties in switching off from work, worrying about work outside working hours, and feeling too tired after work to meet family obligations remain widespread across all employment forms — and have not meaningfully improved since previous editions despite legislative progress. The EWCS 2024 confirms that access to flexible scheduling has increased overall, but that the quality and usability of that flexibility — in terms of real predictability, schedule control, and protected rest — lags behind formal entitlements. These constraints are also present when, due to a lack of flexibility, workers opt for part-time jobs as a way to balance work and family life. In addition, there are significant gender disparities among those who choose part-time work to better balance work and family life: across the EU, 25% of women in part-time employment report doing so due to care responsibilities, compared to only 5.5% of men.⁴² These findings support the conclusion that the issue is not only access to flexibility in principle, but whether flexibility is usable, protected, and compatible with clear limits on working time.

Implications for EU-Level Action

Time sovereignty at work is therefore retained as a policy priority because it captures a recurrent source of dissatisfaction that is analytically distinct from care scarcity, directly relevant to the feasibility of everyday reconciliation, and open to policy development around predictability, schedule control, and protected boundaries between work and family time.

Policy Priority 3: Fair Sharing and Career Protection

Why This Is a Priority

A third recurring problem cluster concerns the unequal and cumulative penalties associated with caring responsibilities. Read analytically, the issue is not only that care requires time, but that its costs are distributed unevenly and often translated into longer-term disadvantages in employment, earnings, and career progression. In this sense, what appears in the material as frustration with leave-taking, reduced hours, interrupted careers, or the silent burden placed on one household member can be interpreted as the visible expression of a deeper structural imbalance: reconciliation systems often continue to rely on unequal assumptions about who absorbs care and who bears the associated penalties.

From the perspective of the Handbook's analytical framework, this bottleneck reflects one of the most direct mechanisms through which gendered positional deprivation is reproduced over time. Where care responsibilities translate into persistent employment and income penalties, particularly for women, the effects accumulate across the life course and shape long-term economic security. These patterns are not only experienced as unequal outcomes but also as indicators of insufficient institutional protection, reinforcing perceptions that existing policy arrangements do not adequately distribute the costs of care or support equal participation in the labour market.

⁴² Eurostat (2025). *Part-time employment due to care responsibilities (Ifsa_epgar)*. Luxembourg: European Commission. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative evidence supports retaining this problem cluster as a priority. EU-wide comparative data directly confirm the scale and structural nature of these penalties. According to EIGE's CARE Survey 2024⁴³ — the most comprehensive survey of its kind, covering all 27 EU Member States — women remain far more likely than men to adjust their employment to accommodate care: 28% of women in the EU work part-time, compared with only 8% of men, a gap directly attributable to care responsibilities; as this survey evidences, women take on 17% more household and caregiving responsibilities than men. Furthermore, this gender gap in part-time work was even more pronounced in 2024 in some countries, such as Germany (37.2%) and Switzerland (42.4%) (Eurostat, 2026b). In 2018, 33% of employed women in the EU reported taking a work break of at least six months for childcare, compared with just over 1% of men. The career and earnings consequences are cumulative: for couples with children under the age of seven, the gender pay gap reaches 48% — its highest point across any life stage. These inequalities compound over the life course, contributing to a gender pension gap estimated at 39% in the EU, meaning women reach retirement with significantly less accumulated entitlement than men. The gender employment gap in 2024 stood at 10 percentage points (70.8% for women vs 80.8% for men), with gaps reaching 19.4 points in Italy and 18.8 in Greece — countries where childcare coverage remains below EU averages.⁴⁴ Taken together, these findings support the interpretation that fairer sharing is not only a cultural aspiration, but a policy-relevant condition for preventing care from generating permanent and unequal penalties.

Implications for EU-Level Action

Fair sharing and career protection are therefore retained as a policy priority because they identify a recurrent structural source of dissatisfaction that is empirically grounded, closely linked to perceived unfairness, and relevant for EU-level option development around leave design, equal take-up, employment protection, and recognition of informal carers.

13.2. Policy Recommendations

Purpose of the Policy Packages

The five policy packages presented in this section respond to the three priorities identified in Section 13.1: expanding access to affordable and reliable care as the binding constraint on labour-market participation, strengthening time sovereignty at work, and reducing the unequal and cumulative career penalties associated with caring responsibilities. Each package is developed as an EU-plausible intervention, drawing on the Work–Life Balance Directive, the European Care Strategy, and ESF+ financing,

⁴³ EIGE. (2026). CARE Survey – Second wave: Online panel survey on gender gaps in unpaid care, individual and social activities – Analytical report, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

⁴⁴ Eurostat. (2026, March). *Women at work: A snapshot of the EU's gender employment gap*. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/en/web/products-eurostat-news/w/edn-20260303-1>.

and evaluated against the criteria of feasibility, impact, and communicative potential. A central design principle across the packages is that formal rights are necessary but not sufficient: the EU's role is not only to set minimum standards but to ensure that entitlements are genuinely usable in practice—accessible to those who most need them, protected from employer deterrence, and backed by the services and enforcement capacity that make them effective in everyday life.

How the Packages Are Assessed and Ranked

In line with the analytical framework developed in Part II, these policy packages are designed to address the mechanisms through which constraints in work–family balance are experienced and interpreted. By targeting care availability, working-time conditions, and the distribution of career penalties, they aim to reduce the everyday pressures that contribute to gendered positional deprivation, particularly among women, and to improve the perceived alignment between institutional arrangements and lived realities. In this sense, their relevance is not only technical but also political: their effectiveness depends on their capacity to produce visible and tangible improvements in how work and care can be combined, thereby strengthening perceptions of institutional responsiveness in a domain closely linked to stability, fairness, and life-course opportunities.

Table 3. List of policy packages on work-family balance, ordered by weighted scores

Proposal package	Feasibility (1–5)	Impact (1–5)	Communicative potential (1–5)	Weighted score
Expanding Childcare and After-School Care	4	5	4	4.4
Making Work-Life Balance Rights Work in Practice	5	4	4	4.3
Expanding Home and Community Care	3	5	4	4.1
Predictable Schedules and Stable Hours	4	4	4	4.0
Right to Disconnect and Healthy Work Boundaries	3	4	5	4.0

Why These Packages Matter

By improving access to care services, work–life balance arrangements, job quality, and care infrastructure, these measures aim to strengthen institutional responsiveness in a domain central to everyday life, thereby reducing the plausibility of blame-based and scapegoating narratives built on unresolved work–family reconciliation pressures.

POLICY PACKAGE 1: Expanding Childcare and After-School Care

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 5 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.4)

About: This policy package aims to expand childcare and after-school care capacity across Europe, with particular attention to children under three and to families whose working hours do not fit standard service schedules. Its purpose is not only to create more places, but to make care usable in real life by improving coverage, affordability, and compatibility with working time. The package builds on the Barcelona targets for 2030 and supports their practical implementation through shared goals, common delivery features, aligned funding, and comparable monitoring of progress. The EU's role is to provide coordination, targets, funding support, and accountability, while Member States and local authorities remain responsible for delivering places, staffing, and day-to-day service capacity. The strength of the package is that it addresses one of the clearest bottlenecks in work–family balance: when childcare is unavailable, unaffordable, or incompatible with working hours, employment becomes fragile or impossible.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – care availability and affordability as the binding constraint.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Strong but enabling, because the package matches an EU role in coordination, shared targets, and compatibility standards while leaving service delivery and capacity expansion to national and local systems.

Instrument readiness. Solid, because the Barcelona targets and the European Care Strategy already provide a policy anchor, monitoring channel, and link to EU funding and Semester follow-up.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because comparable reporting is manageable, but the heavier burden lies in local staffing, facilities, and operating budgets, which the EU can support but not substitute.

Time to visible result. Medium, because expanded places and published monitoring can show progress relatively quickly, while full capacity build-out remains slower due to workforce and infrastructure constraints.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to treat the package as EU-enabled and locally activated, combining common targets with a short set of delivery requirements on hours compatibility, affordability, and territorial coverage.

Impact (score: 5)

Population reach. Very broad, because childcare constraints affect large shares of working-age parents, especially families with young children and those with atypical schedules.

Intensity of change. High, because expanding usable childcare removes a binding logistical barrier and can directly improve labour-market participation and the daily feasibility of employment.

Equity effects. Potentially strong, because affordability and territorial coverage can reduce unequal access, although gains weaken if expansion mainly benefits households already better placed to secure care.

System spillovers. Significant, because greater care capacity can support women's employment, reduce household instability, and improve child wellbeing and educational readiness.

Sustainability. High if expansion is tied to stable operating funding and workforce retention, but weaker if provision grows without durable affordability and staffing capacity.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to prioritise the highest-multiplier constraints first: under-3 access, affordability for low- and middle-income households, and service coverage that matches real working schedules.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Strong, because the promise is concrete and easy to understand: a childcare place you can afford, at hours you can actually use.

Attribution clarity. Credible if disciplined, because the EU can plausibly claim to set targets, support delivery, and make progress measurable without claiming to provide childcare directly.

Fairness robustness. Generally robust, because the package is framed around enabling working families and expanding access rather than favouring a narrow subgroup.

Proof indicator. Clear proof can come from participation rates, affordability indicators, compatibility coverage, and visible reporting on local delivery and service expansion.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package fits a "making work possible" and "restoring everyday stability" narrative, though communication must manage expectations about delivery times.

POLICY PACKAGE 2: Making Work-Life Balance Rights Work in Practice

Proposed score: Feasibility 5 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.3)

About: This policy package aims to make the rights established under Directive (EU) 2019/1158 usable in practice. Its focus is not on creating new rights, but on improving how existing ones are implemented, understood, and enforced. This includes clearer procedures, stronger enforcement, and public indicators showing whether rights such as paternity leave, parental leave, carers' leave, and flexible working arrangements are genuinely accessible without hidden penalties. The package pays particular attention to fathers and carers, for whom formal rights often exist but remain harder to use in real working environments. The EU's role is to provide guidance, enforcement support, monitoring, and comparability, while Member States and employers remain responsible for day-to-day implementation. The strength of the package lies in closing a familiar gap between rights on paper and rights in real life.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 3 – fair sharing and career protection.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 5)

Competence fit. Very strong, because the EU is acting within an existing legal framework and improving the implementation of minimum rights already agreed at EU level.

Instrument readiness. High, because the Directive already provides a precise rulebook and enforceable rights, backed by transposition checks, implementation guidance, and infringement procedures where needed.

Administrative/data burden. Manageable, because the package mainly requires procedural standardisation, clearer complaint routes, and monitoring indicators, although it does increase some reporting and inspectorate demands.

Time to visible result. Relatively fast, because clearer procedures, better awareness, and stronger enforcement can improve approval rates and reduce retaliation complaints sooner than deeper behavioural change.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to frame the package as making existing rights usable, through standard request processes, response deadlines, simple complaint pathways, and inspectorate support rather than reopening the Directive itself.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Broad, because the Directive's rights apply to large numbers of working parents and carers, even if realised reach depends on awareness and practical usability.

Intensity of change. Meaningful but conditional, because better uptake, especially by fathers, can shift care patterns and reduce career penalties, though intensity depends on whether rights are affordable and safe to use.

Equity effects. Plausible and potentially strong, because usability improvements can reduce gendered penalties and protect workers in lower-paid or more precarious jobs where retaliation risks are higher.

System spillovers. Relevant, because better leave and flexible working arrangements can support child wellbeing, reduce household stress, and strengthen labour-market attachment.

Sustainability. High if enforcement and monitoring become institutionalised, preventing rights from remaining formally available but practically weak.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to focus on uptake multipliers such as fathers' use of leave, carers' access to carers' leave, and real access to flexibility without career penalties.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Strong, because the rights themselves are concrete and understandable, including paternity leave, parental leave, carers' leave, and the right to request flexibility.

Attribution clarity. Credible if disciplined, because the EU can say it set the minimum rights and is ensuring they work, while Member States and employers remain responsible for day-to-day delivery.

Fairness robustness. Generally robust, because the package is framed around enabling shared caregiving and protecting carers from penalties, though credibility depends on showing real usability for lower-income workers.

Proof indicator. Good proof can come from take-up rates, approval and response times for flexibility requests, complaint outcomes, and return-to-work or retention patterns after leave.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package fits a “rights that work in real life” narrative, but only if communication is backed by enforcement and measurable outcomes.

POLICY PACKAGE 3: Expanding Home and Community Care

Proposed score: Feasibility 3 / Impact 5 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.1)

About: This policy package aims to expand home and community-based long-term care and improve respite support for unpaid carers across Europe. Its purpose is to reduce the care burden that often pushes people, especially women, out of work or into reduced hours, while making support for older people and dependent adults more stable and accessible. The package builds on the Council Recommendation of 8 December 2022 on access to affordable, high-quality long-term care under the European Care Strategy. It would support this shift through shared standards, aligned reform and investment support, and measurable progress through indicators and monitoring. The EU’s role is to provide guidance, standards, support, and comparability, while Member States and local systems remain responsible for delivering services, staffing, and care capacity. The strength of the package lies in addressing one of the least visible but most consequential work–family balance pressures: when long-term care is unavailable, families absorb the strain, and employment becomes harder to sustain.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – care availability and affordability as the binding constraint.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 3)

Competence fit. Limited rather than strong, because long-term care organisation and funding remain primarily national and local, so the EU can enable but not guarantee service delivery.

Instrument readiness. Fairly good, because the Council Recommendation already provides a relatively concrete blueprint on availability, affordability, home and community care, quality, and indicators.

Administrative/data burden. High, because implementation depends on workforce availability, service capacity, local ecosystem variation, and the creation of credible quality and monitoring systems.

Time to visible result. Medium-to-slow overall, because service expansion takes time, although targeted improvements such as faster needs assessment, respite offers, and expanded home-care coverage can produce earlier relief.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to keep the package tightly aligned with the Recommendation, focusing on home and community services, respite capacity, workforce and quality measures, and a basic monitoring pack rather than forcing a single system model.

Impact (score: 5)

Population reach. Very broad, because long-term care gaps affect both people with care needs and the large number of relatives who provide unpaid care.

Intensity of change. High, because reducing intensive unpaid care burdens can prevent carers from leaving work or reducing hours and can materially improve daily wellbeing.

Equity effects. Strong, because care burdens fall disproportionately on women and lower-resource households, so better access to home care and respite can reduce both gendered and income-based inequalities.

System spillovers. Significant, because expanded home and community care can reduce crisis-driven service use, improve coordination with health services, and lower caregiver burnout.

Sustainability. High if service capacity and workforce stability are built durably, but much weaker if home-care and respite expansion depend on short-lived projects without stable funding.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to design the package around measurable pressure relief: faster needs assessment, broader home-care coverage, guaranteed respite availability, and better coordination between health and care systems.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Strong, because the promise is simple and resonant: people should not have to quit their job in order to care.

Attribution clarity. Credible if disciplined, because the EU can plausibly claim to enable countries to expand home-first options, close gaps, and make access measurable without claiming to run care systems directly.

Fairness robustness. Generally robust, because the package is framed as basic protection for carers and vulnerable people, although trust depends on whether services genuinely become available.

Proof indicator. Credible proof can come from waiting times for needs assessment, home-care coverage, respite availability, caregiver employment retention, and reductions in crisis episodes linked to lack of support.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package fits a “making care compatible with work” narrative, though credibility depends on showing measurable improvement in a previously hidden pressure.

POLICY PACKAGE 4: Predictable Schedules and Stable Hours

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.0)

About: This policy package aims to make predictable schedules and stable working hours a real condition of work, especially in sectors where late notice, cancelled shifts, last-minute changes, and “always available” expectations are common. It builds on existing EU law under Directive (EU) 2019/1152 on transparent and predictable working conditions, but focuses on making those protections work better in practice. The package would do this through clearer implementation rules, common templates, stronger enforcement expectations, and comparable indicators in the sectors where unpredictability is most concentrated. The EU’s role is to support enforcement, comparability, and implementation clarity, while Member States and employers remain responsible for scheduling practices and labour inspection. The strength of the package is that it addresses a very visible pressure in everyday life: when working time is unstable, family life becomes harder to organise and care responsibilities become harder to manage.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 2 – time sovereignty at work.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Strong, because the package reinforces an existing minimum-rights framework on predictability rather than creating a new layer of labour-market harmonisation.

Instrument readiness. Solid, because Directive (EU) 2019/1152 already provides a concrete legal anchor on reference hours and days, reasonable notice, refusal rights, and cancellation-related protections.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because making predictability inspectable requires documentation, reporting, and enforcement capacity, but these requirements are operationally feasible and support auditable compliance.

Time to visible result. Relatively fast, because improvements can show up early in measurable scheduling outcomes such as notice periods achieved, cancellations compensated, and written reference hours and days.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to treat the package as a compliance-and-capacity push, using standard templates, inspectable rights, and practical tools for labour inspectorates and social partners in high-volatility sectors.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. High in affected sectors, because unpredictability is concentrated in retail, hospitality, logistics, care, and other variable-hours settings, even if reach is narrower outside them.

Intensity of change. Meaningful, because greater predictability directly improves families’ planning capacity and reduces last-minute disruption, though impact remains bounded to workers facing unstable schedules.

Equity effects. Potentially strong, because schedule volatility is concentrated among lower-paid and more precarious workers, so stabilising hours can reduce both time shocks and income shocks.

System spillovers. Relevant, because more predictable working time can reduce work–family conflict, improve retention, and lessen reliance on emergency care arrangements.

Sustainability. High if compliance becomes routine and inspectable, but weaker if enforcement remains too thin and rights stay formal rather than practical.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to focus first on the sectors and contracts with the greatest unpredictability and to tie the package to measurable outcomes such as notice achieved, compensated cancellations, refusals without retaliation, and transitions to more predictable contracts.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Strong, because the claims are plain and verifiable: people deserve notice, can refuse outside agreed hours, and should be compensated for late cancellations.

Attribution clarity. Credible if framed as enforcing minimum rights that already exist across Europe rather than claiming to govern all workplace scheduling practices directly.

Fairness robustness. Robust, because the package protects a basic condition of livable work in volatile sectors, though employer concerns require communication that emphasises proportionality and clarity.

Proof indicator. Straightforward proof can come from notice periods, compensation rates for cancellations, written reference hours and days, complaint outcomes, and sector-by-sector comparisons.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package fits a “protecting time” and “making schedules livable” narrative, especially for workers exposed to volatile hours.

POLICY PACKAGE 5: Right to Disconnect and Healthy Work Boundaries

Proposed score: Feasibility 3 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 5 (weighted score: 4.0)

About: This policy package aims to protect workers’ time off and make healthy boundaries between work and private life enforceable in practice. It builds on the Working Time Directive 2003/88/EC, especially its rules on daily and weekly rest and limits on working time, and turns those protections into clearer workplace obligations. In practice, this means stronger enforcement of working-time rules, clearer expectations on when workers can be contacted, better recording of working time including in remote work, and sector-adapted agreements developed with social partners. The EU’s role is to support implementation, compliance, and comparable monitoring, while Member States and employers remain responsible for workplace practices and enforcement. The strength of the package is that it addresses a problem citizens recognise

immediately: when work never really stops, family life, care responsibilities, and wellbeing all come under pressure.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 2 – time sovereignty at work.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 3)

Competence fit. Moderate rather than strong, because the EU has a binding legal basis on rest time and maximum working time, but disconnect practices are still heavily shaped by workplace organisation and management culture.

Instrument readiness. Reasonably solid, because the Working Time Directive already provides enforceable minimum standards, even if operationalising disconnect will depend more on guidance, enforcement, and social dialogue than on a single new statute.

Administrative/data burden. Quite demanding, because after-hours work is often informal or weakly recorded, so effective enforcement requires stronger recording systems and added inspectorate capacity.

Time to visible result. Mixed but potentially fairly quick at workplace level, because rule changes and reductions in after-hours contact can appear early, while deeper cultural and workload change takes longer.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to build on what is legally solid, using standard elements such as no-contact windows, working-time recording, enforcement support, and sector-adapted agreements rather than relying on abstract principles alone.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Significant but uneven, because the package matters most for ICT-enabled, hybrid, and remote workers exposed to blurred boundaries, while it is less central in jobs where after-hours contact is rarer.

Intensity of change. Meaningful, because stronger boundaries can materially improve rest, family time, and wellbeing, although impact is limited if workload expectations remain unchanged.

Equity effects. Mixed but potentially important, because disconnect rules may primarily benefit higher-skilled remote workers unless recording and enforcement also protect lower-status workers facing implicit availability pressures.

System spillovers. Relevant, because better boundary protection can reduce stress and burnout, improve retention, and support caregiving time, with wider effects on health and productivity.

Sustainability. High if the package becomes embedded in enforceable routines and working-time compliance, but weak if disconnect remains a paper policy without real monitoring.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to require implementation designs that actually change routines, including no-contact windows, meeting-free boundaries, workload audits, after-hours monitoring, and enforceable rest-time compliance.

Communication (score: 5)

Citizen-legibility. Extremely strong, because the core message is instantly understood: when you are off, you should be off.

Attribution clarity. Credible if anchored in existing EU law, because the EU can plausibly claim to protect rest time and ensure that this protection still works under remote and digitally connected work.

Fairness robustness. Robust, because the package protects a basic right to rest, though sector-specific concerns require communication that stresses flexible implementation through social dialogue.

Proof indicator. Clear proof can come from after-hours message traffic, self-reported inability to disconnect, recorded extra working time, rest-time compliance, and complaint or enforcement outcomes.

Narrative fit. Very strong, because the package fits a “healthy boundaries” and “protecting family time” narrative naturally, provided communication stays proof-led and avoids overclaiming cultural control.

14. Care Systems: Strengthening Provision and Support for Dependents. EU Policy Packages.

Why This Domain Matters

The organisation of care responsibilities is a theme that resonates across national contexts. It is often experienced as a structural imbalance: the demand for care is increasing due to demographic change and rising service costs, while institutional provision remains limited or uneven. In line with the analytical framework developed in Part I, these pressures are not only experienced as practical constraints, but as part of a broader lived experience of time scarcity, dependency management, and insecurity that contributes to perceptions of gendered positional deprivation, while also reinforcing a representation gap in which existing policy frameworks are seen as insufficiently responsive to everyday care realities.

What Citizens Told Us Across Europe

Caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents is discussed in both focus groups and participatory workshops in all countries in UNTWIST (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary). Cross-national variation highlights different facets of this shared challenge. In Denmark, participants emphasise the perceived decline in state-provided elder care and difficulties in maintaining intergenerational relationships. In Germany, both focus groups and participatory workshops call for a more equitable distribution of childcare responsibilities, including expanded paternity leave and improved access to daycare. Hungary provides a stark example of shifting responsibility, with recent legal changes assigning greater care duties to families and disproportionately increasing the burden on women. In Spain, care continues to be widely perceived as a predominantly female responsibility, alongside growing concern about the adequacy of elder care provision. In the UK, discussions alternate between support for shared parental responsibility and persistent beliefs that women are better suited to caregiving, with childcare costs emerging as a central constraint.

Gendered Experiences of Care

Caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents constitutes a central axis of gendered grievance. Women describe the intensity, emotional labour, and moral weight of caregiving, as well as the limited institutional support available to sustain it, with direct implications for employment trajectories, financial security, and personal well-being. Care is framed as non-optional and identity-shaping. Men, in contrast, tend to describe care as a secondary or supportive role, often emphasising episodic involvement rather than continuous responsibility. The emotional and temporal demands of care are less elaborated, and shortcomings in public provision are less frequently articulated as structural or political problems. These differences in framing reflect not only distinct experiences, but also different interpretations of institutional performance, with women more likely to connect everyday care constraints to broader patterns of inequality and insufficient policy support.

What the Survey Evidence Shows

Figure 19. Ranking of "caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents" as the most challenging aspect of life for people like them among RWPP, MR, and ML voters

Quantitatively, in the UNTWIST survey caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents emerges as a consistently relevant issue across the six countries examined, although with marked cross-national and political variation. As shown in Figure 19, the topic reaches its highest prominence in Germany, where it ranks as the top priority among MR voters and remains highly placed among ML electorates. It is also strongly prioritised in the United Kingdom, where it appears among the leading concerns across party families. In Hungary and Switzerland, the issue remains salient but more unevenly distributed across voter groups, while in Spain it occupies a mid-level position across the political spectrum. Denmark shows comparatively lower ranking positions, though care still remains part of the broader field of recognised social concerns.

The overall pattern indicates that care responsibilities constitute a cross-cutting socio-economic issue, although with greater variation across countries and voter groups than the previous topics. Concern is visible across ideological blocs, yet its intensity differs across cases and reflects the diverse ways in which care responsibilities and available support are experienced in everyday life.

Figure 20. Total percentage of voters (broken down by gender) who believe that “caring for children, elderly relatives, and other dependents” is the most challenging aspect of life for people like them

Gender differences are pronounced and substantively significant in this domain (Figure 20). In most countries, women report higher levels of concern than men, and these gaps are consistent with the qualitative evidence on unequal care burdens and differing everyday experiences of dependency management. The clearest divide appears among RWPP voters in Switzerland, where women place substantially greater emphasis on the issue than men. This alignment between qualitative and quantitative findings suggests that the politics of care are closely linked to women’s greater exposure to continuous caregiving responsibilities, employment interruptions, emotional labour, and insufficient institutional support.

From Diagnosis to Policy Action

Taken together, these patterns position care as an important shared priority, but one characterised by sharper internal inequalities and stronger contextual variation than healthcare, housing, or even work–family balance. The issue therefore reflects not only practical pressures of time, cost, and dependency, but also enduring conflicts over who provides care, who bears its consequences, and how societies value caregiving itself.

The following sections presents priorities, policy packages, and recommendations in concise form. Extended analytical material for each domain is available in the supplementary material online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

14.1. Policy Priorities of Caring

Purpose of This Section

This section identifies the policy priorities for caring by moving from the concerns presented in the previous section to the bottlenecks that most consistently structure dissatisfaction in this field. Its purpose is not to restate the evidence already discussed, but to carry out the intermediate analytical step described in Section 9.1: translating politically salient concerns into analytically defined problem clusters that can support policy development.

From the perspective developed in Part I, this step is essential to understanding how care-related pressures are not only experienced as practical constraints but also as structurally patterned forms of disadvantage. The organisation of care—its availability, affordability, and distribution—shapes everyday life in ways that can generate gendered positional deprivation, particularly for women, and contribute to a representation gap where institutional arrangements are perceived as insufficiently responsive to the realities of dependency and caregiving.

In this field, that analytical step requires distinguishing between three interrelated but analytically distinct pressures: whether childcare provision is sufficiently affordable and reliable to meet everyday needs; whether long-term care is accessible, affordable, and supported by stable service capacity; and whether informal care continues to absorb pressures that public systems do not adequately address. The section therefore retains only those problem clusters that are both empirically supported and plausibly open to EU-level influence.

Retained Policy Priorities

On that basis, three policy priorities are identified for caring:

- Affordable, reliable childcare and after-school coverage.
- Long-term care that is accessible without impoverishing families, with quality and workforce stability.
- Real support for informal carers and fair distribution of care between women and men.

Figure 21 shows a summary of the five policy packages developed within this domain of Housing for each of the policy priorities that are retained in the analysis.

Figure 21. Policy priorities and packages for Care (excerpt from Figure 9)

Policy Priority 1: Affordable, Reliable Childcare and After-School Coverage
Recommendation

- Childcare Hours That Fit Work

Policy Priority 2: Long-Term Care That Is Accessible Without Impoverishing Families, With Quality and Workforce Stability
Recommendation

- Keeping Care Affordable for Families
- Reliable Home Care Provision (Staffing Capacity, Continuity, and Basic Quality Standards)

Policy Priority 3: Real Support for Informal Carers and Fair Distribution of Care Between Women and Men
Recommendation

- Making Carers' Leave and Flexibility Work in Practice
- Respite and Emergency Back-Up Care

Policy priority 1: Affordable, Reliable Childcare and After-School Coverage

Why This Is a Priority

Across the project material, childcare emerges as one of the clearest points at which care pressure becomes operational in everyday life. Read analytically, these concerns point not simply to parental stress, but to a recurrent bottleneck in the availability, affordability, and practical usability of childcare provision. In this sense, what appears in the material as disrupted routines, constant improvisation, difficulty matching care to working hours, or the fragility of arrangements when something changes can be interpreted as the visible expression of a broader service constraint: childcare often exists unevenly, at the wrong times, or at a cost that weakens its protective function.

From the perspective developed in Part I, these constraints reflect how limited and poorly aligned childcare provision shapes lived experiences of pressure and instability, contributing to gendered positional deprivation where caregiving responsibilities fall unevenly on women. Where these constraints persist, they can also reinforce a representation gap, as institutional arrangements are perceived as insufficiently responsive to the practical conditions under which families organise care and employment.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative evidence supports retaining this problem cluster as a priority. On availability, in 2024 only 50.7% of children aged 1 to 2 in the EU received formal childcare or education, compared with 89.3% of children aged 3 to the minimum compulsory school age — with particularly low coverage in Hungary (below 20% for under-3s) and significant variation across the project countries.⁴⁵ This gap reveals a structural weakness at precisely the life stage where parental employment pressure is highest. On affordability, net childcare costs for a two-earner couple with average wages consuming full-time childcare reach 19% of household net income in Germany and 14% in Denmark; for a single parent on low income, costs represent over 20% of take-home pay in several Member States.⁴⁶ On usability and reliability, the OECD Family Database shows that the hours of subsidised childcare available do not always match standard working hours, leaving families to cover gaps privately or through informal arrangements that are inherently fragile. These elements support the view that childcare shortages are not a peripheral inconvenience, but a structural weakness in the care system's ability to provide reliable support.

Implications for EU-Level Action

For that reason, affordable and reliable childcare and after-school coverage are retained here as a policy priority. They represent a recurrent bottleneck that is empirically supported, clearly linked to lived dissatisfaction, and relevant for EU-level option development around access, affordability, and usable service design.

Policy priority 2: Long-Term Care That Is Accessible Without Impoverishing Families, With Quality and Workforce Stability

Why This Is a Priority

A second recurring pattern in the material concerns long-term care. Taken analytically, the issue is not only that care needs are rising, but that long-term care systems often remain too difficult to access, too costly, or too unstable to provide dependable protection when dependency emerges. In this respect, recurring references to exhaustion, household strain, uncertainty, or the need for families to absorb complex care responsibilities can be read as the visible manifestations of a broader structural weakness: a bottleneck in long-term care provision, where demand is increasing while service availability, affordability, and workforce capacity remain insufficient or uneven.

Drawing on the analytical framework set out in Part I, these pressures reflect how limited and unevenly developed long-term care provision shapes lived experiences of strain and insecurity, contributing to gendered positional deprivation where caregiving responsibilities are absorbed within households and fall disproportionately on women.

⁴⁵ Eurostat. (2025, September). *Living conditions in Europe - childcare arrangements*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Living_conditions_in_Europe_-_childcare_arrangements.

⁴⁶ OECD Family Database. (2024). *PF3.4: Childcare support*. OECD Publishing. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/en/data/datasets/oecd-family-database.html>.

Where these pressures persist, they can also reinforce a representation gap, as institutional arrangements are perceived as insufficiently responsive to care-related risks and the practical conditions under which families organise support.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative and institutional evidence reinforces this interpretation. On 1 January 2025, people aged 65 and over represented 22% of the EU population a share set to reach 30% by 2050 as the baby-boom cohort ages.⁴⁷ Yet formal long-term care coverage remains insufficient: OECD Health at a Glance 2025⁴⁸ reports that only around 10–12% of adults aged 65 and over across OECD countries receive formal long-term care services at home, despite significantly higher rates of functional limitations in this population. On affordability, out-of-pocket long-term care costs can reach catastrophic levels — the OECD estimates that in several Member States, residential care costs exceed the full net income of the average older person, pushing families to either deplete household assets or withdraw formal care entirely. On workforce, the long-term care sector faces shortages of up to 1.4 million workers across the EU by 2030, with high turnover, low pay, and poor working conditions threatening service continuity and quality.⁴⁹ Evidence on unmet need reinforces these constraints: on average, 47% of older adults with care limitations across OECD countries do not receive adequate long-term care, with even higher levels in countries such as Denmark (54%), Switzerland (55%) and Hungary (52%). Taken together, these indicators confirm that long-term care is not a future risk but a present system failure with direct and unequal consequences for families.

Implications for EU-Level Action

Long-term care is therefore retained as a policy priority because it captures a recurrent structural constraint that is empirically grounded, institutionally visible, and highly relevant for policy development around service access, affordability, quality assurance, and workforce stability.

Policy priority 3: Real Support for Informal Carers and Fair Distribution of Care Between Women and Men

Why This Is a Priority

A third recurring problem cluster concerns the role of informal care and the unequal way in which its burdens are distributed. Read analytically, the issue is not only that families continue to provide substantial care, but that systems frequently rely on

⁴⁷ Eurostat. (2026, February). *Population structure and ageing*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Population_structure_and_ageing

⁴⁸ OECD. (2025). *Health at a Glance 2025: OECD Indicators*. OECD Publishing. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/health-at-a-glance-2025_8f9e3f98-en.html.

⁴⁹ European Commission. (2022). *A European Care Strategy for caregivers and care receivers (COM(2022) 440 final)*. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52022DC0440>.

informal carers without making their role sufficiently visible, supported, or fairly shared. In this sense, what appears in the material as reduced hours, leave-taking, accumulated stress, interrupted careers, or the concentration of caring responsibility in one household member can be interpreted as the visible expression of a deeper institutional pattern: a bottleneck in the recognition, support, and redistribution of informal care, through which care systems continue to externalise pressure onto households, and where that pressure remains strongly gendered.

From the perspective developed in Part I, this dynamic is central to the production of gendered positional deprivation, as care responsibilities disproportionately affect women's employment trajectories, income stability, and long-term security. Where institutional support remains limited or uneven, these patterns can also contribute to a representation gap, reinforcing the perception that care systems rely on households without adequately recognising or supporting their role.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative evidence supports retaining this problem cluster as a priority. OECD Health at a Glance 2025⁵⁰ estimates that around 13% of adults aged 50 and over across OECD countries provide informal care on a regular basis, with women accounting for a disproportionate share — particularly in the 50–64 age bracket, where care obligations intensify at a critical point in career trajectories. EIGE's CARE Survey 2024⁵¹ — conducted across all 27 EU Member States with over 65,000 respondents — provides EU-wide data on the direct consequences: women are more than twice as likely as men to provide intensive informal care, and 40% of women providing care report that it negatively affects their paid work, compared with 25% of men. In terms of time, women across the EU spend on average 9 hours more per week than men on unpaid care and domestic work — a gap that persists across all age groups and is particularly marked in Hungary and Spain. These are not marginal effects: they systematically shape employment rates, earnings trajectories, and pension entitlements over the life course. The Work–Life Balance Directive (EU) 2019/1158 sets minimum requirements for carers' leave and flexible arrangements, but formal entitlements alone have not closed these gaps. Taken together, these elements support the interpretation that informal care remains both a major source of hidden system dependence and a persistent mechanism of structural gender inequality.

Implications for EU-Level Action

Real support for informal carers and fair distribution of care between women and men are therefore retained as a policy priority because they identify a recurrent source of dissatisfaction that is empirically grounded, closely linked to perceived unfairness, and relevant for EU-level option development around carers' rights, visible support, and more equal care sharing.

⁵⁰ OECD. (2025). *Health at a Glance 2025: OECD Indicators*. OECD Publishing. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/health-at-a-glance-2025_8f9e3f98-en.html.

⁵¹ EIGE. (2026). CARE Survey – Second wave: Online panel survey on gender gaps in unpaid care, individual and social activities – Analytical report, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

14.2. Policy Recommendations

Purpose of the Policy Packages

The five policy packages presented in this section respond to the three priorities identified in Section 14.1: improving the availability and affordability of childcare and after-school provision, making long-term care accessible without impoverishing families, and providing real support for informal carers while reducing the gendered concentration of care burdens. Each package is developed as an EU-plausible intervention, grounded in the European Care Strategy, the Council Recommendation on long-term care, and ESF+ and EAFRD financing instruments, and evaluated against the criteria of feasibility, impact, and communicative potential. The packages span the full care continuum—from early childhood services through home and residential long-term care to the rights and recognition of the millions of informal carers on whom European care systems silently depend—and are ordered from highest to lowest weighted score.

How the Packages Are Assessed and Ranked

In line with the analytical framework developed in Part II, these policy packages are designed to address the mechanisms through which care-related constraints are experienced and interpreted in everyday life. By targeting service availability, affordability, and the distribution of care responsibilities, they aim to reduce the pressures that contribute to gendered positional deprivation, particularly for women, and to improve the alignment between institutional arrangements and lived realities. In this sense, their relevance is not only technical but also political: their effectiveness depends on their capacity to produce visible and tangible improvements in how care is organised and supported, thereby strengthening perceptions of institutional responsiveness in a domain closely linked to security, dignity, and life-course stability.

Table 4. List of policy packages on care, ordered by weighted scores

Proposal package	Feasibility (1–5)	Impact (1–5)	Communicative potential (1–5)	Weighted score
Making Carers' Leave and Flexibility Work in Practice	5	4	4	4.3
Respite and Emergency Back-Up Care	3	5	4	4.1
Childcare Hours That Fit Work	4	4	4	4.0
Keeping Care Affordable for Families	3	4	5	4.0
Reliable Home Care Provision	4	4	3	3.7

Why These Packages Matter

By improving the availability and affordability of childcare and after-school provision, ensuring access to long-term care without impoverishing families, and strengthening support for informal carers while reducing the gendered concentration of care responsibilities, these measures aim to enhance institutional responsiveness in a domain central to everyday life, thereby reducing the plausibility of blame-based and scapegoating narratives built on unresolved care pressures and unmet dependency needs.

POLICY PACKAGE 1: Making Carers' Leave and Flexibility Work in Practice

Proposed score: Feasibility 5 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.3)

About: This policy package aims to make existing EU rights for informal carers genuinely usable in everyday working life. Building on Directive (EU) 2019/1158 on work-life balance for parents and carers, it focuses on ensuring that carers' leave and the right to request flexible working arrangements are easy to request, answered within a clear timeframe, and protected against retaliation, dismissal, or career penalties. The package does not create new care services; instead, it strengthens the time-rights layer that allows carers to stay in work while managing unavoidable care responsibilities. The EU's role is to improve implementation, enforcement, and comparability across Member States through common procedures, clearer expectations for employers, and a small set of public indicators showing whether carers' rights are real in practice rather than only formal on paper. The strength of the package lies in addressing a very visible gap in the current system: carers often have rights, but not rights they can safely and realistically use.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 3 – real support for informal carers and fair distribution of care between women and men.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 5)

Competence fit. Very strong, because the package sits directly on binding EU labour law that already covers carers' leave, flexible working requests, and protection against adverse treatment and dismissal.

Instrument readiness. High, because the legal instrument is already precise and operational, and the EU can act through familiar tools such as guidance, shared administrative templates, transposition checks, and enforcement support.

Administrative/data burden. Limited and proportionate, because standardising request procedures, response timelines, and basic reporting adds modest requirements compared with the gain in clarity and enforceability.

Time to visible result. Relatively fast, because clearer procedures, quicker responses, lower dispute rates, and higher take-up of carers' leave and flexible arrangements can become visible early.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to keep the package tightly procedural and enforcement-focused, so carers do not need prolonged legal action to access short but essential periods of care time.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Significant, because the package targets a large and growing group of working informal carers, even if it does not affect the entire workforce directly.

Intensity of change. Meaningful but bounded, because making existing rights genuinely usable can reduce forced hour reductions and labour-market exit, though it does not solve underlying service shortages.

Equity effects. Potentially strong, because unpaid care burdens fall disproportionately on women and better access to time rights can reduce gendered career penalties if take-up becomes normalised.

System spillovers. Relevant, because more usable rights can improve employment retention, reduce stress and burnout among carers, and make the coordination of work and care more stable.

Sustainability. High if monitoring and enforcement become routine, but weaker if rights remain formally available while employers can still deter or penalise their use in practice.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to connect rights to real usability through fast written responses, justified refusals, visible anti-retaliation protections, and practical support for both workers and employers.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Strong, because the benefit is immediate and easy to understand: time to care without losing your job.

Attribution clarity. Credible, because the EU can truthfully claim both to have set minimum rights and to be making sure those rights function in real working life.

Fairness robustness. Generally robust, because the package protects people already carrying unavoidable responsibilities rather than redistributing benefits in a visibly zero-sum way.

Proof indicator. Clear proof can come from take-up rates, response times, complaint outcomes, and enforcement actions showing whether the rights are genuinely usable.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package fits a broader narrative of protecting carers and making the sharing of care responsibilities more realistic and fair.

POLICY PACKAGE 2: Respite and Emergency Back-Up Care

Proposed score: Feasibility 3 / Impact 5 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.1)

About: This policy package aims to expand respite care and emergency back-up care for informal carers when regular care arrangements fail. Its purpose is to reduce the crisis moments that push carers into burnout, repeated work disruption, or labour-

market exit by supporting local models that guarantee continuity of care under unforeseen circumstances. The package builds on the Council Recommendation on access to affordable, high-quality long-term care (2022/C 476/01) and the European Care Strategy. The EU's role is to provide co-financing, minimum operational standards, and support for learning and comparability across Member States, while local and national systems remain responsible for delivering services. The strength of the package lies in addressing one of the most fragile points in the care system: when ordinary arrangements collapse, families should not be left alone to absorb the shock.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 3 – real support for informal carers and fair distribution of care between women and men.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 3)

Competence fit. Moderate rather than strong, because service delivery remains national and local, so the EU can only operate credibly through standards, co-financing, and replication support.

Instrument readiness. Reasonably solid, because the long-term care Recommendation already recognises the limits of heavy reliance on informal care and creates a legitimate entry point for continuity planning and support.

Administrative/data burden. Quite demanding, because pilots require coordination, safeguarding, workforce planning, and monitoring, although standardised EU templates can reduce fragmentation and learning costs.

Time to visible result. Mixed but potentially fairly quick in pilot areas, because continuity improvements such as fewer missed visits and faster replacement can appear earlier than full system-wide scale-up.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to design the package as a network of local pilots with common EU rules on response times, respite availability, safeguarding, and evaluation, while keeping service organisation local.

Impact (score: 5)

Population reach. Narrower in direct coverage than broad care reforms, but highly important because the target group faces some of the highest risks of burnout, collapse, and labour-market withdrawal.

Intensity of change. Very high for beneficiaries, because respite and continuity directly prevent crisis-driven work disruption and reduce the point at which care becomes unsustainable.

Equity effects. Strong, because unpaid crisis care falls disproportionately on women and on families with fewer resources to buy private alternatives or absorb lost earnings.

System spillovers. Significant, because stronger continuity can reduce emergency service use, improve outcomes for carers and care recipients, and stabilise employment participation.

Sustainability. Conditional, because pilots only become durable if they are integrated into stable funding, workforce planning, and local service pathways rather than remaining stand-alone experiments.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to structure the package around a clear results chain from continuity capacity, to lower caregiver burden, to stronger employment retention and wellbeing outcomes.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Strong, because the promise is concrete and emotionally intelligible: you will not be left alone when care suddenly breaks down.

Attribution clarity. Credible if disciplined, because the EU can claim to enable and scale continuity models without implying that it is directly providing care services itself.

Fairness robustness. Robust, because the frame is protective rather than redistributive and speaks to security in moments of breakdown rather than to advantage for a narrow group.

Proof indicator. Credible proof can come from missed-visit rates, response times, caregiver burden measures, and employment-retention outcomes in pilot areas.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package fits a wider narrative of resilience in care systems and protection for families under pressure.

POLICY PACKAGE 3: Childcare Hours That Fit Work

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.0)

About: This policy package aims to make childcare more compatible with real working hours. It focuses on the practical gaps many families face when standard opening times do not match the times people actually work. This includes support for early and late opening, after-school provision, and holiday coverage in the areas where the mismatch is greatest. The package does not replace broader childcare expansion, but complements it by addressing a specific bottleneck: having a childcare place is not enough if the hours do not fit daily life. Its EU anchor is the Council Recommendation on early childhood education and care (2022/C 484/01), which links childcare access directly to labour-market participation. The EU's role is to support targeted capacity adjustments, comparable monitoring, and implementation learning, while Member States and local authorities remain responsible for delivery. The strength of the package lies in turning formal childcare provision into usable support for working families.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – affordable, reliable childcare and after-school coverage.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Strong but enabling, because the EU can act through coordination, targets, and replication support without harmonising national childcare systems or service models.

Instrument readiness. Solid, because the Recommendation and the Barcelona targets already provide a recognised policy framework and a monitoring channel that can host a more practical delivery push.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because extending hours is locally workforce-intensive and operationally complex, though still manageable with targeted support and limited reporting requirements.

Time to visible result. Relatively fast in targeted areas, because local extensions of opening hours and holiday coverage can show quick effects even if broader roll-out depends on staffing availability.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to focus on the highest-need areas first, co-finance workable models, and require a basic set of quality, safeguarding, and compatibility standards.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Significant, because the package matters especially for working parents facing schedule mismatches, including shift workers, single parents, and households with weak informal support.

Intensity of change. Meaningful, because usable hours can materially improve the feasibility of employment and daily coordination, although effects remain dependent on affordability and local take-up.

Equity effects. Potentially strong, because extended-hours provision can help households that are least able to absorb schedule mismatches, provided access does not depend on premium pricing.

System spillovers. Relevant, because more usable childcare hours can raise labour supply, reduce last-minute reliance on informal care, and lower household instability caused by schedule conflicts.

Sustainability. Conditional, because lasting gains depend on stable operating funding and workforce retention rather than short-term pilot logic alone.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to prioritise extended opening, after-school pathways, holiday coverage, and affordability protections so that the extra capacity is genuinely usable by lower- and middle-income families.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. Strong, because “childcare that matches working life” is intuitive, concrete, and easy to verify against daily experience.

Attribution clarity. Credible, because the EU can plausibly claim to enable and support usable childcare models without pretending to run childcare services directly.

Fairness robustness. Generally robust, because the framing removes a practical constraint on family life rather than prescribing how people should organise work and care.

Proof indicator. Clear proof can come from opening-hour coverage, take-up rates, waiting times for extended-hour places, and employment outcomes linked to improved compatibility.

Narrative fit. Strong, because the package fits a practical narrative of making work feasible for families rather than merely expanding provision in formal terms.

POLICY PACKAGE 4: Keeping Care Affordable for Families

Proposed score: Feasibility 3 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 5 (weighted score: 4.0)

About: This policy package aims to make care costs more visible, more comparable, and easier to act on when they become too heavy for families. Its purpose is to identify situations in which the cost of childcare or long-term care pushes households into financial strain, greater reliance on unpaid care, or withdrawal from the labour market. The package would do this by creating a common EU framework for measuring care affordability, defining warning signs of excessive cost pressure, and linking those signals to follow-up through EU coordination and funding channels. It builds on the European Care Strategy and the Council Recommendation on access to affordable, high-quality long-term care. The EU's role is not to set prices directly, but to improve measurement, accountability, and follow-up, so that care affordability becomes a visible policy issue rather than a hidden household burden. The strength of the package lies in addressing a problem citizens recognise immediately: when care becomes too expensive, families experience it as a direct threat to work, income, and stability.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 2 – long-term care that is accessible without impoverishing families, with quality and workforce stability.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 3)

Competence fit. Limited but credible, because the EU cannot set fees or redesign care financing directly, yet it can build a common framework for measurement, comparability, and accountability.

Instrument readiness. Reasonably strong, because existing EU coordination channels, statistical systems, and care-strategy commitments provide an institutional home for a focused affordability framework.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because comparability is difficult across highly different care systems, though a small and disciplined indicator set can keep the exercise workable.

Time to visible result. Fast in monitoring terms, because measurement, affordability flags, and reporting can be introduced relatively quickly, even if actual price relief depends on national follow-up action.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to keep the indicator set tight, thresholds transparent, and follow-up obligations clear so that the framework remains actionable rather than merely descriptive.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Broad, because affordability pressures affect large numbers of households with childcare or long-term care needs, including many that do not appear in narrow poverty indicators.

Intensity of change. Meaningful but indirect, because measurement alone is not transformative, yet linked action can significantly reduce financial stress and labour-market withdrawal caused by care costs.

Equity effects. Potentially strong, because lower- and middle-income households are most exposed to care-related cost pressure and can benefit most from better visibility and targeted response.

System spillovers. Relevant, because reducing affordability pressure can lessen reliance on unpaid care, improve labour-market participation, and reduce the hidden transfer of care costs onto families.

Sustainability. Strong if embedded into recurring coordination and monitoring cycles, but weaker if affordability is measured without clear response pathways or political follow-through.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to connect affordability stress flags to a staged chain of short-, medium-, and long-term responses so that visibility leads to correction rather than passive reporting.

Communication (score: 5)

Citizen-legibility. Extremely strong, because “I cannot afford care” is immediate, concrete, and easily understood across social and political groups.

Attribution clarity. Credible, because the EU can plausibly claim to make care costs visible, comparable, and impossible to ignore without pretending to set prices directly.

Fairness robustness. Very robust, because the package is framed around protecting families from care-related impoverishment rather than distributing visible advantages to one group at another’s expense.

Proof indicator. Strong proof can come from published cost indicators, affordability stress flags, and visible records of the follow-up actions triggered by those signals.

Narrative fit. Excellent, because the package fits a narrative of protecting families from care-driven financial strain and making hidden burdens politically visible.

POLICY PACKAGE 5: Reliable Home Care Provision (Staffing Capacity, Continuity, and Basic Quality Standards)

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 3 (weighted score: 3.7)

About: This policy package aims to improve the reliability, continuity, and basic quality of home and community-based long-term care. Its purpose is to ensure that families can depend on services that arrive on time, remain stable over time, and are delivered with adequate quality standards. The package focuses especially on workforce stability, because weak staffing, turnover, and fragmented provision are major reasons why home care becomes unreliable in practice. It builds directly on the Council Recommendation on access to affordable, high-quality long-term care and the European Care Strategy. The EU’s role is to support common standards, workforce strengthening, and monitored delivery, while Member States and local systems remain responsible for organising and providing services. The strength of the package lies in addressing a basic but politically important problem: when home care is inconsistent, families absorb the instability; when it is reliable, care becomes more manageable and everyday life more secure.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 2 – long-term care that is accessible without impoverishing families, with quality and workforce stability.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. Strong in enabling terms, because the EU can credibly act through standards, workforce support, capacity-building, and funding alignment without taking over service organisation.

Instrument readiness. Good, because there is a clear policy mandate through the Care Strategy and long-term care Recommendation, and the package can be integrated into existing EU coordination routines.

Administrative/data burden. Moderate, because monitoring reliability and continuity indicators adds reporting requirements, but these are directly linked to accountability and service improvement.

Time to visible result. Incremental rather than immediate, because continuity improvements can appear progressively while deeper workforce effects take longer to build.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. Important to focus on a small operational set of reliability indicators so that the package remains practical and does not collapse under excessive measurement demands.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. Significant, because the package matters directly to households relying on home care and indirectly to the relatives whose work and daily stability depend on it being dependable.

Intensity of change. Meaningful, because more reliable care can materially reduce informal care pressure and make everyday coordination more manageable, even if it does not solve all capacity shortages.

Equity effects. Strong, because unstable home care shifts burdens most heavily onto women and lower-income households with less capacity to replace missing provision privately.

System spillovers. Relevant, because stronger continuity can improve health outcomes, reduce emergency use, and support employment retention among family carers.

Sustainability. Conditional, because long-term success depends heavily on workforce recruitment, retention, and organisational stability rather than on one-off quality pushes.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Essential to target high-need areas first and tie funding and support to measurable gains in continuity, reliability, workforce stability, and basic quality.

Communication (score: 3)

Citizen-legibility. Moderate, because reliability matters deeply to families but is less immediately headline-friendly than affordability or leave rights.

Attribution clarity. Credible but less automatic, because the EU role has to be explained as enabling reliability and monitored improvement rather than directly managing home-care services.

Fairness robustness. Generally robust, because the package is easy to defend when framed as care that actually arrives and can be trusted.

Proof indicator. Useful proof can come from missed-visit rates, continuity measures, workforce turnover, and other indicators showing whether services are becoming more dependable.

Narrative fit. Solid, because the package fits a broader narrative of restoring trust in everyday care, even if it is less emotionally immediate than some of the other packages.

15. Labour Market Integration: Reducing Precarity and Barriers to Sustainable Employment. EU Policy Packages.

Why This Domain Matters

Labour market integration is not only an economic issue but a central domain through which citizens experience security, opportunity, and fairness in everyday life. As developed in Part I, when access to stable employment, progression, and fair rewards becomes uncertain or uneven, this can generate forms of gendered positional deprivation, particularly where structural constraints shape trajectories differently for women and men. Where such conditions persist without visible institutional response, they may also contribute to a representation gap, as labour market institutions are perceived as insufficiently responsive to the challenges of securing sustainable and meaningful employment.

What Citizens Told Us Across Europe

Labour market integration is somewhat more unevenly discussed in our focus groups and participatory workshops but still widely relevant. In the UNTWIST countries (Spain, UK, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary), discussions frequently link the issue to economic insecurity and to the precarious position of younger generations. In Denmark, participants complain about companies relocating abroad and about immigrants failing to integrate despite opportunities; workshops add language and vocational training as crucial factors. In Germany, focus groups—especially women's groups—express fears of unemployment amid wider economic uncertainty, though workshops do not address the theme. In Hungary, the issue is less about entering the labour market than about the poor rewards it offers: low wages, insecurity, and a persistent gender pay gap dominate. In Spain, this is a central theme: participants lament precarious employment and the difficulty young people face in gaining independence, with workshops emphasizing pensions and long-term insecurity. In the UK, men in particular worry about automation and the mismatch of their skills with future labour demands, while workshops mention job protection and childcare-linked flexibility.

Gendered Experiences of Housing Insecurity

Gender differences are pronounced in the narratives of women and men, reflecting distinct and substantively significant gendered grievances. Women's accounts of labour market integration highlight fragmented and precarious trajectories shaped by care obligations and institutional constraints. Part-time work, temporary contracts, interrupted careers, and limited progression opportunities are recurrent themes, and successful integration is defined not only by employment itself but also by sustainability, dignity, and compatibility with family life. Men's narratives, by contrast, emphasize employment stability, income, and occupational status, and tend to assume a more linear model of labour market participation. Setbacks are generally attributed to economic conditions rather than to caregiving responsibilities or gendered barriers, which are rarely foregrounded.

What the Survey Evidence Shows

From a quantitative point of view, the UNTWIST survey shows that "integrating successfully into the labour market" emerges as a relevant but more unevenly prioritised issue across the six countries examined. As shown in the Figure 22, the topic reaches its highest prominence in Hungary, where it ranks particularly strongly among MR voters and remains salient among RWPP electorates. It is also highly visible in Spain, where concerns about labour-market access and secure employment occupy upper-tier positions across party families. In Switzerland, the issue holds a mid-level position across voter groups, while in the United Kingdom and Germany it appears as a secondary but still recognised concern. Denmark records the lowest ranking positions overall, although the issue remains present within the broader landscape of socio-economic priorities.

The overall pattern indicates that labour market integration constitutes a cross-cutting socio-economic issue, although with greater variation across countries and voter groups than the previous topics. Concern is visible across ideological blocs, but no single country or party-family pattern dominates across the cases examined. Its salience appears to depend on the specific forms of insecurity emphasised in different contexts, including access to employment, job quality, low wages, skills mismatches, and opportunities for long-term stability.

Gender differences are visible but less uniform than in the domains of care or work–family reconciliation (Figure 23). In several cases, women report higher levels of concern than men, particularly where labour-market participation is closely linked to precarious trajectories, interrupted careers, or limited progression opportunities. At the same time, qualitative evidence suggests that women and men often attach different meanings to successful labour-market integration: women more frequently emphasise sustainability, dignity, and compatibility with family life, whereas men more often stress income security, occupational status, and stable employment. These contrasts indicate that differences lie not only in the level of concern, but also in the social experience and interpretation of labour-market opportunity.

Figure 22. Ranking of "Integrating successfully into the labour market" as the most challenging aspect of life for people like them among RWPP, MR, and ML voters

Figure 23. Total percentage of voters (broken down by gender) who believe that "Integrating successfully into the labour market " is the most challenging aspect of life for people like them

From Diagnosis to Policy Action

Taken together, these patterns position labour market integration as an important shared priority, but one with weaker overall consensus and sharper contextual variation than healthcare, housing, or family–care themes. The issue therefore reflects not only access to employment itself, but also broader questions of economic security, social mobility, and the capacity of labour markets to provide sustainable and meaningful life chances.

The following sections presents priorities, policy packages, and recommendations in concise form. Extended analytical material for each domain is available in the supplementary material online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

15.1. Policy Priorities of Labour Market

Purpose of This Section

This section identifies the policy priorities for the labour market by moving from the concerns presented in the previous section to the bottlenecks that most consistently structure dissatisfaction in this field. Its purpose is not to restate the evidence already discussed, but to carry out the intermediate analytical step described in Section 9.1: translating politically salient concerns into analytically defined problem clusters that can support policy development.

Drawing on the analytical framework set out in Part I, this step is essential to understanding how labour market pressures are not only experienced as practical constraints but also as structurally patterned forms of disadvantage. In this sense, bottlenecks capture the points at which these pressures become most visible and consequential in everyday life. The organisation of employment trajectories—entry

conditions, opportunities for progression, and the availability of credible reintegration pathways—shapes experiences of stability and insecurity in ways that can contribute to gendered positional deprivation, particularly where risks and constraints are unevenly distributed across social groups, and to a representation gap where labour market institutions are perceived as insufficiently responsive to the challenges of securing sustainable and forward-looking employment trajectories.

In this field, that analytical step requires distinguishing between three interrelated but analytically distinct pressures: whether entry into employment leads to stable trajectories, whether access to learning supports real mobility and progression, and whether those facing structural barriers or economic disruption are reconnected to work through credible pathways.

The section therefore retains only those problem clusters that are both empirically supported and plausibly open to EU-level influence.

Retained Policy Priorities

Figure 24 shows a summary of the four policy packages developed within this domain of Labour Market for each of the policy priorities that are retained in the analysis.

Figure 24. Policy priorities and packages for Labour Market (excerpt from Figure 9)

On the previous basis, three policy priorities are identified for the labour market:

- Transitions into stable jobs.
- Training participation that supports mobility and progression
- Inclusion of disadvantaged groups and workers facing disruption.

Policy Priority 1: Transitions into Stable Jobs

Why This Is a Priority

Across the project material, labour-market dissatisfaction is most consistently associated with the weakness of entry and transition pathways. Read analytically, these concerns point not only to difficulties in finding work, but to a recurrent bottleneck in the conversion of labour-market entry into stable employment trajectories. In this sense, what appears in the qualitative and survey material as repeated churn, temporary work without progression, or the sense that getting in does not lead anywhere can be interpreted as the visible expression of a broader structural problem: early and precarious transitions often fail to generate cumulative security, making labour-market participation feel provisional rather than developmental.

From the perspective developed in Part I, these dynamics are not only economic but experiential. When effort does not translate into stability, individuals may perceive their position as increasingly insecure and unfair, contributing to forms of gendered positional deprivation, particularly among younger workers and those in more fragmented career paths. Where such trajectories are widespread and insufficiently addressed, they may also weaken perceptions of institutional responsiveness, reinforcing a representation gap in how labour market policies are experienced.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative evidence supports retaining this problem cluster as a priority. In 2024, 11% of young people aged 15–29 in the EU were neither in employment nor in education and training, indicating that blocked entry remains a real and measurable phenomenon, particularly pronounced in Spain (19.3%) and Hungary (12.1%).⁵² But the NEET rate captures only the most visible segment of the problem: it does not reflect the much larger share of young workers who are in employment but on precarious terms. In 2023, 43.4% of employed people aged 15–24 in the EU were on temporary contracts — in Spain the figure reached 52.9%.⁵³ The EWCS 2024⁵⁴ confirms that younger workers disproportionately report lack of job security, limited control over their

⁵² Eurostat. (2025, May). *Statistics on young people neither in employment nor in education or training*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Statistics_on_young_people_neither_in_employment_nor_in_education_or_training.

⁵³ Eurostat. (2025). *Temporary employees as percentage of the total number of employees, by sex, age and citizenship (%) [Data set]*. European Commission. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>.

⁵⁴ Eurofound. (2025). *European Working Conditions Survey 2024: First findings*. Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a97b37dd-beb8-11f0-a612-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>.

work situation, and fewer prospects for advancement, all of which feed the sense that effort does not lead to stable outcomes. Underemployment adds a further layer of constraint. In 2024, 18.3% of EU part-time workers reported that they could not find a full-time job, rising to 22.1% in Hungary and 46.6% in Spain, with higher rates among men than women. This suggests that barriers to secure employment do not end once young people enter the labour market, but often persist through involuntary part-time work and limited opportunities to progress into stable and adequate employment. Taken together these data confirm that the bottleneck is not only at the point of entry but extends across the transition from precarious to durable employment.

Implications for EU-Level Action

For that reason, transitions into stable jobs are retained here as a policy priority. They represent a recurrent bottleneck that is empirically supported, clearly linked to lived dissatisfaction, and relevant for EU-level option development around entry pathways, transition support, and the quality and durability of initial employment trajectories.

Policy Priority 2: Training Participation That Supports Mobility and Progression

Why This Is a Priority

A second recurring pattern in the material concerns the role of skills and learning in shaping labour-market prospects. Taken analytically, the issue is not simply whether training exists, but whether participation in learning is sufficiently accessible, relevant, and recognisable to function as a real channel of mobility and progression. In this respect, recurring references to blocked advancement, weak returns to effort, or the limited practical value of available training can be read as the visible manifestations of a broader structural weakness: a bottleneck in the capacity of upskilling and reskilling opportunities to translate into labour-market movement that people can perceive as credible.

As outlined in Part I, when access to meaningful progression is constrained despite individual effort, this can shape perceptions of fairness and opportunity in ways that contribute to gendered positional deprivation, particularly where access to training is uneven across education levels, contract types, or care responsibilities. Where these constraints remain visible and unresolved, they may also contribute to a representation gap, as institutions are perceived as failing to support credible pathways for advancement.

Comparative Evidence

Comparative evidence reinforces this interpretation. In 2022, 46.6% of adults aged 25–64 in the EU participated in formal or non-formal education and training in the previous 12 months. However, participation is highly unequal: among low-educated adults, participation rates fall to around 19% in Germany and 13% in Hungary, well below the EU average — meaning that those with the greatest need for upskilling are the least

likely to access it.⁵⁵ Besides, across the EU pronounced inequalities are evident in participation in education and training, with professionals recording markedly higher rates (48.9% of males and 51.9% of females) than service and sales workers (33.0% and 31.2%, respectively) and elementary occupations (21.4% and 17.3%). Gender disparities persist unevenly, particularly disadvantaging women in lower-skilled role.⁵⁶ The EU Labour Force Survey⁵⁷ further shows that participation in employer-provided training is strongly correlated with contract type: workers on temporary contracts are significantly less likely to receive training than their permanent counterparts, compounding the transition bottleneck identified above. The EWCS 2024 confirms this pattern at the individual level: workers who report having no access to training or development opportunities at work are more likely to feel stuck, undervalued, and likely to leave employment — particularly in lower-skilled occupations in Hungary and Spain. These data matter because they show that the problem is not the absence of learning as a policy field, but the persistence of structural gaps in who can participate, under what conditions, and with what payoff.

Implications for EU-Level Action

Training participation is therefore retained as a policy priority because it captures a recurrent mobility constraint that is empirically grounded, analytically distinct from entry problems, and relevant for EU-level option development around access to training, recognition of skills, and progression across employers and sectors.

Policy Priority 3: Inclusion of Disadvantaged Groups and Workers Facing Disruption

Why This Is a Priority

A third recurring problem cluster concerns what happens when people face structural barriers to employment or are displaced by economic change. Read analytically, the issue is not only exclusion in a static sense, but a recurrent bottleneck in reintegration pathways, particularly for those whose attachment to the labour market is fragile or has been disrupted. In this sense, what appears in the material as drift between inactivity and low-quality work, weak support after restructuring, or the sense that some groups are left behind can be interpreted as the visible expression of a broader institutional constraint: labour markets do not always provide timely and effective routes back into employment for those who encounter cumulative disadvantage or sudden disruption.

From the perspective developed in Part I, these patterns are closely linked to how inequality and disadvantage are experienced over time. When reintegration pathways are weak or uneven, they can reinforce gendered positional deprivation, particularly for

⁵⁵ Eurostat. (2024, March). *Adult learning - participants*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Adult_learning_-_participants.

⁵⁶ Eurostat. (2024). *European Union Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS)*. Publications Office of the European Union.

⁵⁷ Eurofound. (2025). *European Working Conditions Survey 2024: First findings*. Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a97b37dd-beb8-11f0-a612-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>.

groups facing multiple or compounding barriers. Where institutional responses are perceived as insufficient or inaccessible, these dynamics may also contribute to a representation gap, weakening confidence in the capacity of labour market systems to provide fair and inclusive opportunities.

Comparative Evidence

This interpretation is supported by the wider logic of the evidence presented above. The EU Labour Force Survey shows that in 2024 the unemployment rate for people with disabilities stood at 9.5% across the EU — well above the rate for people without disabilities (6.0%) — and that inactivity rates remain above 45% for this group in several Member States.⁵⁸ For people born outside the EU, the employment rate gap relative to native-born workers averaged 9.5 percentage points in 2023, with particularly wide gaps in Denmark (15.6%) and Germany (11.2%) — two of the project countries.⁵⁹ Older workers facing displacement show similar vulnerabilities: the EU-SILC data show that the risk of poverty or social exclusion rises sharply among older adults, reaching 20.8% for people aged 50–64 across the EU in 2024, with rates above the EU average in Hungary and Spain.⁶⁰ The EWCS 2024 confirms that workers in routine manual and clerical occupations — those most exposed to automation-driven disruption — are the least likely to report having access to retraining, career guidance, or transition support from their employers.⁶¹ Taken together, these data confirm that exclusion is not a residual or marginal phenomenon: it is a structural outcome of compounding disadvantages that labour-market and social protection systems currently do not adequately address.

Implications for EU-Level Action

Inclusion of disadvantaged groups and workers facing disruption is therefore retained as a policy priority because it identifies a recurrent and institutionally significant source of dissatisfaction, closely linked to perceived unfairness and system credibility, and relevant for EU-level option development around reintegration pathways, targeted support, and managed transitions.

⁵⁸ Eurostat. (2025). *Disability statistics – unemployment and people outside the labour force*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Disability_statistics_-_unemployment_and_people_outside_the_labour_force.

⁵⁹ Eurostat. (2025). *Migrant integration statistics – labour market indicators*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Migrant_integration_statistics_%E2%80%93_labour_market_indicators.

⁶⁰ Eurostat. (2025). *Living conditions in Europe – poverty and social exclusion*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Living_conditions_in_Europe_-_poverty_and_social_exclusion.

⁶¹ Eurofound. (2025). *European Working Conditions Survey 2024: First findings*. Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a97b37dd-beb8-11f0-a612-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>.

15.2. Policy Recommendations

Purpose of the Policy Packages

The four policy packages presented in this section respond to the three priorities identified in Section 15.1: improving transitions from precarious entry into stable employment, widening access to training that generates real mobility and progression, and strengthening reintegration pathways for disadvantaged groups and workers facing disruption. Each package is developed as an EU-plausible intervention, drawing on the Reinforced Youth Guarantee, the European Skills Agenda, ESF+ financing, and the coordination capacity of the European Labour Authority and the European Semester, and evaluated against the criteria of feasibility, impact, and communicative potential. A common thread across the packages is the need to move beyond formal access: the EU's added value lies not only in setting standards or funding programmes, but in making transitions credible—so that effort leads somewhere, learning leads to recognition, and disruption does not become permanent exclusion. Packages are ordered from highest to lowest weighted score.

How the Packages Are Assessed and Ranked

In line with the analytical framework developed in Part II, these policy packages are designed to address the mechanisms through which labour market constraints are experienced and interpreted in everyday life. By targeting entry pathways, access to meaningful training, and reintegration opportunities, they aim to reduce the conditions that contribute to gendered positional deprivation, particularly where instability, blocked progression, or unequal access to opportunities affect different groups unevenly. Their relevance is therefore not only technical but also political: their effectiveness depends on their capacity to produce visible and credible improvements in employment trajectories, thereby strengthening perceptions of institutional responsiveness in a domain central to autonomy, security, and future prospects.

Table 5. List of policy packages on labour market, ordered by weighted scores

Proposal package	Feasibility (1–5)	Impact (1–5)	Communicative potential (1–5)	Weighted score
Quality First Jobs for Young People	4	5	4	4.4
A Skills Passport Employers Can Trust	4	4	4	4.0
Clear Pay and Progression at Entry	4	3	5	3.9
Early Support for Job Transitions	3	4	4	3.7

Why These Packages Matter

By improving transitions into stable employment, widening access to training that supports real mobility and progression, and strengthening reintegration pathways for

disadvantaged groups and workers facing disruption, these measures aim to enhance institutional responsiveness in a domain central to everyday life, thereby reducing the plausibility of blame-based and scapegoating narratives built on unresolved labour-market insecurity, blocked advancement, and persistent exclusion from sustainable employment trajectories.

POLICY PACKAGE 1: Quality First Jobs for Young People

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 5 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.4)

About: This policy package aims to improve the quality of young people's entry into the labour market by ensuring that first-job support leads to paid, structured, and credible opportunities rather than repeated low-quality placements. Building on the Youth Guarantee, it would establish a clearer EU standard for what counts as a good offer: a paid placement, a written training plan, proper supervision or mentoring, a maximum duration, and a visible route either to a contract or to a recognised qualification. The EU would not hire young people directly or redesign national labour markets. Its role would be to define the quality framework, attach EU support and monitoring to compliance, and make outcomes more comparable across Member States. The package responds to a very visible frustration: for too many young people, entering work still does not mean entering a stable path. Its purpose is therefore to make first-job support more credible, more consistent, and more clearly linked to progression.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – transitions into stable jobs.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. The package fits well with EU competences because it relies on coordination, common standards, and conditional funding rather than on harmonising national labour markets or wage-setting systems.

Instrument readiness. Existing policy anchors, especially the Youth Guarantee and EU-level quality references for traineeships and apprenticeships, make this package realistic as an upgrade to current delivery rather than as an entirely new institutional architecture.

Administrative/data burden. The burden is moderate. Implementation would require common reporting on placement quality and conversion outcomes, as well as safeguards to prevent low-quality offers from simply being re-labelled as compliant.

Time to visible result. Results could become visible relatively quickly if success is measured through compliance with the quality standard and through conversion outcomes within 6 to 12 months, rather than through participation numbers alone.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. A minimal EU definition of a "real first job" should be adopted, centred on pay, a training plan, mentoring, a maximum duration, and a route to contract or qualification. EU support should then be tied to applying that definition and reporting comparable outcomes.

Impact (score: 5)

Population reach. The package has high reach among school-to-work entrants and is especially relevant in labour markets marked by repeated cycles of short contracts or low-quality placements.

Intensity of change. Its likely intensity is high because it targets the early post-education period, when instability can produce long-term scarring effects on earnings, confidence, and labour-market attachment.

Equity effects. The package has strong equity potential because it improves access for young people without strong social networks and reduces the scope for exploitative entry routes.

System spillovers. Wider effects could include better matching and productivity for firms, together with lower churn and disengagement among young workers.

Sustainability. Its sustainability is strong if it shifts incentives away from placement volume and towards stable conversion, thereby reducing the risk that young people are trapped in recurrent holding patterns.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Conversion to stable employment should be the headline metric, and anti-substitution safeguards should ensure that subsidised placements do not displace regular jobs.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. The message is straightforward: your first step into work should be paid, real, and lead somewhere.

Attribution clarity. Attribution is credible if the EU presents its role accurately: it sets the quality standard and links support and monitoring to delivery, while Member States remain responsible for implementation.

Fairness robustness. The fairness frame is robust because anti-exploitation language travels well across ideological and electoral divides.

Proof indicator. Communication would be strengthened by publishing conversion rates, the share of offers meeting the quality standard, and churn or drop-out indicators.

Narrative fit. The package fits well within a broader “learning as a doorway into stable work” narrative.

POLICY PACKAGE 2: A Skills Passport Employers Can Trust

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 4.0)

About: This policy package aims to make short, job-relevant learning easier for employers to understand and trust across Europe. It would do so through a simple Skills Passport that records learning outcomes in a clear, portable, and verifiable format, especially where skills are acquired through micro-credentials and other shorter forms of training. The EU’s role would not be to harmonise national education systems,

but to create a common standard for how skills are described, verified, and presented so that they can travel more easily across employers, countries, and digital platforms. The package addresses a practical barrier in labour-market mobility and progression: many people acquire useful skills, but those skills often do not travel well enough to be recognised quickly and confidently in hiring decisions. The aim is therefore to provide a common trust layer that reduces friction in recognition and makes shorter learning pathways more usable in practice.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 2 – training participation that supports mobility and progression.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. This package fits strongly with EU competences because portability, verification, and common standards are areas where EU-level coordination adds clear value.

Instrument readiness. Relevant foundations already exist in current EU work on micro-credential standardisation and digital credential infrastructure, which makes it plausible to extend these tools into a passport model.

Administrative/data burden. The burden would be medium. Adoption and quality assurance require coordination, but common standards should reduce fragmentation and duplication over time.

Time to visible result. Visible effects could emerge at medium speed, particularly in priority sectors where employers face shortages and faster recognition of relevant learning can improve recruitment.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. The passport should remain minimal and practical. A sensible route would be to begin in a small number of shortage sectors and require that included credentials meet core EU standard fields such as issuer identity, learning outcomes, workload, and verification method.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. The package has broad potential reach, including young workers, career changers, displaced workers, and mobile citizens.

Intensity of change. Its likely intensity is moderate to high where skill mismatch is a binding constraint, although the effect will depend on whether employers genuinely trust the format and whether the recorded skills are labour-market relevant.

Equity effects. Equity potential is significant if the passport strengthens the signal value of non-traditional pathways rather than merely increasing the number of credentials in circulation.

System spillovers. Wider benefits could include better matching, shorter vacancy duration, lower hiring frictions, and easier mobility across sectors and countries.

Sustainability. Sustainability would be high if the passport becomes a default trust mechanism embedded in hiring and progression decisions rather than an additional bureaucratic layer.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Success should be tied to labour-market outcomes such as time-to-hire, progression, and vacancy filling, rather than to the number of credentials issued.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. The core message is clear: show what you can do in a format employers can verify and trust.

Attribution clarity. Attribution is relatively clean because the EU can plausibly claim responsibility for providing the common portability and verification framework.

Fairness robustness. The fairness argument is robust when framed as fewer paperwork loops and fewer situations in which workers have to “prove it again” every time they move.

Proof indicator. Communication should rely on adoption rates, employer recognition, and evidence of faster matching outcomes.

Narrative fit. The package fits well within a “skills that travel” narrative.

POLICY PACKAGE 3: Clear Pay and Progression at Entry

Proposed score: Feasibility 4 / Impact 3 / Communicative potential 5 (weighted score: 3.9)

About: This policy package aims to make entry-level work clearer, fairer, and easier to enforce. Its core idea is that workers should know the pay or pay range before accepting a job and should also have a basic understanding, from the outset, of what happens next—whether that means progression, review points, or the route out of an entry-level role. The EU’s role would not be to set wages, but to strengthen transparency and enforceability at the point of hiring and to reduce grey-zone practices that leave workers uncertain about what they are accepting. The package builds on existing EU rules on pay transparency and predictable written information, while supporting their practical use through simple templates and compliance routines, particularly in high-churn entry jobs. Its strength lies in addressing a very common source of frustration at the start of working life: people may receive an offer, but still lack a clear sense of what it pays, what it leads to, and whether it offers any real progression.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 1 – transitions into stable jobs.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 4)

Competence fit. The package has a strong competence fit because it focuses on transparency and predictability rights rather than on shaping national wage-setting regimes.

Instrument readiness. Relevant directives already exist, so the package mainly requires implementation support, practical templates, and stronger compliance emphasis rather than major legislative innovation.

Administrative/data burden. The burden is low to medium. Standard vacancy templates and compliance checks are relatively manageable, with the main constraint likely to lie in enforcement capacity.

Time to visible result. Results could appear relatively quickly because pay-range disclosure and clearer written conditions are directly observable in hiring practices.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. The EU role should remain narrow and disciplined: provide templates, guidance, and inspectorate support, while avoiding any implication that the EU is setting wages. The promise should be enforceable clarity, not “EU wages”.

Impact (score: 3)

Population reach. The package has broad reach, especially among young entrants and workers in high-turnover sectors where information asymmetries are common.

Intensity of change. The likely intensity is moderate. It can improve decision quality and reduce uncertainty, but it does not by itself transform low-wage structures or weak progression ladders.

Equity effects. The equity effect is positive because it particularly helps workers with weaker bargaining positions by reducing hidden-pay traps and unclear conditions.

System spillovers. Wider benefits could include lower churn, better matching, improved trust in hiring, and somewhat stronger retention.

Sustainability. Sustainability is likely to be high if transparency norms become embedded in standard recruitment practices and routine compliance processes.

Strategic guidelines for impact. Implementation should focus on high-failure sectors, and success should be measured through wage growth after 6 to 12 months, conversion to stable contracts, and reduced churn.

Communication (score: 5)

Citizen-legibility. This is the clearest package communicatively: people should know what they will earn before saying yes, and they should know what the next step looks like.

Attribution clarity. The EU can credibly claim a role here because the package is about enforceable transparency and predictability rights at the point of entry.

Fairness robustness. The fairness frame is extremely robust because it reads as a basic rule of decency rather than as an ideological position.

Proof indicator. Strong proof points would include the share of vacancies showing pay ranges, complaint outcomes, and indicators on churn and contract conversion.

Narrative fit. The package fits strongly within a “work that leads somewhere” narrative.

POLICY PACKAGE 4: Early Support for Job Transitions

Proposed score: Feasibility 3 / Impact 4 / Communicative potential 4 (weighted score: 3.7)

About: This policy package aims to support job-to-job transitions when restructuring, automation, or the green transition reshapes local labour markets. Its purpose is to intervene early, before unemployment becomes entrenched, by helping workers move more quickly into new opportunities. It would do so through a standard transition pathway combining a rapid skills assessment, access to vetted training linked to high-demand occupations, and mandatory matching support. The EU's role would be to mobilise solidarity funding quickly, provide a common pathway template, and encourage earlier intervention through coordination, funding alignment, and outcome reporting. The package addresses a highly visible fear in periods of economic change: people do not necessarily reject transition itself, but they do reject being left alone to absorb its costs. Its added value lies in making adjustment more protective, faster, and more credible for those most exposed to displacement.

Political priority with which it connects: Policy priority 3 – inclusion of disadvantaged groups and workers facing disruption.

Evaluation according to the proposed scoring model

Feasibility (score: 3)

Competence fit. The package is EU-plausible because it works through funding, coordination, and common templates rather than through control over firm restructuring decisions.

Instrument readiness. Relevant EU support tools already exist, but activation mechanisms and the standardisation of early intervention still add operational complexity.

Administrative/data burden. The burden is relatively high because delivery depends on coordination across employers, public employment services, training providers, and local labour markets, whose institutional readiness varies significantly.

Time to visible result. Results would likely emerge at medium speed, with meaningful outcomes observable over 6, 12, and 18 months if tracking is built in from the start.

Strategic guidelines for feasibility. A minimal transition pathway should be standardised around assessment, vetted shortage-linked training, and matching support, and it should be connected to the EU instruments capable of moving fastest. Priority should go to regions and sectors facing clear displacement risk.

Impact (score: 4)

Population reach. The direct reach is more targeted than in the other packages, since it focuses on affected sectors and regions, but the issue is politically salient and socially consequential.

Intensity of change. For beneficiaries, the intensity of change can be high because early intervention may prevent unemployment scarring, downward mobility, and long periods of detachment.

Equity effects. The package has strong equity potential if it prioritises workers at highest risk of displacement, especially lower-skilled and older workers who often face steeper barriers to re-entry.

System spillovers. Wider effects could include lower long-term unemployment, better labour reallocation, and reduced social and fiscal costs linked to failed transitions.

Sustainability. Sustainability depends on whether early support becomes institutionalised as a normal part of adjustment policy rather than remaining a reactive, post-layoff response.

Strategic guidelines for impact. The focus should be on sustained re-employment rather than course completion, and any voucher or training component should be conditional on labour-market relevance, provider quality, and employer-linked matching.

Communication (score: 4)

Citizen-legibility. The message is understandable and strong: if your job is disappearing, you should get a fast and credible route to the next one.

Attribution clarity. Attribution is credible if the EU's claim remains disciplined: it can mobilise solidarity support and speed up transitions, but it should not claim to "create jobs" directly.

Fairness robustness. The fairness frame is robust because it presents protection against predictable transition risks rather than resistance to change itself.

Proof indicator. The most convincing indicators would be time-to-next-job, sustained employment at 12 and 18 months, and evidence of progression after re-entry.

Narrative fit. The package fits well within a "transitions that do not punish you" narrative.

CONCLUSION

This Handbook has developed an integrated framework to understand and respond to contemporary political dissatisfaction in Europe from a gender perspective. Its central argument is that the growing support for right-wing populist actors cannot be adequately explained as a purely ideological reaction, but must be understood in relation to the interaction between material conditions, institutional performance, and the ways in which these are experienced through gendered social positions. Where everyday needs remain unmet in domains such as healthcare, housing, care, work–family balance, and labour-market integration, these conditions generate forms of **gendered positional deprivation** that, when combined with limited or poorly perceived institutional responsiveness, contribute to a **representation gap** in which political systems are experienced as distant, unresponsive, or unfair.

Building on this diagnosis, the Handbook has shown that these experiences are not diffuse or unstructured. They concentrate around identifiable **bottlenecks**—points at which institutional arrangements fail to translate into reliable, accessible, and meaningful outcomes in everyday life. By moving from citizen-defined concerns to analytically specified problem clusters, Part II has provided a systematic method for identifying where intervention is both necessary and feasible, linking these bottlenecks to the European Union’s legal, financial, and coordination capacities within a multi-level governance system.

The policy packages presented in Part III **operationalise this framework** across the five core domains. Their purpose is not only to improve policy performance in technical terms, but to address the mechanisms through which dissatisfaction is produced and interpreted. By targeting access, affordability, continuity, and credible progression, they seek to ensure that effort leads to tangible outcomes, that risks do not translate into lasting disadvantage, and that institutional support is experienced as reliable and fair. In doing so, they aim to strengthen **institutional responsiveness** in areas central to everyday life, thereby reducing the plausibility of **blame-based and scapegoating narratives** built on unresolved insecurity and perceived neglect.

The contribution of this Handbook is therefore twofold. Substantively, it identifies priority areas for intervention that are grounded in empirical evidence and aligned with EU competences. Analytically, it offers a framework for linking lived experience, institutional design, and political interpretation, showing how improvements in material conditions can reinforce **democratic legitimacy**. This is particularly important in a context where dissatisfaction is often mobilised through simplified narratives that attribute complex structural problems to easily identifiable targets.

Ultimately, the findings point to a clear implication for European policymaking. Restoring confidence in democratic institutions does not depend only on communication, nor only on normative commitments, but on the capacity to deliver **visible and credible improvements** in the conditions that shape everyday life. In this sense, the task is not to counter dissatisfaction at the level of discourse alone, but to address the structural conditions that sustain it. Where institutions are able to do so—by making support accessible, outcomes reliable, and responsibilities fairly shared—the link between citizens and democratic governance can be strengthened in a durable and politically meaningful way.

Readers seeking fuller supporting analysis and extended domain chapters may consult the accompanying supplementary material online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19604243>).

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